

DEDICAT 6G

DEDICAT 6G: Dynamic coverage Extension and Distributed Intelligence for human Centric Applications with assured security, privacy and Trust: from 5G to 6G

Deliverable D6.3
Final pilot results,
best practices and guidelines

Project Details

Call	H2020-ICT-52-2020
Type of Action	RIA
Project start date	01/01/2021
Duration	36 months
GA No	101016499

Deliverable Details

Deliverable WP:	WP6 Proof of concept and demonstrators
Deliverable Task:	Task 6.1: Integration and proof of concept setup Task T6.2: Pilot studies execution and validation Task T6.3: Lessons learnt
Deliverable Identifier:	DEDICAT6G_D6.3
Deliverable Title:	D6.3 Final pilot results, best practices and guidelines
Editor(s):	Drazen Ribar (ADS)
Author(s):	ALL PARTNERS
Reviewer(s):	F. Carrez (UoS)
Contractual Date of Delivery:	31/12/2023
Submission Date:	14/02/2024
Dissemination Level:	PU
Status:	Final
Version:	V1.0
File Name:	DEDICAT_D6.3_Final_Pilot_Results_Best_Practices_Guidelines_v1.0.docx

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Deliverable History

Version	Date	Modification
V1.0	14/02/2024	Final version, submitted to EC through SyGMa

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
2D	Two-dimensional
3D	Three-dimensional
3GPP	Third Generation Partnership Project
5G	Fifth-generation wireless
5GC	5G Core
5G SA	5G standalone
5GTN	5G Test Network
6G	Sixth-generation wireless
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
a.k.a.	Also known as
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
ARM	Advanced RISC Machines
ASE	Area Spectral Efficiency
BF-OFDM	Block-Filtered Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
BLEMAT	BLE Micro-location Asset Tracking
BMSC	Broadcast Multicast Service Center
BPM	Broadcast Provisioning Manager
BS	Base Station
BW	Bandwidth
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CAN-BUS	Controller Area Network bus
CE	Coverage Extension
CEaaS	Coverage Extension as a Service
CEDM	Coverage Extension Decision Making
COTS	Commercial (or Component) Off-the-Shelf
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRUD	Create/Read/Update/Delete

CU	Control (or Centralized) Unit
CURL	Client for URL
DB	Database
DDS	Data Distribution Service
DIKW	Data Information Knowledge Wisdom
DL	Downlink
DM	Decision Making
DoA	Description of Action
DTX	Discontinuous Transmission
DU	Distributed Unit
E2E	End-to-End
EC	Edge Computing
EE	Execution Environment
EN	Edge Node
eNB	Evolved NodeB
ESM	Emulated Shared Memory
FC	Functional component
FDD	Frequency Division Duplex
FE	Functional Entity
FG	Functional group
FGPA	Field Programmable Gate Array
gBS	ground Base Station
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GLEW	OpenGL Extension Library
gNB	Next Generation NodeB
GNN	Graph Neural Network
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPIO	General Purpose Input/Output
GPP	General Purpose Processor
GPS	Global Positioning System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HARQ	Hybrid Automatic Repeat reQuest
HD	High Definition
HE	Hosting Entity

HLS	HTTP Live Streaming
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HW (or H/W)	Hardware
IAB	Integrated Access and Backhaul
IAB-DU	IAB-Distributed Unit
IAB-MT	IAB-Mobile Termination
ICMP	Internet Control Message Protocol
ID	Intelligence Distribution
IDaaS	Information Distribution as a Service
IDDM	Intelligence Distribution Decision Making
IoT	Internet of Things
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
ITS	Intelligent Transportation System
JOBPRP	Joint Order Batching Problem and Picker Routing Problem)
K8s	Kubernetes
KNF	Kubernetes-based Network Function
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LDM	Local Dynamic Map
LIDAR	Laser Imaging, Detection, and Ranging
LoS	Line of Sight
LSTM	Long/Short Term Memory
LTE	Long Term Evolution
M	Milestone
MA	Mobile Asset
MAC	Medium Access Control
MANO	Management and Network Orchestration
MAP	Mobile Access Point
MBMS	Multimedia Broadcast/Multicast Service
MBS	Multicast and Broadcast Service
MC	Mission Critical
MC-DATA	Mission Critical – multimedia Data service
MC-PTT	Mission Critical – Push to Talk
MC-VIDEO	Mission Critical – Video service
MCS	Mission Critical Services or Modulation and Coding Scheme (depending on the context)

MCX	Mission Critical Services
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
MIMD	Multiple Instruction Multiple Data
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
MiR	Mobile Industrial Robot
ML	Machine Learning
MPEG-DASH	Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
mmWave	Millimeter wave (band)
MSC	Mass Storage Class
NDM	Nokia Data Marketplace
NEF	Network Exposure Function (5G Core component)
NS	Network Slice
NSA	Non-Standalone
NF	Network Function
NFV	Network Functions Virtualization
NFV-O	NFV Orchestrator
NO	Network Operation
NODM	Network Operation Decision Making
NR	New Radio
NRTK	Network Real Time Kinematic
NST	Network Slice Template
NSST	Network Slice Subnet Template
NW (or N/W)	Network
NWDAF	Network Data Analytics Function (5G Core component)
OBP	Order Batching Problem
OBU	On-Board Unit
OF	Objective Function
OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
O-RAN	Open-Radio Access Network
p/f	Platform
PER	Packet Error Rate
PLR	Packet Loss Rate
PoC	Proof of Concept

PoI	Point of Interest
PPDR	Public Protection and Disaster Relief
PRP	Picking Routing Problem
PS	Physical System
PTP	Precision Time Protocol
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
QR	Quick Response
RAM	Random Access Memory
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAT	Radio Access Technology
REST	Representational State Transfer
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RISC	Reduced Instruction Set Computer
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error
ROS	Robot Operating System
RRH	Remote Radio Head
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator
RSU	Road Side Unit
RTK	Real Time Kinematic
RTP	Real-time Transmission Protocol
RTT	Round-trip Time
Rx	Reception
SA	Standalone
SDN	Software Defined Network
SDN-C	SDN - Controller
SDR	Software-defined Radio
SIMD	Single Instruction Multiple Data
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
SNR	Signal to Noise Ratio
SQL	Structured Query Language
SUC	System Use Case
SW (or S/W)	Software

TCF	Thick Control Flow
TDD	Time Division Duplex
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TSP	Travelling Salesman Problem
TWAMP	Two-way Active Management Protocol
Tx	Transmission
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UC	Use Case
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UE	User Equipment
UEDM	User Equipment (UE/BS/MAP association) Decision Making
UL	Uplink
UML	Unified Modelling Language
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
USB	Universal Serial Bus
USRP	Universal Software Radio Peripheral
V2I	Vehicle to Infrastructure
V2V	Vehicle to Vehicle
V2X	Vehicle to everything
VFF	Virtual Force Field
VM	Virtual Machine
VPN	Virtual Private Network
VR	Virtual Reality
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WCET	Worst Case Execution Time
XR	Extended Reality
μS	Microservice

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Executive Summary

Connectivity is a key element in societal interactions or in fast decision-making, depending on the situation; it has a direct negative impact in case of failure of data or information sharing.

The DEDICAT 6G project has the objective to innovate with intelligent distribution mechanisms and dynamic coverage extension to leverage connectivity, enhance users' experience and increase users' safety. The goal of work package *Proof of concept and demonstrations* was to experiment, evaluate and demonstrate benefits of DEDICAT 6G through four Use Cases:

1. Smart warehousing covers the trustworthy automated real-time monitoring, surveillance, and optimized operation of a warehouse;
2. Enhanced experience provides live streaming applications that use enhanced data overlay in 360°, *Augmented Reality (AR)* applications and *Virtual Reality (VR)*;
3. Public safety (Public Protection and Disaster Relief, PPDR) aims to showcase how resilience of critical communications can be enforced through DEDICAT 6G solutions and how human security can be protected in extreme situations;
4. Smart highway demonstrates how connected and autonomous mobility can benefit from *Beyond 5G (B5G)* and 6G connectivity.

The use cases have been evaluated during the execution of several pilots and demonstrations which were conducted in a real environment.

This deliverable provides a final status on the DEDICAT 6G global architecture, including logical perspective based on inputs from WP2, and components integration based on the mechanisms developed in WP3, WP4 and WP5 into an overall working DEDICAT 6G platform presenting the different project Use Cases. Inputs from WP3, WP4, WP5 and a final overview on implementation of novel interactions between human and digital systems offered to the end-users.

This document concludes on validation results and presents lessons learnt and guidelines for the future implementation of a solution based on DEDICAT 6G outcomes.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This deliverable D6.3 reflects and describes the outcome of the work done in *Proof of concept and demonstrators* work package: experimentation of mechanisms developed in WP3, WP4 and WP5 based on the architecture defined in WP2 and evaluation of KPIs done in laboratory or during the pilots driven through the four use cases of the project.

Deliverable D6.3 outlines results from the final evaluation executed within the task T6.2 "Pilot studies execution and validation" which has started on month M15 and concludes on lessons learnt.

1.2 Structure

The structure of this document is as follow:

- Section 2 provides the final update of DEDICAT 6G platform integration overview and the overall logical platform architecture and its interaction with 5G systems defined in D2.5 [1]. It also summarizes the different mechanisms described in D3.3 [7], in D4.3 [9] and in D5.3 [11] and reports on final evaluation of these mechanisms;
- Sections 3 to 6 present an overall description of, respectively Use Cases, UC1 – Smart warehousing, UC2 – Enhanced experience, UC3 – Public safety and UC4 – Smart highway, scenarios and detailed stories. Furthermore, each of these sections describes for each Use Case the human centric applications/services by integrating innovative interfaces. Each of these sections reports on final evaluation performed during the execution of pilots in the M15-M36 period;
- Section 7 describes the lessons learnt from experimentation conducted during the fourth pilots, recommendation and guidelines about future design and implementation of DEDICAT 6G platform;
- Section 8 concludes the deliverable.

2 Platform integration overview

2.1 Logical overview

In D2.5 [1], a Functional Model and a Functional Decomposition have been elucidated and proposed. While the Functional Model focuses on a layered approach, in organizing classes of functionalities with regard to their inherent focuses and roles they partake within the Platform, the Functional Decomposition provides a catalogue of *Functional Components (FCs)* that populated those layers (a.k.a. *Functional Groups (FGs)*). This functional decomposition offers a **logical** view of which functionalities are needed in the DEDICAT 6G platform in order to fulfil the project technical objectives. In addition, D2.4 provides precise interfaces for the vast majority of the FCs.

When it comes to implementing the platform, the resulting software classes / libraries / modules (say- entities) may differ from the catalogue of FCs introduced by the functional decomposition. Typically, there won't be a 1-to-1 mapping between FCs and implemented software entities, as in the scope of WP6. In DEDICAT 6G, we primarily focus on essential FCs that are necessary to underpin the 4 project Use Cases; this, obviously, includes all functionalities which are part of the 3 project Pillars/Key Enablers as introduced in the project *Description of Action (DoA)* (namely *Intelligence Distribution (WP3)*, *Coverage Extension (WP4)* and *end-to-end Security, Privacy and Trust (WP5)*).

However, the behaviours of those implemented functionalities must be compliant with the behaviours of the logical counter-part FCs they are implementing, as elucidated in D2.5 [1] *System Use Cases (SUC)*. The interface they implement must also be compliant with the logical interfaces described in the Information View of the architecture document (which on purpose, remains language independent).

The aim of this Section 2.1 is then to illustrate and explain this functional decomposition and to introduce the reader to the principles and concepts followed in the DEDICAT 6G architecture work.

We also refer in the following text to the *Data-Information-Knowledge-Wisdom (DIKW)* pyramid model¹ which is sometimes used to show how initial raw data can be enriched/enhanced before ultimately reaching the latest step where decisions are undertaken (Wisdom).

The general way the platform is operating complies with the well-known *Sense-Awareness-Analyse & Decide-Act* loop where:

- **“Sensing”**: is undertaken mostly by agents scattered at the Edge/Far Edge, but also at the 5G System side (NEF, NWDAF), that aim at collecting raw Data (the D in DIKW), adding also some useful meta-data reaching the “I (information)” level of the DIKW model; that information is then forwarded to the next layer (see below);
- **“Awareness”**: is about the collection, aggregation and analysis of information received from the myriad of agents introduced above. They aim to build contexts for the components of the *Decision Making (DM)* FG to use; here we reach the K (knowledge) level of DIKW model. It is worth noting also that different sorts of agents and aggregators are used depending on the nature of the initial raw data. Consequently, we are dealing with *Network (NW)*, *Mobile Access Point (MAP)*, *User*

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/DIKW_pyramid

Equipment (UE), *Edge Node*, *Micro-services (μS)/FC*-related contexts which are in turn used by the various DM components depending on their roles and inner goals. Designing this layer and structuring contexts are paramount as they are expected to characterize the environment as a whole without discarding essential information to be used in the next steps of the loop;

- **“Analysing & Deciding”**: is naturally undertaken by the decision-making components. Based on contexts that give an overall (but still precise with good granularity level) “picture” of the whole system being monitored (in that precise case, the DEDICAT 6G platform including the edges and the supporting legacy 5G network) the service logics embedded in the *decision-making (DM)* components take decision according to their inner objectives (reaching then the “Wisdom” level of the DIKW model). Such objectives are e.g., maintaining appropriate quality of service (QoS), palliating equipment failure, answering an optimization recommendation, providing a service to a vertical etc. What makes the difference between a proactive or reactive DM, depends on how the DM logic is built: if this logic is driven by recurring goals and issues actions (intents) based on internal beliefs embodied into contexts, the behaviour of the DM can be seen as “pro-active”. If its service logic is driven by incoming events and implemented as a rather static set of rules, it would be considered “reactive”. Of course, adopting a hybrid architecture approach -like we do in DEDICAT 6G- is also feasible and sound;
- **“Acting”**: this final step of the loop implements the decisions undertaken by the DMs and is taken care of by several components that are either hosted in the cloud or deployed towards the Edge/Far Edge.

Figure 1 focuses on the DM components, elucidating most of the interactions existing between the “Analysing & Deciding” layer (hosting the DM FCs) and the underpinning “Awareness” (aggregators only) and “Acting” layers. Other FCs which provide essential additional information (mainly registries) to the DM process are also shown.

In Figure 1 we can see that the three DM functional components (in green) are interacting with each other following a “separation-of-duties” principle. The reason for that is that if two different DMs taking their knowledge from the same source would perform independently and especially differently some decision-making activities, most likely two different sets of actions would be issued, resulting in interferences.

Consequently, and as an example, whenever the *Coverage Extension Decision Making (CEDM)* FC is triggered by a *Coverage Extension as a Service (CEaaS)* request from a vertical, the CEDM FC focuses on *Coverage Extension (CE)* matters only and relies on the *Intelligence Distribution Decision Making (IDDM)* FC for the *Intelligence Distribution (ID)* part of the CEaaS request and on the *Network Operation Decision Making (NODM)* FC for network slice dimensioning and provisioning aspects (using the *Service Orchestrator* and *NFV/SDN Connector* FCs). In the same way, if the same NODM FC either detects some equipment failure or receives network optimization recommendations from the *Network Optimization* FC which potentially needs establishment of CE, it relies on the CEDM FC to cover that aspect.

Figure 1: Decision Making and its interactions

This next paragraph elucidates the various FCs involved in that figure and outlines their roles:

- **“Awareness”** (in blue): those components aggregate information into a context that can be used by the DM. It is based on information received from the relating agents:
 - *µS/FC Awareness*: focuses on *µS* and FC at run time (how much resources are used);
 - *Edge Node (EN) Awareness*: focuses on Edge Node and their status in terms of available resources (CPU, RAM, Disk...);
 - *Network (NW) Awareness*: focuses on networking aspects (throughput, capacity, QoS...);
 - *User Equipment (UE) Awareness*: focusses on UE-related information (e.g., perceived signal strength per Base Station (BS)/Mobile Access Point (MAP));
 - *MAP Awareness*: focusses on the status of the MAPs and their nature. It is typically used by the Swarm Operation FC for enabling self-organizing swarm of drones.

Typically, from the two first awareness components it can be deduced 1/ that a EN runs out of resources 2/ that an *Execution Environment (EE)* needs to be reconfigured or 3/ that some μ S/FCs need to be scaled-up and/or migrated to another EE.

- **“Analyzing & Deciding”** (in green):
 - *NODM FC*: the NODM is responsible for monitoring the networking aspects (based on context and Network Optimization-issued recommendations) and may trigger the CEDM if the result of its inner analysis suggests that CE is needed. The NODM is also responsible for dimensioning and provisioning network slices;
 - *IDDM FC*: The IDDM FC primary objective is to find the optimal allocation of Tasks (e.g., FC or μ S) to Edge Nodes depending mainly on μ S/FC and EN contexts. It is also responsible for implementing an IDaaS request. Part of its duties is also the scaling-up or migration of already deployed tasks. Depending on execution indicators it can be decided, for instance, to duplicate or migrate a deployed μ S or FC from one EE to another, which in turn can also involve changing from one edge node (a physical system) to another;
 - *CEDM FC*: The CEDM FC objective is to decide about the physical deployment of 5G-enabled MAPs in order to either implement a CEaaS service or to overcome an occurring problem relating to e.g., coverage, capacity, QoS (WP6 features a quite comprehensive collection of scenarios where such issues can arise). The CEDM FC mostly relies on the MAP Operation FC which is the entity responsible for implementing the CEDM FC's decisions. The MAP Operation FC in turn, relies from the CE operation point of view on various kinds of MAPs such as AGVs (e.g., robots), UAVs (e.g., drones) and Connected Cars, as instructed by the CEDM FC. The CEDM FC delegates to the IDDM FC all aspects involving the deployment of μ Ss or FCs to those MAPs (which are also Edge nodes); As the NODM FC continuously monitors the network performance (see first bullet point above), the CEDM may in turn be requested to reconsider and modify existing MAP deployments at any time;
 - *UE/{BS/MAP} Association Decision Making (UEDM)*: the UEDM FC is responsible for managing the multiple associations existing between a UE and its surrounding MAPs and BSs; this component is deployed in every UE.
- **“Acting”** (in yellow): those components are in charge of implementing the decision taken by the DM process.
 - *ID- or MAP configuration- related*: Load Balancing FC, Service Orchestrator FC and Edge Orchestrator FC are responsible for balancing the execution load inside an EE, between several EEs in an edge Node or even between EEs belonging to different edge nodes; the goal being to provide an optimized and fair distribution of tasks between the EEs and to make sure all FCs, μ Ss and NFs are executed appropriately according to their requirements (see μ S/FC registry) and the agreed *Service Level Agreements (SLA)* (if any).
 - *Network Slicing related*: The Service Orchestrator FC receives from the NODM FC a characterization of the network slice to be provisioned, in the form of a *Network Slice Template (NST)* and *Network Slice Subnet Template (NSST)* which –in a nutshell– defines a set of subnets (with their own deployed Network Functions) and routing between subnets according to the performance

requirements in term of latency, throughput, etc. The two NFV-O and SDN-C Connectors are used to support the Service Orchestrator FC when creating the new slice or expanding an existing slice (more detail about that process is available in D2.5). Those two later FCs are the two components interfacing with the 5G MANO components at the 5G network side;

- *CE related*: a collection of FCs is used to implement (at various stages) the CEDM FC decisions:
 - MAP Operation FC: as we have seen previously, this component is the main entry point to CE operation. It is responsible for implementing the CEDM decision which includes 1/ the MAP configuration, as far as deploying Network Functions is concerned, 2/ some aspects of the network slice(s) life cycle (i.e., activate/ (start | stop)* /deactivate), 3/ the management of the CE service life-cycle depending on the agreed schedule, and 4/ the activation/deactivation of the various MAPs;
 - UAV Operation FC deals with drone operation where each drone is explicitly addressed;
 - Swarm Operation FC provides a high level of autonomy. Drones are able then to spatially organize themselves in order to provide better coverage of a designated geographical area;
 - AGV Operation FC: provides the basic management of robots and provides a basic palette of so-called atomic actions it can perform. Those atomic actions are then played with, in order to build more complex capabilities (e.g., in UC1 with identifying parcels and moving them from A to B with obstacle avoidance or performing quality checks);
 - Connected Car Operation FC: basic management of a non-automatically guided vehicle.

Additional components (in orange) are used to assist the DM process:

- *SLA Repository FC*: encodes an SLA resulting from a negotiation between a DEDICAT 6G platform customer (either CEaaS or IDaaS) and the DEDICAT 6G Platform. This component is also responsible for enforcing SLAs, based on performance indicators brought by the various contexts;
- *EN Registry FC*: contains the characteristics of an edge node with the granularity of the EEs it manages;
- *μS/FC Registry FC*: this essential registry stores the execution requirements for all FCs and μSs that are candidate for deployment to the edge;
- *Edge Computing (EC) Policy FC*: set up constraints on μSs and FCs deployments (if any);
- *Network Optimization FC*: this component -that belongs to the Analytics FG- performs off-line network performance optimization and issues recommendations to the NODM FC.

We discuss now briefly additional components that are essential in any DEDICAT 6G scenario, but which do not interact directly with the DM components, especially agents, and the way they can be deployed towards the edge.

In the DEDICAT 6G architecture, agents come in different “flavours” still following similar deployment strategies. Some examples of “sensing” FCs are introduced below:

- *μS/FC Status Agent FC*: they are responsible for collecting information about the *μS* or FC execution;
- *EN Status Agent FC*: they are responsible for collecting information about a particular Edge Node and its execution environment;
- *NW Status Agent FC*: they are -likewise- responsible for collecting information about networking, focusing on performance and operation.

Figure 2: Hierarchies of agents as used for Edge Computing purpose

The information they provide to their Awareness FC counterparts is used to build-up contexts as explained earlier. However, they can also be deployed hierarchically (see Figure 2), meaning that before reaching out to their counterpart Awareness components (where the context is actually derived) they may propagate their information to an upper-level similar agent. In that case, that Agent ++ (as depicted in Figure 2) compiles a larger status, needed e.g., locally for Load Balancing purpose.

In the deployment example above, we can see several *μS/FC* agents (one per EE) reporting partial information from their own EEs to the *μS/FC* Agent ++ which aggregate it in the same data format. That one in turn provides a bigger view (still at the information level) to the Load Balancing FC which -in this deployment case- is responsible for balancing execution load in

both *Physical Systems (PS)*, even if residing primarily in PS#1. Of course, there could be also one dedicated Load Balancing FC taking care of PS#2 alone.

Each μ S/FC status agent senses any other executed entity within its own EE, including itself (and other agents) since it is an executed entity too and therefore consumes its own amount of computing resources.

A hierarchy of orchestrators is also illustrated in the figure above. The Service Orchestrator residing in the cloud -say the master orchestrator- is instrumenting Edge Orchestrators (only one in that figure) and also both *Network Functions Virtualization – Orchestrator (NFV-O)* and *Software Defined Network – Controller (SDN-C) connectors- Orchestrator* which are then interacting with their 5G system counterparts in order to create new network slices or extending existing ones.

A 3GPP compliant figure in the Deployment view of D2.5 [1], shows in more detail how DEDICAT 6G interacts with the existing 5G system for the sake of coverage extension.

As a final remark, it has probably been noticed that we have not explicitly shown any explicit interaction (arrow) with any Security Privacy and Trust components in the two figures above. As a matter of fact, most of those essential components work in the background and are not necessarily noticed by the Use Case (bar registration and authentication of course), even if they are indeed extremely important for its implementation and safe operation. However, we can mention a few components which are defined in D2.2 and also shown in some of the UML diagrams of D2.3 [2]:

- AuthN, AuthZ FCs: which respectively provide respectively both local or platform-wise authentication and access control (AuthoriZation). Local authentication and access control mean that those components would be deployed at the edge to serve a particular vertical;
- Logging FC: keeps track and store everything about occurring interactions either involving FCs and μ Ss only or involving human actors as well. In combination with the *Nokia Data Marketplace (NDM)*, which is built using a blockchain, non-repudiation can be enforced;
- Data Marketplace FC: it is present literally in any interaction and is used to provide in particular peer-to-peer authentication and access-control. Any interaction, either using *Representational State Transfer (REST) Application Programming Interface (API)* or *Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT)*-like message queues (e.g., used by agents) goes via the DMP and is authorized by the DMP using a so-called dProxy component.

Having introduced the different FCs composing the architecture, we elucidate now some of the mechanisms which are shared by all UCs:

- CEaaS/IDaaS request: such services are requested by a vertical which requires the DEDICAT 6G platform to provide (respectively) Coverage Extension or dynamic intelligence distribution support. The process of requesting such services is widely explained in D2.4 textually and also using precise sequence diagrams. However –in a nutshell- this process consists of:
 1. Invoking the service using a web interface. All parameters which are characterizing the requested service are passed on to the CEDM (for coverage extension) or to the IDDM (when intelligence distribution support is needed but coverage extension not required);
 2. Decision Making FCs analyse the set of parameters (EN provided by the vertical, μ S to be deployed, CE parameters like QoS...) feasibility and perform the needed dimensioning (EN, MAP...);

3. Depending on the conclusion of the previous step, the service is either granted or denied.

This phase is described in the context of the UC2 in D2.5 [1] Section 4.2.2.1 and in its generic form in the system use-case section of the Functional view (Sections 4.3.4.3 to 4.3.4.11 and 4.3.4.12);

- FC and μ S deployment: this phase is the result of the IDDM Task \rightarrow EN allocation procedure and relies on the Service Orchestrator for its execution. The deployment of FCs and μ Ss for all UCs is described as a UML diagram in D2.3 [2];
- MAP configuration and *Network Slice (NS)* provisioning: when a CEaaS is requested, the DEDICAT 6G platform needs to make sure that the CE guarantees that the QoS constraints (max latency, min throughput, number of UEs to serve) are compatible with the network capabilities. This is the CEDM responsibility to select a set of MAPs (eventually from different class and in different occurrences) that fits the requested CE characteristics. The CEDM relies on the MAP Operation for the configuration, execution and operation of the CE.
 1. As for MAP configuration the MAP Operation FC relies on the Service Orchestrator (and Edge Orchestrator) for the deployment of the needed *Network Functions (NF)* into the MAPs (typically, *Integrated Access and Backhaul (IAB)*-related NFs such as IAB-MT and IAB-DU). Doing so, when deployed in the field, those MAPs (then IAB-nodes) are able to connect to their allocated IAB-Donor (located at the gNB-donor side);
 2. As for Network Slice provisioning the MAP Operation FC waits for a confirmation notification from the NODM FC about the slice provisioning. From that point on, the NODM becomes responsible for the whole CE service delivery as explained above.
- MAP and network slice activation/start/stop/deactivation: those four steps of the slice lifecycle are controlled by the MAP Operation using the Service Orchestrator and SDN-C/NFV-O Connectors interfaces;
- Dynamic intelligence distribution: the IDDM is responsible for optimizing the deployment of the μ S and FCs over a set of edge nodes (typically provided by a vertical, and the characteristics of which are part of the request parameters). The optimization algorithm takes into consideration the EN characteristics, execution constraints from the μ S/FC (CPU usage, needed memory, etc...) and various contextual information. The IDDM relies on the Service Orchestrator (in the cloud) and Edge Orchestrator (at the far edge) for distributing the FCs/ μ Ss to the available Execution Environments;
- Load-balancing: this mechanism is implicitly used by all UCs and involves the Service Operation FG components and IDDM. Different scenarios are possible some involving the IDDM if it receives as part of the contextual information alarms relating to degraded execution condition for some FCs/ μ Ss and some relying exclusively on the Edge Orchestrator/Load Balancing FCs (depending on the technologies used). Some FC/ μ S migration scenarios are shown for all UCs in the D2.3 Document using UML use-cases;
- SLA monitoring: when a vertical is granted a service (either CEaaS or IDaaS) the terms of the service are stored by the SLA Registry FC. This component is also responsible for monitoring independently the execution parameters of the FCs/ μ Ss (and also the network condition) in order to detect possible SLA breach. When such breaches occur, they are logged into a blockchain, and a breach notification is sent to the IDDM and/or CEDM (that includes the proof of breach in the form of a context) in order to request corrective measures. When the conditions return to normal, the resulting context is logged into the blockchain too (as a proof of corrective action). The purpose

of the blockchain is to serve as pieces of evidence in case of a dispute being raised between the Vertical and the Service Provider (the DEDICAT 6G platform operator).

2.2 Mechanisms overview

This section summarizes the different mechanisms for supporting dynamic distribution of intelligence described in D3.2 [6] and D3.3 [7] the different mechanisms for dynamic coverage and connectivity presented in D4.2 [8] and D4.3 [9] and the different mechanisms for security, privacy and trust depicted in D5.2 [10] and D5.3 [11]. Those three classes of mechanisms constitute the three project innovation pillars described in the DoA.

2.2.1 Mechanisms for supporting dynamic distribution of intelligence

WP3 addresses the design and development of mechanisms for supporting dynamic distribution of intelligence. It includes architectural techniques for supporting offloading, migration and distribution of computing and communication on processor, storage, and network levels. In order to fulfil the objectives of the project, the DEDICAT 6G platform must enable high availability and quality of service (such as imperceptible end-to-end latency for instance). To this end, it is necessary to move service and network intelligence closer to the end-users. In consequence, intelligence must be distributed towards the edge network, and in order to enable minimal resource consumption, it is necessary to enable the migration of services at the needed times.

In order to support distribution of intelligence in the network, one needs to divide the intelligence (computation and related communication) to parts (threads, processes, services) that execute in parallel/concurrently in multiple execution units (be they different cores of a processor, different processors of a machine, different machines of a cloudlet, different edge servers of a region in a network, or different nodes of the network in general). The number of computational parts often exceeds the number of execution units introducing the need for multitasking, i.e., sharing one or more units between the parts. Efficient multitasking requires efficient *context switching* between the parts targeted to a single execution unit. If computational parts of a single service are executed in multiple execution units, there is need to perform intercommunication between these parts that can form specific *patterns of computation and communication*. There can be a need for *balancing the computational (and communication) load* of the execution units in order to achieve better utilization. One way to do this is to *move computation (threads, processes and services)* between the execution units. Since moving computations translates to communication between execution units, *reducing the state of computation* can increase the performance. If there exist dependencies between the parallel/concurrent parts, one needs to perform *synchronizations* of computation to obtain correct results. If one chooses not to divide the intelligence into parts, the performance will be severely limited. Another dimension of distribution of intelligence is the way how it is done in practice. Does it, e.g., involve programming and if so, how difficult will it be? A metric related to this is called *usability or programmability*. Finally, the *means/algorithms for placing the intelligence* efficiently contribute significantly to how efficient distribution is.

In the following, architectural techniques for improving the behaviour of the system with respect to KPIs and the aspects mentioned above, are considered one by one:

Context switching – Typically, context switching in a *Central Processing Unit (CPU)* relies on interrupting execution of the current thread, waiting until all the operations under execution are completed, saving its registers to the thread table—a data structure keeping the state of the threads while they are not in execution—selecting a new thread for execution, loading the appropriate registers from the thread table and restarting the execution. If the context

switching involves changing of the process too, writing to/reading from the process table, flushing resources keeping critical data and setting up memory spaces and privileges are needed.

While all CPUs are capable of executing multitasking operating systems support switching of threads, the latency of thread switching is typically a few hundred clock cycles. This is not a problem when executing independent threads. However, if the threads of the functionality at hands require dense intercommunication, the performance can be catastrophically poor.

The main mechanisms for accelerating context switching include *Multithreading* [15] and *Thick Control Flow (TCF) execution* [16].

Patterns of computation and communication - Patterns of parallel and distributed computation and communication refer to situations where multiple computational threads interact in a regular way that can be seen as a pattern. The most popular patterns include parallel execution, reduction and spreading and permutation. These are used, e.g., in parallel processing and communication, collection of data, multicasting as well as in certain mapping tasks. There exist a few techniques to speed up these patterns: multioperation [17], broadcasting/multicasting, flexible mapping.

Load balancing - Load imbalance is one of the most important reasons for poor utilization of the computational hardware. In a networked computing system such as DEDICAT 6G, load imbalance can happen, e.g., between the user equipment and the network, between the cloud and edge, or between the edge servers of the same network region. The worst-case scenario for a region of edge servers occurs when a sole server executes everything. Then the execution time of a set of tasks in a region with N servers would be N times slower than perfectly balanced execution where all servers run with the full utilization. The main means for load balancing include work sharing, work stealing, moving threads.

Movement of threads - An essential part of computation offloading, functionality migration and load balancing are the movement of actual computational threads and processes. These include the state of the computation in processor (context) and memory area containing data and executable as well as needed libraries. The baseline technique is to move everything in the computational node to another. The overall latency associated to movement of a thread, set of threads or a process includes the amount of data that needs to be transported, time to move the functionality from one computer to another, downtime needed before a program can be restarted in the target node. These are highly dependent on the part of the network (nodes, routers/switches and communication links) involved in computing and transferring the functionality. More advanced techniques for movement of threads include containers and moving threads [18] [19].

Reducing the state of computation - The state of computation at processor level is directly proportional to the latency of moving/migrating computation in the network. The smaller the state is, the faster the movement gets. The most popular model of Flynn's Taxonomy of parallel execution [20] is the *Multiple Instruction Multiple Data (MIMD)* model. In this model, multiple threads are executed in multiple processor cores in parallel. The main problems of the MIMD execution are that the state of computation is fully replicated for each thread of execution and that providing a (unique) program for each thread can be tedious if the number of threads is high. There exist, however, alternatives to the MIMD model, but they also come with limitations. The most interesting ones include *Single Instruction Multiple Data (SIMD)* [20] and TCF execution [16].

Synchronization - Synchronization is the key mechanism to ensure the correct behaviour of parallel and distributed software at hands in the case of inter-thread dependencies. Unfortunately, in current multicore systems the cost of synchronization can be very high. The main

reason for this is the asynchronous nature of execution in multicore CPUs, computers with multiple processor sockets, clusters of computers and especially in the network. A notable fact is that the need for fast and efficient synchronizations is much more stringent in fine-grained parallel computing than in coarse-grained distributed computing that is not supposed to be able to execute fine-grained parallel algorithms efficiently. The low-level mechanisms to support synchronization include barrier synchronization and wave synchronization mechanisms [21][22].

Programmability - A processor can be said to have good programmability if the functionalities can be expressed compactly and naturally without unnecessary architecture-dependent constructs. An important factor of programmability is also portability and ability to retain speedup with respect to the number of execution units among a group of processors using the same paradigm/approach, but having different hardware implementation parameters. The main challenges of current systems include the asynchronous nature of execution and sensitivity to non-trivial memory access patterns. Distributed systems, such as regions of edge servers, pose additional challenges to programmability since the latencies are much higher, throughputs much lower than those in clusters or parallel machines. Programmability is an important performance indicator since it is directly proportional to productivity of software development, and thus the cost of the software. A known method to address this challenge is to use *Emulated Shared Memory (ESM)* architecture [22][23].

Placement of data and functionality - The best performance is achieved when the right data is in the right place at the right time since moving both data and computation, i.e., execution of operations takes time. Additional complications come from the fact that the farther away data is from the place where it is needed, the longer time it takes to obtain it and the more dependencies there are, the longer it takes to execute if there are resource limitations. Even more complications can come from possible contention of traffic in the network caused by non-optimal placement of data and functionality in the network, reliability issues potentially requiring resubmissions, protocol issues, deadlocks, livelocks, race conditions, sequentialization, physical defects, noise etc. Current multicore systems are highly sensitive to data and functionality placement. These phenomena are augmented in the distributed computers such as cloudlets and regions of edge servers due to high latencies and limited bandwidths. The main software techniques to reduce the performance penalties are matching the software parallelism with the hardware one and the blocking technique [23].

Placement Algorithms - Another aspect of distribution of intelligence is the choice of where to place the computing tasks or the data. In addition, different services may have different requirements, so the placement algorithms must consider all the service requirements (such as maximum end-to-end latency, or minimum throughput, for instance), along with other constraints such as the limited capacity of the nodes. Finally, the placement algorithms must consider the KPIs defined in WP3, namely energy consumption, QoS, Mission Critical QoS, and Service Reliability, along with Use-Case specific ones.

Our plan is to test these techniques in order to see whether we can achieve any speedup/improvement here that would help us to achieve the ambitious KPI related goals of the project. According to our preliminary tests, many of these techniques appear to improve the performance and thus, allow us to achieve better utilization of edge servers/network nodes of the DEDICAT 6G system. We report these techniques in more details in Deliverable D3.2.

2.2.2 Mechanisms for dynamic coverage and connectivity extension

DEDICAT 6G project develops dynamic coverage and connectivity extension mechanisms exploiting multiple types of MAPs for covering areas that cannot be easily reached (e.g., hard geo-morphology such as “forest cave”), where infrastructure, or additional capacity is required only for a finite, short amount of time (e.g., moving hotspots like festivals), or where regular network infrastructure has been damaged (e.g., after an emergency like earthquake, fire, terrorist attack). These mechanisms can be triggered by verticals using Coverage Extension as a Service.

Figure 3 illustrates the implementation of DEDICAT 6G framework for CEaaS. One important feature is the context awareness, the ability to monitor what is happening in the network and the system as a whole, to constantly deduce the current status and whether decision making is required. Another important aspect is related to decision making components, to enable the system to make decisions on the MAPs deployment strategies. This includes making decisions about intelligence distribution (i.e., service placement), network operation (i.e., MAP-UE association and *Radio Access Technology (RAT)* selection) and coverage extension (e.g., MAP and swarm operation).

Figure 3: DEDICAT 6G framework for CEaaS

The context and situation awareness FCs contains several functionalities. These following modules provide essential information for making decisions exploiting MAPs:

- Device discovery module is based on a new type of enhanced IoT devices estimating the number of users in a coverage area by short-range signal scanning techniques (e.g., Bluetooth or Wi-Fi signals). Thanks to the information monitored and collected by the IoT sensing nodes, the backend of the micro-service generates detection chart reporting the history of device detections that have been performed by each of the nodes and real-time heat maps of the occupation by connected and non-

connected users present in the area of interest. Thus, a possible overloading of communication networks due to the presence of a high number of users can be detected.

- Technology recognition module can recognize a wide range of wireless technologies operating in the 5.9GHz ITS band (LTE, 5G NR, WiFi, C-V2X PC5 and ITS-G5) and can use the statistics of each identified technology to estimate and predict the traffic characteristics of each technology and to implement flexible and dynamic spectrum management and utilization.
- *Vulnerable Road User (VRU)* tracking module can track the movement of VRUs on the road or obscured subjects in real-time through camera sensors installed in the road-side unit located at an intersection and warns the driver of a hazardous situation via wireless vehicle-based infrastructure communication.

The CEDM FC proposes several approaches for MAP/UE association:

- A distributed UE association and MAP placement deciding the number and the optimal location of MAPs, which maximizes the throughput and ratio of well served users while minimizing the number of drones deployed and the execution time in sub-6GHz and mmWave bands;
- Heterogeneous MAP-assisted networks with machine learning to maximize the QoS satisfaction level and the energy efficiency by jointly optimizing user association and power allocation under wireless backhaul link capacity constraint in highly crowded areas with heavy traffic loads. Another network operation decision making functionality is the management and configuration of vehicular based MAPs (i.e., RAT selection and configuration based on MAP capabilities, applications/services traffic demands, and/or identified characteristics of the wireless environment).

An AGV mobility management μS proposes an access to an algorithm for robot-based MAPs, finding the path or trajectory that each MAP should follow to reach the target position and the selection of nearby docking/charging stations. The interface dealing with AGV configuration (e.g. Networking) and service management is provided by AGV Operation. It also provides (in this architecture) a set of very basic actions the AGV can perform (although in real-life it would be preferable to consider it as a basic μS). Interface dealing with AGV high-level capabilities (as depicted in D2.3 / UC1 section e.g. "move item "xyz" from place A to place B") should be offered through dedicated μS (because AGV's capabilities vary with AGV types) which can be (re)deployed at will, among available AGVs.

When using a fleet of cooperating UAVs, the Swarm Operation FC performs self-organizing functions as an ad-hoc network (including access and backhaul links), UAV placement, UAV path optimization to achieve placement within the constraints of the CEDM coverage area, and self-management of resources, including autonomy (e.g., how often and where a UAV should return to its docking station).

The IDDM FC proposes assistance to Intelligence distribution in the coverage extension. Intelligence is every software-based part that can consume computational resources available at the nodes of a B5G network scheme. Three types of intelligence can be defined: (i) DEDICAT 6G FC instances assisting the placement optimization and deploying concrete FCs instances along the network depending on the needs, (ii) NFV Orchestration of VNFs in the instantiation of network slices to enable end-to-end 5G/B5G connectivity and (iii) verticals apps/ μS s impacting the coverage extension to guarantee the service.

This CEaaS framework can be optimized specifically for a use-case:

- The context awareness through sensing node network in shared traffic space improves the network orchestration and increases the safety of people, helping to build reliable maps with the location of VRUs;
- The smart highway strategies track VRUs with *Roadside Units (RSU)* for smart Highway scenarios and manage and configure vehicular-based MAPs that offer multi-RAT capabilities. The objective is to guarantee safety of VRUs and to enable harmless coexistence and incumbent technologies protection;
- For enhanced experience of temporary events, different MAP placement and user association strategies are investigated according to the different characteristics of temporary events, multiuser interference scenarios, and different levels of network topology information;
- For public safety, a dedicated mission critical service strategy is investigated to bring critical communications close to the PPDR users and first responders. The objective is to provide on-demand and autonomous network management (i.e., self-configuration, self-healing and self-optimization).

2.2.2.1 Integrated Access and Backhaul platform

In DEDICAT 6G, we investigate state-of-the-art mechanisms for dynamic coverage extension. In addition to the strategies presented in D4.1 [4], D4.2 [8] and D4.3 [9] an additional mechanism is considered: multi-hop backhauling with Integrated Access & Backhaul. With IAB, both access and backhaul links share the same frequency bands. It provides an alternative to optical-fibre backhaul with a cost-effective and rapid deployment over a RAN network. It has been included in Release 16 [31].

We can deploy IAB in order to ensure a minimum coverage for each user equipment even in a harsh and dynamic environment. Such approach is particularly interesting:

- To avoid RF blockages with dynamic deployment of APs;
- To quickly deploy a mmWave network over an uncovered area at limited costs;
- To temporarily densify the number of APs without the need of extra optical-fibres.

Figure 4: IAB Architecture (courtesy Prof Launay, Université de Poitiers, France)

IAB has been proposed with various levels of decentralization. In the project, we consider the standardized version which is depicted in Figure 4. IAB donors are directly connected to the 5G Core network and support *Control (or Centralized) Unit (CU)*-related functions. They usually correspond to fixed APs. IAB nodes support *Distributed Unit (DU)*-related functions and are linked with IAB donors with a backhaul link. IAB nodes can simultaneously forward the backhaul link and provide access to user terminals (Figure 4).

Considering IAB as a coverage extension mechanism in DEDICAT 6G project makes sense as it relies on some project strategies [D6.1][12]. Indeed, the performance achieved by IAB is highly dependent of the context awareness. The knowledge of the coverage quality in real-time is critical in order to anticipate the MAP (IAB donor) deployments. In addition to that, the implementations of IAB we propose, rely on multi-RAT technology with a sub-6GHz and a 26 GHz link. The sub-6GHz can be either a WiFi or a 5G 3.5 GHz link and is used for control signals (mainly telemetry between IAB donor and IAB nodes and feedback on user locations) and for low data-rate signals. The feedback of user locations facilitates the beam steering and avoids the cell search when user equipment wakes up. On the other hand, the mmWave is used for demanding applications (such as HD video streaming). It requires proper beam alignment.

2.2.3 Mechanisms for security, privacy and trust

WP5 addresses *Artificial Intelligence- (AI)* and blockchain-enabled security framework and trust management platform and mechanisms to provide security and trust. D5.1 [5] gives an overview of the interface provided by the framework, D5.2 [10] discusses the initial implementation of the framework and D5.3 [11] contains the final implementation report. The best practices are used to protect confidential data and the blockchain technologies are used to ensure trust between participants.

The DEDICAT 6G security and privacy protection framework is based on a decentralized, blockchain-powered data marketplace for secure, automated processing and exchange of IoT sensors and digital assets data with policy-based data verification and protection.

The framework's unique features for exchange of data between arbitrary interested parties are:

- Private, permissioned blockchain technology which provides network security, data integrity, smart contract for fast automated transactions developed around token economy;
- Data access verification and policy-based access control through blockchain smart contracts and data encryption.

There are three main goals the framework is aiming to achieve:

Security - To protect sensitive data, the framework relies on best cryptography practices for modern cloud-based applications. The sensitive user information such as passwords are stored encrypted using best practices for hashing, so that potential data leak or direct access to the database won't reveal login credentials. Also, the framework does not require storing data streams from IoT sensors and edge gateways, but data can be kept on the data producer side and fetched by data consumer on request. When accessing protected data, data source location (as a *Uniform Resource Locators (URL)*) is protected using best practices for symmetrical encryption.

Privacy - The platform provides not only data exchange, but also subscriptions to continuous data streams (potentially of infinite size) are supported. This is particularly useful for IoT use-cases where data is streamed directly by the edge gateways. All subscriptions are time-limited and access to data is denied upon expiration. To ensure access control over sensitive information, framework relies on attribute-based access control. Attribute-based access control enables creating fine-grained access control rules giving great flexibility to the framework. For some cases, however, role-based access control is a better fit due to its simplicity and long-time use in the industry. Role-based access control is using an artificial attribute(s)

called role in the system to evaluate access control rights. The platform uses roles for determination of high-level access rights and attributes to provide more fine-grained control.

Trust - To ensure trust between parties, the framework uses blockchain technologies. Each data exchange is written to the immutable ledger. Decentralization, advanced consensus algorithms, and ledger immutability are three main properties of blockchain technologies. Support for smart contracts is used to automate the execution of an agreement so that both data consumer and producer can be immediately certain of the outcome. All these properties make blockchain a perfect fit to provide trust between parties who produce and consume data.

One practical use-case for security and privacy protection framework is data monetization in the *Nokia Data Marketplace* which is explained in D5.2 and D5.3. Tokens and Transactions are used to verify data transfer when creating data subscriptions. Tokens are digital assets stored in the blockchain and used for trading assets. The transaction is any exchange of tokens, including funding, defunding, and renting digital assets. Blockchain is used to store tokens in the form of smart contracts and each transaction results in a change of token balance for each participating party, platform included (platform can take a configurable fee from each transaction – also using fee smart contract). While this concept reminds us of the real marketplaces where the real money is exchanged for real goods, tokens are not necessarily used as a monetization tool, but simply the asset that proves the transaction that results in enabling and disabling access to the virtual resource.

Two main benefits of using blockchain as the underlying technology are security and trust that come from its decentralized ledger nature. Blockchain acts as a source of trust between parties. Blockchain is also used to store users' terms and conditions of dataset/stream - that way platform can track eventual changes in data usage terms and condition and provide its integrity which is very important for the end-user.

The implementation of the Security framework for access control management is described in D5.1 and implemented in D5.2 and D5.3. It includes role-based and attribute-based access control to the resources, and data access control supported by blockchain.

In all project Use Cases, the security and trust framework have the same position: central source of identity and trust. All device interactions go through the framework where requested action is authorized against access control policies and allowed if policy evaluation is successful. Clients are authenticated using access tokens and authorized using access control policies. More implementation details can be found in Section 3.1.1 of deliverable D5.2 and in D5.3. Sensors and edge devices, as well as smartphones and web clients of all four project Use Cases, are providing data streams exchanged through the platform which is an implementation of the framework. Users are provisioned by the platform administrators, and users are able to add data streams to the catalogue of available streams. To make them accessible, other users need to generate cryptographically protected data streams out of the original using its location. Each access is recorded in the blockchain ledger, providing trust between client who provides and client who accesses the data.

3 UC1: SMART WAREHOUSING

3.1 Scenario and stories

According to the latest report by the IMARC Group, titled “Warehousing and Storage Market: Global Industry Trends, Share, Size, Growth, Opportunity and Forecast 2022-2027”, the global warehousing and storage market size reached a value of US\$ 451.9 Billion in 2021 and is estimated to reach US\$ 605.6 Billion by 2027, exhibiting at a *Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR)* of 4.9% during 2022-2027 [24]. The COVID-19 pandemic has increased the need for warehousing and storage facilities to cater to the surging demand for numerous essential goods and healthcare products across the globe. Smart warehousing and logistics are key for the proper preservation of goods and consequently of the public health. Today, real-time tracking of vehicles and goods at the transfer points are much consolidated operations, for both end users and companies. However, the availability of data as well as functionalities such as augmented reality and remote-controlled operations, that can be supported by B5G/6G technologies along the warehousing and logistic supply chain, can enable much more advanced services reducing operational delays and wastes (due to disrupted products which do not reach the consumer market). This Use Case intends to demonstrate the feasibility and value of applying distributed intelligence in an overall Smart Warehousing context, for:

- Optimizing warehousing operations with increased performance and improved efficiency;
- Assisting training of new Warehouse Workers and maintenance of warehouse systems through application of 3D augmented reality, promoting human-robot interaction with 3D video-driven solutions;
- Enhancing the safety of personnel and goods;
- Enabling remote inspection and diagnostics;
- Identification and tracking of goods.

This is achieved through an integrated state-of-the-art operational system based on *Automated Guided Vehicles (AGV)*, *Internet of Things (IoT)* systems and edge computation capabilities supporting deployment of DEDICAT 6G enablers through the DEDICAT 6G platform.

In the following more detailed stories are presented focusing on the tasks of key actors in the warehouse setting for showcasing the advantages of DEDICAT 6G enablers in a Smart Warehousing context.

3.1.1 Detailed Stories

The main actors in the smart warehousing scenario are Warehouse Workers focusing on their daily tasks and Warehouse Managers/Administrators focused on improving overall efficiency, performance, and safety by applying new processes, organizing personnel and resources, and remotely monitoring deployed systems. These main actors will interface with the deployed DEDICAT 6G systems and new technology in different ways. Therefore the perspectives of 1) a Warehouse Manager and 2) a typical Warehouse Worker are described in the two stories.

Story 1: This story focuses on a Warehouse Administrator/Manager who is responsible for setting up the strategy for improving performance, efficiency and safety of personnel and stored goods. This person also performs monitoring of the deployed resources and configured processes in order to assess performance and derive necessary updates. Finally, a

Warehouse Manager is also responsible for interaction of the smart warehouse systems with the outside world including the wider supply chain. The assumption is that a Warehouse Manager monitors the operations from a dedicated location/office which might or might not be at the same location as the warehouse itself.

Story 2: This story emphasizes how a typical Warehouse Worker utilizes deployed technologies to perform daily tasks (goods inventorying, goods shipment, training of a new worker, warehouse maintenance, etc.) more efficiently and safely. Warehouse workers are those who directly interact with the deployed AGVs, goods and other warehousing infrastructure. They perform all their activities within the perimeter of the warehouse.

3.1.2 Services – Human centric applications

The Smart Warehousing human-centric application essentially aims to address the needs of the Warehouse manager and the Warehouse worker foremostly. In this direction, two applications have been developed: a dashboard for the Warehouse manager and a mobile application for the Warehouse worker.

Through the **Warehouse Manager dashboard** (Figure 5), the Warehouse Manager can:

- Configure daily tasks for the fleet of AGVs including product quality monitoring parameters, interaction rules with warehouse personnel and product offloading/loading schedule;
- View the overall status of AGVs and processes of the warehouse;
- Direct personnel or AGVs towards an area of interest or an asset;
- Configure safety rules for workers including social distancing and safety zones with configurable geo-fencing zones for different time periods and in line with offloading or loading schedule;
- Configure authorization levels for workers with respect to warehouse areas.

Figure 5: View of Warehouse Manager dashboard

The Warehouse Manager dashboard also allows to view the overall status and processes of the warehouse through dedicated cameras, view notifications e.g., on completed tasks, view precise location of key assets, direct personnel or AGVs towards an area of interest or an asset, view AGV camera feeds, view real time data from the robots such as their status, battery level, availability and other statistical and historical data.

The Warehouse Manager is aware at all times of the robots within the system. In the "Smart Warehouse Context" panel (Figure 5 – left side), robots are constantly transmitting information about their status to the system. In the main window of the application there is an interactive virtual map, through which the movement of robots in the digital space can be observed as well as the positions of objects/products. Live video streaming from the robots camera gives additional information about their position in space, and the tasks they are performing at that time (Figure 6). A Notifications panel & Progress window (Figure 5 – right side) provides the Warehouse Manager with additional information about the running processes. The Warehouse Manager can select a product from the list, and then the robots will work together to perform an automated process of delivering the selected product to a specific point. Information about the progress is provided.

Figure 6: Warehouse Manager dashboard - robot cameras view

The Warehouse Manager can supervise the robots in two-dimensional graphics or in three-dimensional space (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Warehouse Manager dashboard - robots information

In case of possible damage or failure of a robot the circle or "ring" around the robot changes from green to red in the Warehouse Manager dashboard, while a notification also appears informing the Warehouse Manager (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Warehouse Manager dashboard - problematic robot identified

In such a case, if the problematic robot is involved in an ongoing process the intelligence distribution algorithm is triggered (Figure 9) and the services running on that robot are re-distributed. This re-distribution is also visualized in the Warehouse Manager dashboard.

Figure 9: Warehouse Manager dashboard - Intelligence distribution triggered due to robot failure

Through the Warehouse Manager dashboard, the warehouse manager can assign tasks to employees with different priorities and comments (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Warehouse Manager dashboard - Task assignment

The **Warehouse Worker mobile app** (Figure 11), the worker can:

- receive a list of daily tasks as specified by the Warehouse Manager;
- direct AGVs towards a product or an area of interest if he/she is authorized to do so;
- view digital information on real world objects through the **Augmented Reality application** e.g., interact with the 3D model of an AGV or even watch a video explaining how the robotic arm works.

Figure 11: Warehouse Worker mobile application

Figure 12: Warehouse Worker Augmented Reality application for training

The worker training Augmented Reality application combines real world objects with digital information. For example, a specific model of a robot has on its robotic arm a unique *Quick Response (QR)* code. The user will be able to target the QR-code with the camera of his mobile device (smartphone/tablet/AR glasses) and to get access to the robot statistics in real time, to download the user's manual, to interact with the 3D model or even to watch video and animations explaining how the robotic arm works.

3.2 Scenario Setup

This section aims to provide an overview of the pilot setup in terms of hardware and software components, while also outlining the relationship to the DEDICAT 6G architecture as defined in WP2 and the status of the integration of mechanisms from WP3, WP4 and WP5.

3.2.1 Pilot setup

Figure 13 depicts the full setup considered at this time for realization of the Smart Ware-housing use case in the context of a pilot. This setup considers the following:

- AGVs are deployed and configured to support smart warehousing tasks;
- IoT system is deployed and configured to support smart warehousing tasks;
- Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) beacons are provided to *Mobile Assets (MA)*;
- IoT system for access control is connected to electric locks;
- Environmental sensors are connected to the IoT system;
- Personnel is registered and authorized;
- Smart warehousing layout/plan is digitalized;
- DEDICAT 6G mobile app is installed on personnel's mobile devices;
- DEDICAT 6G web-based dashboard is provided to the Warehouse Manager;
- DEDICAT 6G solutions for distributed computing, opportunistic networking and trust and security management are deployed and configured.

Figure 13: Smart warehousing use case setup plan

The **robots/AGVs** utilised in this Use Case are *LoCoBot WX250 6 DOF*. The LoCoBot (Figure 14) is a *Robot Operating System (ROS)* research rover for mapping, navigation and manipulation. Development on the LoCoBot is simplified with opensource software, full ROS-mapping and navigation packages and modular opensource Python API.

Figure 14: LoCoBot AGV

The rover is built on the Yujin Robot Kobuki Base (YMR-K01-W1) and powered by the Intel NUC NUC8i3BEH Core i3 w/ 8GB of ram and 240GB HD. An Intel® RealSense™ Depth Camera D435

sits atop an independently controlled pan / tilt mechanism (2XL430-W250-T) at the top of the platform which allows mapping and scanning. The 360-degree LIDAR can further improve both mapping and scanning (Figure 15).

The WidowX 250 is a 6-degrees of freedom manipulator with a maximum reach of 650mm and a working payload of 250g. The WidowX 250 is built using the DYNAMIXEL X Series servos from Robotis, which features high resolution (4096 positions), user definable PID parameters, temperature and positional feedback and much more.

Figure 15: AGV hardware components

In addition to the AGVs, an automated barrier has been implemented to showcase automated access authorization for robots in parts of the warehouse. This authorization barrier is essentially an IoT device that can interact with robotic devices. It is a custom device that was primarily 3D printed, using a stepper motor to control the state of the barrier (open/closed). It runs Ubuntu + ROS2 on a Raspberry Pi 4B with a fitted 5G modem in order to leverage low latencies. In the scenario, using ZeroTier *Virtual Private Network (VPN)*, the device can then discover and be discovered by other ROS2 devices providing a seamless communication. Finally, for visual purposes and debugging, the device is fitted with a series of LED's that give better information on the communication flow between the barrier and other ROS2 devices.

The **SmartAccess360 (SAC360)** Universal Internet of Everything Controller is specifically designed to offer smart solutions that maximize the performance of Smart Building services. The controller is an integrated multi-radio hardware and software system that acts as a gateway to connect networks of devices, to collect data in real time, and to monitor devices off-site from a smartphone app. SAC360 as an IoT system, is responsible for door access-control and operation of the electric strikes.

Figure 16: SmartAccess360 controller (left) and installation scheme (right)

Table 1: SmartAccess360 specification

Power:	802.3af/at Power over Ethernet (PoE) enabled (Alternative: 5V DC via USB-C connector (minimum 3A))
Physical size:	120mm x 120mm x 50mm (W x L x H)
SoC:	Broadcom BCM2711
CPU:	Quad core Cortex-A72 (ARM v8) 64-bit @ 1.5GHz
GPU:	Broadcom VideoCore VI
RAM:	2GB, 4GB or 8GB LPDDR4-3200 SDRAM
Networking:	Gigabit Ethernet, 2.4 GHz and 5.0 GHz IEEE 802.11ac wireless, Bluetooth 5.0, BLE
Storage:	Micro-SD card (8/16/32 GB)
Ports:	1x Gigabit Ethernet (PoE enabled) 2 USB 3.0 ports 2 USB 2.0 ports 2 × micro-HDMI ports (up to 4kp60 supported) 4-pole stereo audio and composite video port 2-lane MIPI DSI display port 2-lane MIPI CSI camera port 2x Contact sensor inputs 2x Push button inputs 40 <i>General Purpose Input/Output (GPIO)</i> pins, Serial Peripheral Interface Bus (SPI), I ² C, I ² S, [5] I2C IDC Pins at 3.3V; Not all 40 pins are available. Physical pin 5 (GPIO3) used for software reset/power off; Pins 8 (UART0_TXD), 10 (UART0_RXD) used by EnOcean transceiver; Pins 12 (GPIO18) and 13 (GPIO27) used for contact sensor input; Pin 32 (GPIO12 with PWM) used for FAN control; Pins 35 (GPIO19) and 37 (GPIO26) used

	for push button LED control; Pins 36 (GPIO16), 33 (GPIO13) used for driving relays; Pins 38 (GPIO20) and 40 (GPIO21) used for push button input
Relays:	2x embedded relays: Nominal switching capacity (resistive load) N.O. side: 10 A 125 V AC, 5 A 250 V AC, 5 A 30 V DC N.C. side: 3 A 125 V AC, 2 A 250 V AC, 1 A 30 V DC Max. switching power (resistive load) N.O. side: 150 W, 1,250 VA N.C. side: 30 W, 500 VA Max. switching voltage 250 V AC, 30 V DC Max. switching current N.O.: 10 A (125V AC), N.C.: 3 A (125V AC) Expected life: Mechanical Min. 107 (at 180 times/min.)
Environmental:	Operating temperature: 0°C to 50°C
Mounting:	Wall-mounted
Power con.:	Idle: 2.85W Stress: 6.4W
Configuration:	Local Web User Interface (HTTP/S), CLI (Telnet/SSH), Cloud/Web based management and configuration
Monitoring:	Cloud/Web-based monitoring
Software updates:	Over the air (OTA) updates
Frameworks and protocols:	AllJoyn, Project Haystack, SIP, Wireless mesh routing protocol - B.A.T.M.A.N. Advanced
Compliance:	RoHS3 and REACH compliant; FCC ID: 2ABCB-RPI4B; IC ID: 20953-RPI4B; Anatel: 06004-19-10629; KCC: R-C-P2R-RPI4B; NTC: ESD-GEC-1920098C; IFETEL: 2019LAB-ANCE4957; CMIT ID: 2019AJ10494; FCC, CE

The **Bluetooth Low Energy Micro-location Asset Tracking (BLEMAT)** system is a fog computing Internet of Things system based on VizLore's IoT Platform solution and UloE family of IoT controllers.

In the warehouse, BLEMAT platform tracks AGVs Bluetooth beacons and calculates proximity and position of robots. Proximity information is the main trigger for further action. BLEMAT asset tracking capability refers to indoor tracking systems that need to continuously scan and monitor the assets/beacons over a period of time (Figure 17).

Figure 17: BLEMAT system workflow

Asset tracking utilizes trilateration to calculate the exact position of an asset in an indoor area. Where more than 3 controllers are deployed, multi-lateration approach (combinations of more than three points) is used and then the position is averaged. Furthermore, position estimation is enhanced by context-learning and aggressive filtering of both signals and position estimations.

- Decisions are made at the fog level;
- Reactive decision making;
- Failover detection;
- Automatic handover of failing processes.

The cloud layer is used for deeper analysis, overall governance and policy enforcement, should it fail at the fog level.

3.2.2 Smart Warehousing use case implementation

This sub-Section aims to present the implementation of the use case with a key focus on UC specific components.

3.2.2.1 DEDICAT 6G architecture components

The detailed functional decomposition of the interconnection of this Use Case into DEDICAT 6G architecture and platform has been described in D2.3 (typically through UML diagrams), D2.5 and also in D6.1. Table 2 provides a mapping of the functionality of the DEDICAT 6G architecture FCs to the current Smart Warehousing implementation of Figure 18.

Table 2: Mapping of DEDICAT 6G architecture FCs to Smart Warehousing implementation (Figure 18)

DEDICAT 6G architecture FCs	Description	Smart Warehousing implementation
Edge Node (EN) Registry FC	Provides information on the Edge Nodes (including AGVs) that can be exploited for intelligence distribution	Kubernetes, ROS1/2 Bridge, DEDICAT 6G Controller, Warehouse Manager dashboard
μ S/FC Registry FC	Stores the meta-data related to the microservices uploaded in the μ S/FC Repository FC	MANO, Kubernetes
μ S/FC Repository FC	Stores the uploaded microservices images related to the Smart Warehousing such as the Product Quality Check	MANO Kubernetes
Edge Computing (EC) Policy Repository FC	Stores the Edge Computing policies related to Smart Warehousing μ Ss	MANO, Kubernetes, Intelligence Distribution algorithm
EN Status Agent FC	Provides monitored information about the current status of the edge nodes registered to the platform	Kubernetes, Warehouse Manager Dashboard, ROS1/2 Bridge, DEDICAT 6G Controller
μ S/FC Status Agent FC	Provides monitored information about the current status of the microservices and DEDICAT 6G native FCs and Verticals' μ Ss being executed in the use case infrastructure	MANO, Kubernetes, ROS1/2 Bridge, DEDICAT 6G Controller
NW Status Agent FC	Monitors the networking aspects of the Smart Warehousing infrastructure and DEDICAT 6G platform	DEDICAT 6G Controller
IDDM FC	Receives information about the ENs and the microservices and, as output, provides recommendations to the Service Orchestrator FC on the placement, deployment and migration of microservices and FCs	Intelligence Distribution Algorithm
Service Orchestrator FC	Receives recommendations from the IDDM FC and acts over the ENs in order to deploy and orchestrate the microservices and FCs within the Smart Warehousing Physical Systems	MANO

μS/FC Awareness FC	Receives information from a group of μS/FC Status Agent FCs then aggregates/enriches it and finally publishes it to the rest of the FCs available on the DEDICAT 6G platform (mainly Decision-Making FC).	MANO, Kubernetes
EN Awareness FC	Receives information from a group of EN Status Agent FC and enriches/publishes it to the rest of the FCs available on the DEDICAT 6G platform	MANO, Kubernetes
NW Awareness FC	Provides information on the status of the network of the Smart Warehousing infrastructure	DEDICAT 6G Controller
AGV Operation FC	Provides the basic management of robots and provides a basic palette of so-called atomic actions it can perform. Those atomic actions are then played with, in order to build more complex capabilities (e.g., for identifying parcels and moving them from A to B with obstacle avoidance or performing quality checks).	ROS1/2 Bridge, DEDICAT 6G Controller, containerized microservices (docker/ROS)
Threat Analysis FC	Performs threat detection, identification and classification and is executed either in centralized or in edge processing nodes. Threat analysis is based on ML models trained and updated on collected system logs.	Security Mechanism Algorithm

3.2.2.2 UC specific components

This sub-section describes in more detail the UC specific components. The Warehouse Manager dashboard and the workers mobile application are implemented with Unity 3D game engine. Unity is a cross-platform game engine developed by Unity Technologies, first announced and released in June 2005 at Apple Inc.'s Worldwide Developers Conference as a Mac OS X-exclusive game engine. The engine can be used to create three-dimensional (3D) and two-dimensional (2D) games, as well as interactive simulations and other experiences. Unity provides best-in-class software tools to import, optimize and visualize 3D data and can be used to create 2D/3D, virtual reality, and augmented reality applications, as well as physical simulations.

Figure 18: View of the smart warehousing implementation

Figure 18 presents a very high level, abstract, view of the smart warehousing implementation thus far. UC1 Smart Warehousing comprises of two AGVs (Locobots) having a custom lift ability for bringing ordered products to the user. Both AGVs have ROS1/2 bridges and containerized docker microservices running on them. AGVs communicate with the so-called DEDICAT 6G controller through fast *Data Distribution Service (DDS) Discovery*². This controller essentially facilitates communication of the AGVs/robots with the user interfaces (i.e., the Warehouse Manager dashboard and the worker mobile app). For example, information sent to the Warehouse Manager dashboard includes AGV positioning/movement, camera feed and AGV status (e.g., battery level, CPU and RAM usage). The DEDICAT 6G controller is hosted in the cloud together with other auxiliary entities including an orchestrator based on open source ETSI *Management and Orchestration (MANO)*³, the Kubernetes platform, an implementation of the intelligence distribution mechanisms from WP3 (specifically an improved version of the algorithm for Placement of Intelligence described in section 2.1 of D3.2 [6] and D3.3 [7]) and an implementation of the threat identification and classification mechanism from WP5 (described in detail in section 6.1 of D5.2 [10] and in section 7.1 of 5.3 [11]).

The Intelligence Distribution Algorithm is responsible for (re-)distributing services dynamically to the network's nodes (AGVs, cloud nodes) for overcoming possible increase of network latency or possible unavailability of an AGV, while also considering power consumption of the involved nodes. This algorithm communicates with the DEDICAT 6G controller and the MANO orchestrator for receiving information related to AGVs, cloud and edge nodes status and services information. The output of the algorithm is sent to the MANO orchestrator, which deploys the corresponding containerized microservices as Network Services implemented by *Kubernetes-based Network Functions (KNF)* at the entities/nodes where the algorithm suggests. The Kubernetes master node deployed alongside MANO, instantiates the microservices on the robots registered as Kubernetes worker nodes. Figure 19 shows a view of the MANO dashboard displaying the status and location (node where they are placed) of the Functional Entities/services with the schematical representation on the bottom right corner of tasks completed per second and the deployment topology.

² <https://fast-dds.docs.eprosima.com/en/v2.1.0/02-formalia/titlepage.html>

³ <https://osm.etsi.org/>

Figure 19: MANO dashboard

The Intelligence Distribution algorithm is a standalone, in-house developed component and communicates with the infrastructure and MANO components (with the help of the FastAPI web framework⁴ to produce and apply management decisions regarding the placement of microservices (Figure 20).

Figure 20: Intelligence distribution FAST API

As mentioned, an improved of the Intelligence Function Placement algorithm, described in Section 2.1 of D3.2 [6] and Section 2.1 of D3.3 [7], was utilized in the smart warehousing use case. This algorithm was further enhanced with an additional term in the objective function related to the physical traveling distance of the robotic units. This term was added mostly for the physical tasks intended for robots and can contribute to the decrease of the possible

⁴ <https://fastapi.tiangolo.com/>

energy consumption and the latency of assigning a task to a robot far away from the physical location where the task should be executed. Additionally, the dynamic and proactive placement of the intelligence functions was studied. Therefore, the algorithm takes the predicted future states of the various metrics as input, instead of the real time capabilities and metrics of the various *Hosting Entities (HE)* e.g., edge nodes, core nodes, robotic units, end user devices, to prevent a possible increase of network latency or possible unavailability of a physical node. For this purpose, *Artificial Intelligence (AI) / Machine Learning (ML)* predictive models for time series forecasting were used, as described further down.

The optimization algorithm of Intelligence Function Placement aims to minimize the following *Objective Function (OF)*, $OF = w_1 B + w_2 P + w_3 D + w_4 T$. The term $B = \sum_{j=1}^m y_j b_j$ denotes the cost related to the battery level of the utilized HEs (takes higher values when battery is low, and close to zero values when it is fully charged or when the HE is not battery-powered). y_j is a binary decision variable that indicates if HE j is utilized or not and b_j is a cost related to the battery level of HE j . The $P = \sum_{j=1}^m (W_{max}^j - W_{idle}^j) \cdot Ucpu_j(x_{i,j}) + W_{idle}^j$ term denotes the power consumption cost which is modelled based on [13], where $Ucpu_j(x_{i,j})$ is the CPU utilization rate on the HE j in terms of the decision variable $x_{i,j}$ which indicates if *Functional Entity (FE)* i is assigned on HE j . W_{max}^j, W_{idle}^j are the power consumption when the HE j is fully loaded and idle, respectively. The $D = \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{j'=1}^m \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{i'=1, i' \neq i}^n z_{i,i',j,j'} \frac{k_{i,i'}}{cap_{j,j'}}$ denotes the cost (transmission delay) imposed by the communication among HEs related to the amount of data transferred ($k_{i,i'}$) between FEs and the maximum capacity link ($cap_{j,j'}$). The binary decision variable $z_{i,i',j,j'}$ shows if HEs j and j' are communicating due to communicating FEs assigned on them. Finally, $T = \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{i=1}^n t_{i,j} x_{i,j}$ denotes the total physical travelling distance covered by the robotic nodes from its initial location till the location where the allocated task must be executed ($t_{i,j}$), if applicable. Each term of the OF is normalized and is weighted (w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4) depending on the use case. The constraints of this problem are the ones described in Section 2.1 of D3.3 [7]. The algorithm, developed for solving this problem for larger scales and utilized in the experiments of smart warehousing use case, is based on the genetic algorithm paradigm. The flowchart of the algorithm is explained in Section 2.1 of D3.3 [7].

Moreover, a proactive approach of functions placement was studied. Time series forecasting models based on *Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)* recurrent neural networks [14] were developed for predicting the behavior of services and/or components, whose output feeds the Intelligence Function Placement algorithm. The LSTM models are trained using monitoring telemetry data from selected services and infrastructure components. However, within the smart warehousing use case the focus is on the health of the AGV components mostly. Hence, the batteries and location of robots are monitored among others to feed the intelligence function placement algorithm and to dynamically reallocate the intelligence to the available nodes, as well as prevent a possible malfunction, low battery level, overvoltage and so on.

Figure 21 shows the predicted and actual battery consumption of an AGV when it performs the smart warehousing scenario. The obtained training score of 0.09 *Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)* and the test score of 0.32 RMSE indicates that the model has lower error on the training data and a bit higher error on the unseen test data. When battery data is smoothed with the exponentially weighted moving average filtering for decreasing the noise, the model is trained again, and the obtained results are shown in Figure 22. The RMSE of the training data is now 0.02, and the RMSE of the testing data is 0.26. These measurements indicate that during training, the model can predict battery consumption accurately with a small error margin. However, on test data, the model performance is not perfect, but it is still good enough to be used as input to the optimization algorithm since the accuracy levels

are not so important in the specific problem. However, these results can be further improved with more historical data and real-time training.

Figure 21: Intelligence distribution improvements - Battery consumption prediction of actual data using the developed time series forecasting model

Figure 22: Intelligence distribution improvements - Battery consumption prediction of smoothed data using the developed time series forecasting model

Additionally, the AGVs' future physical locations (trajectory prediction) was modeled with the use of a multivariate LSTM model. The predicted future locations of robots can be used by the optimization algorithm in the case of a need of reallocation of physical robotic tasks. The data used for training the time series forecasting model is collected during the smart warehousing scenario and a 2D and 3D visualization is presented in Figure 23 left and right side, respectively. Figure 24 shows the actual and predicted locations of the test data. As it is shown in this figure, the prediction is close to the actual measurement. And if we zoom in (Figure 25), we can see that there are some deviations due to the complexity of the actual data. In particular, the RMSE of the testing data is 0.25. This model can be further improved

by training the model with more data. The analysis of additional metrics like motor stress, navigation error, etc. produced similar results.

By proactively reconfiguring service and network components, preventing production interruptions, and minimizing maintenance expenses, this predictive strategy can save critical time as compared to the reactive approach of fixing or replacing faulty components after they fail.

Figure 23: Intelligence distribution improvements - A 2D and 3D representation of trajectory data utilized by the time series forecasting model

Figure 24: Intelligence distribution improvements - The actual and predicted locations of the test data

Figure 25: Intelligence distribution improvements - An example of the actual and predicted locations of an AGV

Furthermore, the implemented Security Mechanism for threat identification and classification monitors network traffic all over the smart warehousing infrastructure. In the case of a possible detected threat / cyber-attack, it alerts the DEDICAT 6G controller (the component that facilitates communication of the AGVs/robots with the user interfaces and other components) and a relevant notification appears on the Warehouse Manager dashboard. For the training of the algorithm, UNSW-NB15 dataset was used. The algorithm uses a random forest classifier to classify the instances in 10 classes, depending on the type of attack it has been detected. The classes are: Normal, Fuzzers, Analysis, Backdoor, DoS, Exploits, Generic, Reconnaissance, Shellcode and Worms.

Additionally, in order to be able to test the security mechanism, a simulator was developed. The simulator is also implemented in Python and produces instances of five types of attacks, based on the UNSW-NB15 dataset. Figure 26 shows the interface of the simulator. Every time the user wants to simulate an attack, the software writes in a csv file the values for every feature in the dataset according to the attack type that was selected. Subsequently, the security mechanism takes as input the last instance that was written and classifies it.

Figure 26: User interface for security mechanism testing

In a separate pilot demonstration, BLEMAT -based on VLF IoT controllers- was used for tracking simulated devices and personnel.

Figure 27: BLEMAT signal acquisition and data distribution

BLE high precision battery powered location beacons was deployed on strategic resources to simulate AGVs and key personnel. In Figure 27 we can see process of collecting detected Bluetooth signals present around one single IoT device. Another service is responsible for data formatting and sending to the main Mosquitto MQTT server.


```

blemat@blemat1: ~/blemat-service-controller
File Edit Tabs Help
["dc:a6:32:7d:3f:71,dc:a6:32:7d:3e:70,dc:a6:32:7d:3e:91",
"rssi": "-70.00565275797474,-72.70872711739585,-72.54681232080613",
"distances": "9.213458906991056,8.574327602924157,12.194252147911078",
"correction_factor": 0}, {"x": 8.345192972330201, "y": 4.968971329612937, "beacon_mac": "53:7e:65:8c:9f:85",
"controller_mac": "dc:a6:32:7d:29:97,dc:a6:32:7d:3e:70,dc:a6:32:7d:3e:91",
"rssi": "-72.54681232080613,-72.54681232080613,-72.54681232080613",
"distances": "9.712513671544805,8.574327602924157,12.194252147911078",
"correction_factor": 0}, {"x": 6.467755760825473, "y": 6.764143870659671, "beacon_mac": "53:7e:65:8c:9f:85",
"controller_mac": "dc:a6:32:7d:29:97,dc:a6:32:7d:3f:71,dc:a6:32:7d:3e:70",
"rssi": "-72.54681232080613,-70.00565275797474,-72.70872711739585",
"distances": "9.712513671544805,9.213458906991056,8.574327602924157",
"correction_factor": 0}]

blemat@blemat1: ~/blemat-service-controller
File Edit Tabs Help
3258
-----
Beacon=56:ba:24:29:46:07; X=292.602350301071; Y=0.0
-----
Beacon=35:4e:eb:35:00:3c; X=7.094842677095592; Y=7.254327508797799
-----
Beacon=f4:ec:f3:41:ad:05; X=8.0; Y=49.864039916819216
-----
Beacon=65:b0:a6:bd:34:45; X=6.286125948235302; Y=5.233830863157373
-----
Beacon=1d:d9:2c:1b:09:0b; X=4.978221723256401; Y=2.095288063887616
-----
Beacon=53:7e:65:8c:9f:85; X=6.347970397829041; Y=6.878611681813258
-----

```

Figure 28: BLEMAT calculation process

Figure 28 shows service responsible for calculations based on Kalman filter. Values are estimates in (x, y) space for each mac address scanned off of Bluetooth. Service runs on the device that is hosting the main IoT device. Every mac address in this demo represents individual AGV / robot.


```

sac-controller > rpi_relay > bleemat-controller.py > main
1 from relay import Device
2 from scanner import BLELS
3 import time
4
5 def main():
6
7     device = Device()
8
9
10    try:
11        while True:
12            if beacons := [x for x in BLELS.scan(BLELS) if x["addr"] == mac_address]:
13                rssi = beacons[0]["rssi"]
14                print(rssi)
15                if rssi > -50 and rssi < -20:
16                    device.door_open()
17                    time.sleep(5)
18                else:
19                    device.door_close()
20                    time.sleep(1)
21        finally:
22            device.cleanup()
23
24    if __name__ == '__main__':
25        main()

```

Figure 29: Smart Access 360 code example for opening warehouse doors

Smart Access 360 IoT system performs edge-based computing and necessary identity management in order to ensure context aware authorization of the smart actuation processes. Figure 29 shows main block of the code for opening warehouse doors based on Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI).

3.2.2.3 Interfaces

A view of the DEDICAT 6G interfaces relevant to this Use Case is provided in the UC1 UML diagrams in D2.3 [2] An overview of the key interfaces between components that are implemented in the scope of this use case pilot are listed (see also Table 2):

- The EN Status Agent FC, μ S/FC Status Agent FC and NW Status Agent FC interface with the EN Awareness FC, μ S/FC Awareness FC and NW Awareness FC respectively;
- The EN Awareness FC, μ S/FC Awareness FC and NW Awareness FC in turn provide input on the EN, μ S/FC and NW context to the IDDM FC;

- The EN Registry FC, μ S/FC Registry FC, μ S/FC Repository FC and EC Policy Repository FC also interface with the IDDM FC;
- The IDDM FC has an interface with the Service Orchestrator FC;
- The Warehouse Manager Dashboard has an interface with the Warehouse worker app;
- The Warehouse Manager Dashboard and the Warehouse worker apps have an interface with the AuthN FC and the AGV Operation FC.

3.2.3 Final integration report

The paragraph below describes the use of WPs outcomes in the UC1 and the contribution per partner done during the period M15 to M36.

3.2.3.1 Description of WPs related outcomes in UC1

Mechanisms for Dynamic Distribution of Intelligence (WP3):

Intelligence placement of computation that takes account of the increasing service requirements as well as the demand of power and delay sensitivity of user devices.

Audit logging and analysis that enables collection and secure storage of all types of logs across the DEDICAT 6G system (with main focus on security) and implements blockchain technology to ensure logs consistency and trustworthiness.

Mechanisms for Dynamic Coverage Extension (WP4):

Context awareness module for device discovery. Enhanced IoT devices that estimate the number of users and devices in a coverage area by short-range signal scanning techniques.

Coverage Extension Decision Making considers MAP operation and swarm operation. MAP operation includes managing mobility, adjusting orientation and tilt, and receiving status reports on ongoing operations.

Mechanisms for Security, Privacy and Trust (WP5): like for all other Use Cases, the security and data protection framework used in UC1 is developed in the D5.1, D5.2 and D5.3. They are used for providing access control to resources and data. The framework is used for fine-grained asset control management, as well as data access control using underlying blockchain technologies. Threat identification and classification mechanisms developed for the WP5 as a component of the security and data protection framework are also used in UC1.

3.2.3.2 Description of contribution per partner in UC1

WINGS: Implementation of intelligence distribution mechanisms from WP3 (specifically the algorithm for placement of intelligence described in section 2.1 of D3.2 [6] and D3.3 [7]) and implementation of the Threat identification and classification mechanism from WP5 (described in detail in section 6.1 of D5.2 [10] and in section 7.1 of 5.3 [11]). Configuration of robots and implementation of robot functionalities for identification and fetching of products. Implementation of Warehouse Manager dashboard and Application for Warehouse worker.

ORANGE: Implementation of an algorithm for placement of latency-sensitive tasks, described in Section 2 of D3.3. The algorithm is part of the Intelligence Distribution Decision-Making Functional Component.

VLF: Integration of smart access control and indoor positioning IoT solutions based on IoT platform and edge controllers. Implementation of audit logging and analysis from WP3,

described in D3.2. Implementation of blockchain enabled security and trust management framework from WP5, described in D5.2 and D5.3.

DIA: Provision of facilities for pilot execution of pilot and validation activities; feedback provision during the experiments and confirmation that the final attainable performance is satisfactory. Contribution to technical, functional and business requirements for the design of the DEDICAT 6G architecture capturing warehouse operations and optimization goals.

NOKIA: Implementation of security and trust management framework from WP5 by integrating NDM (Nokia Data Marketplace) with the proposed solution.

3.2.3.3 Description of external assets used in UC1

Know-how and experience accumulated from the participation in projects such as Clear5G⁵, One5G⁶, 5G-EVE⁷, and 5G-TOURS⁸ has been utilised for the implementation of the UC1 prototype and the testing performed so far. The development and implementation of all software and hardware components for UC1 have been done specifically in the context of DEDICAT 6G, with no re-use of specific assets.

VLF has provided Bluetooth Low Energy Micro-location Asset Tracking (BLEMAT) solution for detecting location and mobility patterns of key mobile assets in a typical warehouse. Also, VLF has deployed Smart Access 360 – an IoT system for cyber-physical security managing flow of mobile assets and their access rights in context aware manner.

3.3 Evaluation and final results

An implementation of a Smart warehousing prototype is available including robots, the Warehouse manager dashboard and the AR training application for Warehouse Workers. The prototype also includes a self-made barrier to demonstrate automated access control for robots to diverse areas of the warehouse (Figure 31). If a robot has been given access to a particular area "fenced off" by a barrier then the bar is raised for the robot to go through or deliver a product. Once this has been completed the barrier automatically closes. The implemented prototype is also **integrated with an implementation of intelligence distribution mechanisms from WP3** (specifically the algorithm for Placement of Intelligence described in section 2.1 of D3.2 [6] and D3.3 [7] and improved as described in section 3.1.2) and with **an implementation of the Threat identification and classification mechanism from WP5** (described in detail in section 6.1 of D5.2 [10] and section 7.1 of D5.3[11]). For demonstration purposes of the integration with the Threat identification and classification mechanism a panel for Alerts or Warnings has been added to the Warehouse manager dashboard (Figure 30 left side, middle panel).

⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/761745>

⁶ <https://one5g.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.5g-eve.eu/>

⁸ <https://5gtours.eu/>

Figure 30: Warehouse Manager dashboard displaying security threats and corresponding mitigation actions

This prototype has been demonstrated at various events such as EUCNC 2022, EUCNC 2023, Beyond 2023, 5G Conference South-eastern Europe 2022 and 2023, while corresponding videos have been produced that can be found on the project YouTube channel. The same set-up has also been **tested at the DIAKINISIS warehouse** at various occasions. (Figure 31).

Figure 31: View of DIAKINISIS warehouse testing

In addition, a key demonstration, testing and exploitation activity has been through a partnership between WINGS and Cosmote/Deutsche Telekom as also reported in D7.3 [50]. More specifically, WINGS has been working with Cosmote/Deutsche Telekom (commercial) since September 2023 to prepare use cases which demonstrate Transportation & Logistics operations under 5G *Standalone (5G SA)* networks. For this partnership, Cosmote set up a private 5G SA network provided by Ericsson. During November 2023, the first integration tests were performed to, among others, fine-tune the network behavior. WINGS set up the relevant DEDICAT 6G backend components in an edge server directly connected to the 5G core to achieve a truly private 5G SA network.

Figure 32: View of Smart Warehousing demo set up at OTE Academy Athens, Greece

Demonstrations took place at the Lean Manufacturing conference, on December 6, 2023 at the OTE Academy Auditorium, Athens, Greece & Online. During the preparation period as well as throughout the whole demonstration period, KPIs have been collected.

3.3.1 List of KPIs, target values and gain

This sub-Section describes the KPI related to the UC, specify the KPI target value, the measurement method and the gain with a comparison with t_0 .

3.3.1.1 KPIs and target values

Table 3 presents the list of KPIs related to the Smart Warehousing use case, describing the evaluation methods and defining the target values and the baseline for comparison.

Table 3: UC1 – Smart warehousing KPIs list

KPI ID	Description	Target value	Baseline value
UC1_KPI1	Latency. Decreased latency (incl. mean delay and delay jitter) via intelligence distribution mechanisms by up to a factor of 10 in congested and faulty situations in order to improve quality of experience.	End-to-end: 200ms Uplink (UL)/ Downlink (DL) network delay: 10ms	The baseline values range from less than 10ms (augmented reality in human-machine interfaces), 10ms to 100ms (Human machine interfaces, Mobile control panels, Visualization of Control with periodic deterministic communication), and 40ms to 500ms (Service performance requirements for mobile robots, Periodic communication for standard mobile robot

KPI ID	Description	Target value	Baseline value
			operation and traffic management) based on the "Service requirements for cyber-physical control applications in vertical domains" (3GPP TS 22.104).
UC1_KPI2	Network energy efficiency and device energy efficiency. Decreased energy consumption (incl. communication and computation) via intelligence distribution mechanisms by at least a factor of 10 in order to increase the operation lifetime of a mobile station or server.	<10 Mbit/J	Reduction of energy consumption by a factor of 10 (considering that intelligence distribution can contribute to increasing efficiency of Sleep Mode) [26],[27].
UC1_KPI3	Service reliability (application layer). Service reliability can be defined as the success probability of transmitting a layer 2/3 packet within a maximum latency required by the targeted service (ITU-R M.2410, cf. [17]). With the use of intelligence distribution mechanisms this should either improve or at least remain the same as the baseline	>=99.999	The baseline value is at least 99.999 based on the "Service requirements for the 5G system", (3GPP TS 22.261) and the "Service requirements for cyber-physical control applications in vertical domains" (3GPP TS 22.104).
UC1_KPI4	Warehouse operation efficiency. Advanced warehouse automation towards significant increase of operations' efficiency (elimination of time wastes", decrease of product damages) and safety, in a complex warehousing environment. Reduction of time required to complete processes such as quality assurance and order collection.	15% reduction	The baseline is usual operation of DIAKINISIS warehouse, without the use of DEDICAT 6G solutions.
UC1_KPI5	Warehouse safety. Enhancing safety in warehouses, as automation will reduce the collision risk by timely warning and/or anticipating in case of dangerous situations. An incident reduction is envisioned when a high level of automation is deployed.	>=10%	The baseline is usual operation of DIAKINISIS warehouse, without the use of DEDICAT 6G solutions.

3.3.1.2 Final evaluation and results

This sub-section presents results derived from testing.

Table 4: UC1 – Results obtained and gain

KPI ID and Name	Evaluation method	Result	Gain
UC1_KPI1 Latency	Measurements are collected at the application layer by adding timestamps to requests between functional entities/service components of an overall service. Then the difference in time is calculated between the request from one entity (e.g., client) and the response from the other entity (e.g., server). Measurements are also collected e.g., with the use of ping and iPerf.	Figure 33-40, Figure section 3.3.1.2.1	From the various measurements latency is close to the target and baseline values.
UC1_KPI2 Network energy efficiency and device energy efficiency	The battery level of involved mobile nodes (e.g., phones, laptops, robots) has been measured with and without the use of intelligence distribution mechanisms for certain services/applications. The power consumption of involved servers may also be measured or at least estimated using various ways ranging from cheap watt hour meters for on premises servers.	Figure 41, Figure section 3.3.1.2.2	5-10%
UC1_KPI3 Service reliability	The packet loss rate at the application layer (packets that arrive delayed or erroneous are considered as lost packets) has been measured.	Section 3.3.1.2.3	100% the target is met.
UC1_KPI4 Warehouse operation efficiency	Time is measured for completing product quality check and order picking with and without DEDICAT 6G solutions and in particular AGVs.	Section 3.3.1.2.4	Based on simulations and data provided by DIAKINISIS improvements in the time for order picking range from 7,27 % to - 49,66 %
UC1_KPI5 Warehouse safety	Testing of robots capabilities to stop before an obstacle.	Section 3.3.1.2.5	Based on tests full collision avoidance is achieved for robots.

3.3.1.2.1 Latency

Figure 28 presents results derived from running a ping to a random server (Google in this case) from the robot over WiFi, 5G with and without VPN, indoor and outdoor. It should be noted that a commercial 5G network was used for these experiments. As can be observed, Wifi offers the best latency performance, 5G seems to suffer from interference in indoor settings, whereas the use of VPN does not add a substantial overhead in terms of latency.

Figure 33: Latency performance tests (pinging a server)

In the robotic scenarios that we conduct, beyond the communication with an external server, there is a requirement for the devices to communicate between themselves. To achieve this, the use of a VPN is mandatory. Figure 33 depicts results from a latency performance test (communication between devices), using the ping method. With ping, a data packet is sent to the remote computer, and then the computer that sent the packet waits for an echo reply, i.e., the response to the ping data packet. The packet sent with the ping is called an *Internet Control Message Protocol (ICMP)* echo packet. As can be observed the use of VPN does not add significant latency.

Figure 34: Latency from ping between two robots

The implementation presented in Figure 34 includes processes/services that are enclosed in a docker environment with `ros1_bridge`, using ROS2 middleware. ROS2 has been selected over ROS1 mainly due to two reasons. Firstly, ROS2 allows the creation of a fully distributed system, where each node is independent, whereas ROS1 requires a master node⁹. Moreover, ROS2 offers a rich variety of QoS policies that allows configuring communication between

⁹https://roboticsbackend.com/ros1-vs-ros2-practical-over-view/#Why_ROS2_and_not_keep_ROS1

nodes. With the right set of QoS policies, ROS2 can be as reliable as TCP or as best-effort as UDP, with many, many possible states in between. Unlike ROS1, which primarily only supported TCP, ROS2 benefits from the flexibility of the underlying DDS transport in environments with lossy wireless networks where a “best effort” policy would be more suitable, or in real-time computing systems where the right Quality of Service profile is needed to meet stricter requirements¹⁰. ROS1_bridge is a network bridge which enables the exchange of messages between ROS1 and ROS2. Figure 35 aims to highlight the impact on latency when an application runs in an isolated environment (docker-ized microservices). As we can see, there is a small increase in latency, while we pass from a bare metal environment to a docker-ized one.

Figure 35: Latency when using dockerized microservices

A next step is to measure the latency caused by software. The majority of our processes are implemented in Python. Figure 36 shows a comparison of network latency as derived in Figure 34 with the latency of a service implemented in python and ROS, calculated as a round trip time.

Figure 36: Comparison between network latency as derived in Figure 34, with the latency of a service implemented in python and ROS

¹⁰ <https://docs.ros.org/en/rolling/Concepts/About-Quality-of-Service-Settings.html>

Figure 37 depicts a comparison between ROS1 bridged dockerized services with WiFi and 5G VPN. Non-bridged latency performance from Figure 36 is also included, in order to highlight the impact of ROS1_bridge to latency.

Figure 37: Latency comparison between ROS 1 bridged docker-ized and non-bridged services with WiFi and 5G VPN.

Figure 38, Figure 39 and Figure 40 present additional results from the testing with a dedicated 5G SA network at OTE premises. These show latency results from the commercial 5G network and the 5G SA network for low data rate traffic, medium data rate traffic and high data rate traffic. This traffic refers to the traffic exchanged between the robots and other nodes. For testing purposes these nodes were inserted for obtaining continuous live video streaming from the robot cameras.

Figure 38: Latency with 5G commercial network and 5G SA network for low data rate traffic from testing at OTE premises

Figure 39: Latency with 5G commercial network and 5G SA network for medium data rate traffic from testing at OTE premises

Figure 40: Latency with 5G commercial network and 5G SA network for high data rate traffic from testing at OTE premises

As can be observed as the network gets "stressed" more the latency increases but still remains low. The average latency ranges between 24ms (low data rate traffic), 46ms (medium data rate traffic) to 94ms (high data rate traffic), while higher peaks can be observed in some cases though remaining below 100ms for low and medium data rate traffic and below 150ms for high data rate traffic.

The **average execution time for the intelligence distribution** integrated in the current proof of concept implementation is 2.31sec. This considers 4 hosting entities (2 robots and 2 servers) and 8 functional entities with various computational (CPU, RAM) and execution requirements (need of camera/arm/wheels, need of other Functional entities to be placed in the same node). Further results from lab testing of this implementation of the intelligence distribution mechanism can also be found in D3.2 [6] and D3.3 [7].

The **average execution time for the implemented security mechanism for threat detection and classification** is 68ms for one data stream/row, 900ms for 40 streams, 2.4sec for 100 streams, and 23sec for 1000 streams. This average execution time also applies to the implementation of UC3 Public Safety.

3.3.1.2.2 Energy efficiency

Figure 41 depicts the level of battery of a robot for different levels of intelligence distribution. Specifically, the graph shows how the battery percentage evolves 75% of nodes (i.e., services related to the Smart Warehousing) are hosted on the robot, all services are hosted on the robot and only essential hardware related services/nodes are hosted on the robot. As expected, the battery percentage is at its highest in the latter case, Figure 42 and Figure 43 present similar results for RAM and CPU usage respectively. These results aim to provide an indication of how intelligence distribution can contribute to energy efficiency.

Figure 41: View of impact of Intelligence Distribution on battery consumption of robots

Figure 42: View of impact of Intelligence Distribution on RAM of robots:
(a) all services running on the robot;
(b) only essential hardware related services running on the robot

Figure 43: View of impact of intelligence distribution on CPU of robots:
(a) all services running on the robot;
(b) only essential hardware related services running on the robot

It should be noted that while the results presented here (Figure 33-Figure 43) are presented under UC1, essentially the measurements are also applicable to the UC3 Public Safety part based on a similar implementation architecture (Figure 94).

3.3.1.2.3 Service reliability

Packet Error Rate (PER) is measured continuously by sending test packets from a test sender to a test receiver, and back. No loss of packets was recorded and therefore service reliability is measured at a 100%.

3.3.1.2.4 Warehouse operation efficiency: order picking simulation

3.3.1.2.4.1. General information

Of all warehouse operations, order picking includes the most cost-intensive ones. It is vital to try lots of scenarios to clarify which one could lead to the best results (distance & time reduction). For this to happen, plenty of data is required such as storage locations, order lists, and the included products. We have created a simulator based on the historical data DIAKINISIS

has provided us with. The way the simulator works and all the assumptions that have been made are described in this document.

3.3.1.2.4.2. Planning Problems

The planning and optimization of a warehouse can be split into three basic categories:

1. Storage location assignment problem;
2. Order Picking Strategies;
3. *Picking Routing Problem (PRP)*.

3.3.1.2.4.3. Storage location assignment problem

This problem is about how incoming goods are stored in the warehouse. There are three main approaches:

- **random (chaotic)**: simply stored at the nearest available pallet location;
- **dedicated (slotting)**: goods are assigned specific storage locations;
- **class-based storage**: group by item characteristics and each group has a fixed storage location

3.3.1.2.4.4. Order Picking Strategies

Order picking strategies determine how picklists are generated.

- **single order picking**: One order at a time;
- **batching**: Pick more than one orders simultaneously (NP-hard problem);
- **zoning**: The picker only picks items stored in a specific area.

The literature discusses two methods for order batching. The **proximity batching** which uses the proximity of storage locations that need to be visited. In this case orders are not split between different batches. There is also the **time-window batching** in which all orders that arrive during the same time interval are grouped together in one batch. Finally, is the **picking prioritization per area** in which orders for the same area are picked in order to increase the loading efficiency and not to miss the loading time window.

3.3.1.2.4.5. Picker Routing Problem

PRP is a special case of the *Travelling Salesman Problem (TSP)*¹¹. The literature outlines three approaches to pick-run routing optimization:

- Static routing heuristics, i.e., routing rules that human pickers follow;
- Scalable algorithms that either determine the optimal route, or approximate it;
- Hybridization of both picker routing heuristics and algorithmic approaches.

There is a strong connection between the *Order Batching Problem (OBP)* and *PRP*. Solving these problems simultaneously results in a more efficient solution. This joint problem is known as *JOBPRP (Joint Order Batching Problem and Picker Routing Problem)*.

¹¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Travelling_salesman_problem

3.3.1.2.4.6. Simulation

Assumptions

- Workers can execute at least one order at a single tour. The single tour is defined as all the route steps a picker does before, he goes to a checking station;
- Vendors that are stored at the left area of the warehouse have their orders checked at the checking stations also located on the left side;
- Vendors that are stored at the right area of the warehouse have their orders checked at the checking stations also located on the right side;
- For each one of the two areas (left-right), the checking station for each order is randomly selected. 3 checking stations available for each area;
- The quantity for each product is set to 1 (1 box);
- When a worker starts picking an order, the checking station for that order is already known so that the picking route can be calculated end-to-end;
- For each order the picker starts from one of the available checking stations (the one he put the last order collected), collects all the products, and then goes to one checking station;
- For the picking of each product a time interval (delay) is required. This is the time a picker needs to take the product from one shelf and put it in his/her carton on his/her pedestrian forklift:
 - We have set this value equal to 1mn;
 - Currently all our metrics are about percentages of distance reduction, so the above delay does not affect our results;
- Another time interval (delay) is the time a picker needs to place the collected products at a checking station:
 - We have set this value equal to 30sec;
 - This variable also does not affect our results but is needed if we want to calculate time-based KPIs.

Workflow

Orders are created for each one of the 6 available vendors separately. The order creation procedure for each vendor is split into 3 steps:

1. Calculate the total daily orders for that specific vendor
 - This value follows the normal distribution (the average number of orders each vendor has daily based on the historical data provided by DIA)
2. For each order calculate the number of different products to be included (n different products)
 - The same technique is used: value follows the normal distribution (the average number of products each order has based on the historical data provided by DIA)
 - Different vendors have a different average number of products
3. Select randomly n products from the product list
 - This step is not exactly random, as the 'Lines' column (how many times each product has been picked) is used. Products that have been picked more times are more likely to be selected.

In the end, all the orders that have been created are merged. For a better understanding, the average values mentioned above are provided in Table 5. The order creation procedure is depicted in the diagram of Figure 44.

Table 5: Average values for each vendor

	PFIZER	UPJOHN	BGP	ARRIANI	GENERICS	MEDA
Average Daily Orders	245	130	108	114	37	35
Average products	5	7	6	7	9	6

Figure 44: Order creation procedure

When all orders are available, the picking procedure starts. Half of the available pickers are responsible for the left area of the warehouse and the rest of them for the right. In the case that all the orders have been completed for one area, then all pickers operate in the same area.

Optimization

As described in the Planning Problems Section 3.3.1.2.4.2, the optimization of the warehouse is based on the storage location of the products, the order picking strategies and the PRP. The first simulation uses the current state of the warehouse:

- Storage locations currently used by DIAKINISIS;
- Single order picking;
- Apply TSP algorithm to solve the picker routing problem (there is no other way to simulate the picking order).

This simulation is used as a reference point.

Storage Optimization

Each vendor has a specific number of storage locations which must remain the same (class-based storage, section 1) as shown in Figure 45. Different colours indicate different vendors.

Figure 45: Storage locations per vendor

Our approach is to place most frequently used products near the checking stations to minimise the total distance required for each order. The checking stations are located near the end of the corridors. The products of each vendor are ordered based on their frequency and then placed at the storage locations with the lowest Manhattan distance¹² from the corridors as shown in Figure 46. This approach reduces the distance of high used products from both the checking stations and other products with similar order frequency. If we had historical order data, we could have found more patterns therefore have created an even more accurate storage optimization algorithm.

Figure 46: Original vs modified storage locations heatmap

¹² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Taxicab_geometry

Order Batching

As mentioned in Section 3.3.1.2.4.4, for maximum distance reduction, similar orders are picked together, and the route optimization algorithm (TSP) is applied as if we had one single order (JOBPRP). Batching is applied to orders with common vendors. The order batching algorithm uses a combination of the seed algorithm and data mining. Data mining is used to extract the features that define the similarity of the orders. In our case the similarity is measured using the number of common products between orders. A high-level version of the order batching algorithm is shown in Figure 47.

```
while there exist unassigned customer orders do
  open a new batch;
  select an unassigned order as seed order;
  while orders exist which does not exceed the
    remaining capacity of the current batch then
    select an unassigned order;
    assign order to current batch;
  endwhile
  close current batch;
endwhile
```

Figure 47: Order batching algorithm

The similarity between the seed order and the remaining orders is calculated for each new batch. The most similar orders are assigned to the current batch till the capacity is full.

In our case the capacity refers to the total number of orders per batch. In most cases the number of products is used instead but this would add much more complexity to the algorithm.

3.3.1.2.4.7. Simulation results

The results of each simulation refer to the average daily distance reduction compared with the current state of the warehouse (first simulation). The total distance required for each order is the sum of the picking and checking distance. The picking distance includes all the route steps the picker does from the first to the last product. The checking distance includes the steps from his initial location to the first product and the steps from the last product to the checking station. Three different scenarios were simulated:

1. Update the storage location of the products based on our storage optimization algorithm without changing the picking strategy (single order picking);
2. Use the existing product locations (as provided by DIAKINISIS) but with order batching with 2 orders capacity;
3. Combine scenario 1 and 2.

The overall distance reduction is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Overall daily average distance reduction

Scenario	Total Distance	Checking Distance	Picking Distance
Modified Storage Single Picking	- 7,27 %	+ 1,66 %	- 18,35 %
Original Storage Order Batching	- 45,75 %	- 51,19 %	- 38,12 %
Modified Storage Order Batching	- 49,66 %	- 49,63 %	- 48,90 %

Scenario 1

The impact of checking distance is high and cannot be easily reduced in single order picking. Storage optimization focuses on picking distance (low distance between similar products), while order batching deals with both checking and picking distance.

Although the picking distance was reduced by around 18%, the overall distance was not reduced that much. That is normal because picking and checking distances do not have the same weight. For instance, consider a vendor that is placed far away from the checking stations. Even if all products are placed together (small picking distance), the checking distance will be high as a lot of distance is required from the checking station to the area of that vendor.

The results may differ per vendor. As shown in Figure 45 the total number of storage locations per vendor is not the same. The more products a vendor has, the more the storage combinations will be. Small distance reductions indicate that the storage is already optimised.

Scenario 2

When two orders can be picked at the same time, there is a high possibility to find orders with some common products. In that way, a storage location is accessed only one instead of two times. It is vital to choose orders with as many common products as possible in order to get the maximum distance reduction. No matter whether similar orders are found, the distance between the checking stations and the vendor zones is reduced by around 50%. Order batching seems to smooth the distance weights, as the total distance now is the average of the checking and picking distance.

Scenario 3

When using both the modified storage locations and the order batching the results become even better. The checking distance is almost the same as scenario 2, but the picking distance is reduced even more. Order batching groups similar orders. Even if the orders do not have the same products, they may have products with high usage frequency. Due to the storage optimization algorithm these products have been placed nearby, thus the picking distance is reduced.

3.3.1.2.5 Warehouse safety

Instead of human-driven pallet trucks or forklifts that might not notice a pedestrian worker, a robot equipped with Lidar and cameras can recognize human or other obstacles and stop in time to avoid an accident. Testing both at DIAKINISIS and at OTE academy has confirmed this. More specifically testing has shown that comparing a network with a latency of 60ms with a 5G SA network with 10ms latency a robot that moves 1.5cm/sec can stop 7.5cm earlier. This can be observed in the video available here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ait-wFqzV3wQ>.

Furthermore, applying indoor geofencing with edge controllers and blocking unauthorized personnel access to the restricted areas with smart access significantly lower collision risk. We used minimal-infrastructure approach with BLEMAT service on edge devices to create virtual boundaries around specific zones and locations and track personnel positions in real time.

4 UC2: ENHANCED EXPERIENCE

4.1 Scenario and stories

The Enhanced Experience Use Case scenario focuses on live public events that are characterized by a dense number of local users (participants) as well as remote participants enabling virtual attendance. In such a use case, the underlying mobile network will be stressed by the users accessing their devices and even through live streaming from the site [25] as well as accessing the similar services. Especially in the event site, often more restricted mobile uplink capacity becomes the bottleneck when participants stream live content towards the social media or designated users. As a consequence, a large audience is vying for the same network resources within a small area [28], which creates a need for dynamic flexibility of the network. In addition, large crowds would move from one venue to another depending on the time and places (e.g., multiple stages attract varying size of audience). In this case, dynamic network coverage is needed to provide seamless connectivity [29], [30]. The DEDICAT 6G solution for Enhanced Experience focuses on these issues and strives to provide richer quality of experience to local spectators as well as delivering enhanced live experience to remote users using B5G/6G networking.

As the Enhanced Experience Use Case focuses on reducing the gap between local and remote participants for crowded events, several beneficiaries, a.k.a. stakeholders, can be identified depending on the physical location. In the actual event area, the main beneficiaries consist of the local audience who are able to use their mobile devices even in highly congested network. These users are equipped with DEDICAT 6G compatible devices that can enhance their live *Quality of Experience (QoE)* without any annoying network interruptions and these users can therefore easily share their interests to their friends via online streaming. The local users possess the ability to become content creator by performing live streaming using the developed implementation architecture in DEDICAT 6G.

On the consumer side, remote participants are another group of beneficiaries who can possess remote experience of the live event from a remote destination i.e., from their home. This user group is also equipped with smart terminal technology able to get live announcements of live streams as well as browse through the different views of distinct camera sources of the event area. One of the content sources enables live view “see what I see” originating from the smart glasses.

Video service providers can also benefit from the DEDICAT 6G technology in this use case as the *Quality of Service (QoS)* for remote consumers viewing the content has improved. The end users can obtain higher video streaming quality via novel proactive video adaptation against fluctuating network conditions both in UL and DL side. Mobile multicast is one option to distribute the content efficiently to remote spectators within the same area. Dynamic coverage extension introduced by Connected Car (MAP) according to the crowd movement will also ensure improved connection quality, especially on the UL side, which is definitely considered as the bottleneck in the event site. Naturally, improved service quality can increase the financial value of the service(s). Virtual participation, especially during pandemic can increase the number of remote participants significantly.

4.1.1 Detailed Stories

The three stories planned for the Enhanced Experience Use Case, take place in two locations: on-site (public venue such as music concert) and in a remote location (user’s home, etc.) considered as a means for virtual participation. The stories focus on providing a more efficient DEDICAT 6G-powered technology for on-site participants as well as narrowing the border between physical and virtual presence for such public events. To be precise, Story 1

concentrates on improving the on-site experience, Story 2 enhances the virtual experience remotely, and Story 3 combines the previous stories via live service for remote users. A so-called Connected Car has been pre-deployed at the beginning of the concert in order to increase B5G radio capacity in the event site (as part of Coverage Extension).

Story 1: You are participating in a live public event, such as a live music concert with multiple stages, and you are glancing at the event brochure thinking about which artist to see next. Suddenly, your mobile phone alerts you and you receive a live video stream from your friend who has found a great position close to the stage where an artist you are also interested in, is currently performing. You begin the navigation according to the stream and find yourself quickly with your friend to watch your favourite band. After a while, you remember that some of your friends are not participating in the concert at all, and you decide to invite your friends. Since you are connected to a smart mobile network cell, which is enabled with the DEDICAT 6G technology, you can easily launch a mobile video streaming service with your modern smartphone and high-definition camera even if there are a number of other mobile users competing for the same network resources.

From the brochure, you find that each event is scheduled on a different stage. Viewing the event-stage mapping information, you can move to the target stage and find places to watch the event. Since the network adopting the DEDICAT 6G technology will provide dynamic coverage for connectivity extension, you can connect to the network to share/send video streaming content from anywhere in the event venue.

Story 2: You are staying at home when your friend contacts you via mobile and live streams real-time video from a concert. You live through an enhanced remote experience as if you were amongst the members in the audience by using virtual presence through VR glasses. At some point you receive another stream notification from the event organizers, which is yet another access link to a live stream from the concert. Thus, the high-quality content from static cameras is distributed to a large audience for virtual participation in the event. COVID-19 is an excellent example of such a use case, where the event organizers are not necessarily postponing the event, but instead are live streaming the performances to paid users.

Story 3: This story takes place during a concert in an area (stadium, concert park, etc.) where the concert attendees gather and enjoy the shows (different scenes feature various bands and music styles). Then they engage in live streaming activities. Two actors are involved: the main actor –say user X- is a music concert enthusiast who attends a concert, and the second (category of) actor is one of X's FaceBook™ live followers.

4.1.2 Services – Human centric applications

The Enhanced Experience holds two main actors: local attendees in the event site and remote attendees in distance. The local spectators can act as content producers i.e., streaming the video from the site, or as consumers for playing the content provided by other users. The latter one can help to navigate stages of interest or watch simultaneously alternative content from their UEs. Thus, the virtual participants can locate as well nearby the event surroundings but still outside the area.

The content is pushed according to the stories to dedicated video streaming platform developed in the project with the connection to DEDICAT 6G platform for optimizing the service and visualizing the achieved gains in real demonstration. Nokia Data Marketplace can enable the dedicated remote users to access these services in a more secure way. It is also noticeable that on-site users relying on video streaming technology as content producers, may influence annoying audio latency, which emphasizes the technology usage mainly for remote attendees in distance.

Different source cameras were used for generating enhanced virtual experience for the end users. These cameras included normal 2D-cameras originating from USB-based cameras connected to UEs (such as integrated cameras with smartphones) or *eXtended Reality (XR)* capable cameras (such as 360°) for providing free viewpoint possibility and improved virtual experience. Thus, more complex HW & SW in XR devices can increase not only the *End-to-End (E2E)* latency compared to more traditional solutions but may require higher data rate resulting also to high UL usage in the event site. Eventually, the solutions within DEDICAT 6G platform can enable network flexibility with this issue. Finally, the Smart Glasses for enabling improved visual experience are depicted next.

Optinvent provided Smart Glasses to be used in the event site illustrated in Figure 48: The components for the Smart Glasses used in the Enhanced Experience, which produces enhanced content and experience for the end users. Optinvent has provided several ORA-2 smart glasses for the demonstration and pilot events. These devices are running on Android device platform and are connected each to a local smartphone through a Wi-Fi/mobile hotspot, since the glasses do not have 4G or 5G intrinsic connectivity. The glasses are standalone devices that allow users to see bright images while maintaining the transparency of outdoor scene. The glasses have embedded Global Positioning System (GPS) so that position of the user could also be tracked during the event(s) if necessary, but this feature was not used in the Enhanced Experience use case. The ORA-2 smart glasses use KitKat Android version and are compatible with any existing application from Google Play. The streaming from the glasses could be either directly from the glasses or through the user smartphone (used basically as a 5G hotspot). To interact with the glasses, a touch pad or joystick allows the user to go easily through specific menus provided by the application developed for this Use Case.

Figure 48: The components for the Smart Glasses used in the Enhanced Experience

In the final integration phase of the project, we have further developed the Android streaming application for the Smart Glasses, which is visualized in Figure 49. In the final implementation stage, the application holds the streaming functionality using the HW camera towards the DEDICAT 6G video streaming platform including easy-to-use features such as starting and stopping the streaming and selecting the destination for the live stream. The destination in this case, as depicted in WP2 architectural documents, is the edge server functioning as the video streaming platform, which can be located in conjunction with the Connected Car or in the far edge nodes. From the application implementation point of view, the destination name field consists of the access network name together with edge server IP address. The names of the destinations illustrated in Figure 49 c) simply depicts the network type used in

the experiments. We also implemented logging and timestamping system inside the application for measuring the processing delay before video packet is sent to the network.

Figure 49: The developed Android streaming app GUI for the Smart Glasses. a) Basic view, b) Preview mode, c) Destination selection

The implementation supports RTP/UDP streaming with 1280px720p resolution (camera HW limitation) and dynamic frame rate range 3-30fps. RTP/UDP provides slightly better UL latency compared to HTTP/TCP. Camera HW encoder in ORA-2 supports up to 20Mbit/s, but in practice 5Mbit/s outputs are measured which are sufficient for HD resolution video.

The implemented Android application provides also scalability including functional support also the latest Android OS versions. In the latter half of UC2 development, we have integrated and tested the ORA-2 application in latest Android devices in order to compare the Smart Glasses performance against the latest smartphones. These results have been introduced later in Section 4.3.

As introduced earlier, the usage of 360° camera technology can enable XR-based experience for the end users and therefore providing improved virtual experience for remote participants. We have integrated the aforementioned components as part of UC2. However, as 6 different cameras form the final stream to be streamed through the network, it will consume the bandwidth significantly compared to traditional 2D cameras. This will emphasize the importance of UL in multi-user scenarios such as in UC2, where multiple users are vying from the UL resources and congesting the network. Therefore, intelligent DEDICAT 6G components are needed for increasing the capacity and extending the coverage into the borders of the existing network. Figure 50 below illustrates the aforementioned 360 camera with its view in VTT parking area.

Figure 50: 360° streaming technology to be used within UC2. a) Insta 360 Pro 2 camera, b) Panorama 360° view of VTT parking area.

During the evolution of The Enhanced Experience, VTT provided the latest 5G(TN) infrastructure for the pilots as well as the multicast/unicast video streaming platform with the necessary applications and UEs, which are needed specially to support the mobile multicast. During the project, VTT targeted more on enhancing the user's QoS at the event site (production site) rather than in the consumer site (remote site).

The unicast service and Facebook Live™ (see a sample photo, Figure 51 and Figure 52) can be accessed basically with all the modern smartphones, tablets, and laptops. The video transcoding unit associated with video streaming platform generated the necessary formats (e.g., HLS, MPEG-DASH) for successful and supportive playback in various client devices. Figure 51 represents the sample tests using LTE/5G multicast streaming to three end user devices with pre-encoded content.

Currently the multicast is introduced in the 3GPP standardization [41] as *Multicast and Broadcast Services (MBS)* following the evolution of *Multimedia Broadcast/Multicast Service (MBMS)* [40]. The architectural enhancements towards 5G advanced and 6G include improving resource efficiency with the utilisation of inactive and idle states especially with broadcast mode. This would emphasize its usage also for energy-save optimizations.

Figure 51: A sample set of end user devices supporting mobile multicast.

Figure 52: A sample photo of Facebook Live session (Photo by Nicolas LB on Unsplash)

As the Enhanced Experience Use Case involves different scenarios for optimization, we started to implement real-life visualization as an animation of the UC2. This application is intended to perform as a compact demonstrator, which can take real-life measured values as an input and illustrate the system behaviour like a digital twin.

As an example, we have modelled VTT parking area under 5GTN in the Oulu area, where several real measurements can take place and put into the database for later usage in the visualization. In the final phase of UC2, we have completed the coverage extension and computation offloading scenario animations. In the CE scenario, a MAP (Connected Car) with enhanced connectivity is brought near the DEDICAT 6G user(s) who are live streaming from the event site using e.g., smart glasses or mobiles. With the visualization, we can illustrate the CE concept and also to illustrate which DEDICAT 6G components are taking the action in real time (upper left corner in Figure 53). Similarly, we also completed simplified scenario of computation offloading where e.g., video processing can be not only offloaded to far edge, but also distributed via several machines in order to lower the CPU/energy consumption from the edge server and to fulfil processing latency requirements.

The visualization demonstration was built to be an effortlessly portable and lightweight real time simulation that could be easily modified and shown for demonstrative purposes. The actual implementation is done with C++ with assistance of Simple DirectMedia Layer (SDL2)¹³, OpenGL Extension Wrangler Library (GLEW)¹⁴, libcurl¹⁵, ImGui¹⁶, GLM¹⁷, and Blender¹⁸.

¹³ <https://www.libsdl.org/>

¹⁴ <https://glew.sourceforge.net/>

¹⁵ <https://curl.se/>

¹⁶ <https://github.com/ocornut/imgui>

¹⁷ <https://glm.g-truc.net/0.9.9/>

¹⁸ <https://www.blender.org/>

Figure 53: Real-life visualization application for illustrating UC2 scenario. Upper row: Coverage extension; Bottom row: Computation offloading.

As such, we opted to create the program using C++ with an OpenGL 4.5 drawing backend. Libraries used for the program include Simple DirectMedia Layer (SDL2)¹³ for handling platform independent windowing, graphics context creation and input management, *OpenGL Extension Wrangler (GLEW)*¹⁴ for loading OpenGL 4.5 extensions, OpenGL Mathematics (GLM)¹⁷ for linear algebra functions used for host (CPU) side graphics calculations, ImGUI¹⁶ for SDL2 compatible immediate mode GUI functionality (GUI boxes, buttons, text etc.).

One of the ideas of this visualization program, was the ability to use real measurements from an Influx time series database to which CURL¹⁵ would have been used for http communication to query values from a database. For our purposes however, we adopted of using a customizable scenario for purely demonstrative purposes.

The 3D models for the scenario were modelled in 3D modelling suite Blender¹⁸ and exported with a custom script using Blenders Python API.

4.2 Scenario Setup

4.2.1 Pilot setup

The site setup included ultra-high-definition video cameras, mobile devices, Smart Glasses and a B5G capable mobile network consisting of 5G SA, 5G mmWave, and WIFI 6 technologies. The hidden network infrastructure contains dynamic intelligence implemented via enhanced AI algorithms, routing, and distributed computation processing. In addition, Mobile Access Points, namely as Connected Car as introduced in [2], are included to provide dynamic coverage enhancement of which the static indoor/outdoor prototype is depicted in Figure 56 (left), and the mobile robot version used in the pilot in Figure 56 (right).

Depending on crowded users' movements, the position of MAPs can be adjusted to provide robust connections to the users. In addition, considering that the base station can support

users, user association to MAPs and Base Stations (BS) is arranged efficiently for traffic load balancing as well. Figure 54 illustrates the overall setup of the Enhanced Experience.

The on-site equipment comprises mainly of the components related to the human-centric services depicted earlier. These include mainly the end user devices capable of live streaming from the site with wireless connectivity enriched with the latest available B5G connectivity in 5GTN test infrastructure. Next, we will go through the individual components of the pilot implementation.

Figure 54: The setup plan for the Enhanced Experience (UC2)

4.2.1.1.1 Network connectivity

The pilot utilised VTT test network infrastructure with 5G SA @ 3.5GHz on band n78 as well as WI-FI 6 mesh network in dual-band 2.4 and 5GHz. 5G SA and UEs was configured to use best effort 5GI class (9) and UL was prioritized slightly better by using 3/7 frame configuration ratio. Telewell SDX62 model B (Figure 55) and Oneplus 9 Pro were used as 5G modems for providing 5G connectivity to UEs. Open5GS handled the core functionalities of the network. The WI-FI mesh network consisted of 1 anchor cell with wired connection and 1 client cell which was wirelessly connected to the anchor. This setup reproduced the 5G IAB for the backhaul connection in order to provide additional capacity for the event area.

Figure 55: Telewell 5G SDX62 modem used in the UC2 pilot.

4.2.1.1.2 MAP

For the demonstration, we needed to create a mobile access point capable of moving autonomously in an indoor setting. For this we opted to build the MAP on top of a MIR100 mobile robot illustrated in Figure 56 (right). The MIR robot has a 100kg carrying capacity and uses LiDAR and 3D cameras in order to autonomously navigate space between given coordinates. We also installed Aruba AP-577 access point with a pole on top of MiR as well as Eco-flow River Pro portable battery bank using PoE for the access point.

In order to move the MAP between locations, the DEDICAT 6G controller written in Python responsible for controlling the demonstration would send JSON formatted commands to a MiR control server (MiR controller) based on the needs for coverage extension.

MiR controller served as a higher-level interface for controlling the robot and was used to forward commands to the robots REST API. For the purposes of the demonstration, there were two points that represented the MAP being in standby mode and then arriving to the desired location either based on QoS or manually by the team.

4.2.1.1.3 Video UEs and applications

The pilot consisted of the following video devices and applications with their responsibilities:

- Ubuntu UE client: Dedicated measured laptop connected with Full HD USB camera (Logitech Brio 4K). FFmpeg with X264 video encoding application was used to compress the camera feed into UL RTP/UDP to be streamed to the video server from the event site at 1080p resolution, 4Mbit/s and 30fps. The client can receive instruction via script shell API of the preferable network interface to use. Telewell modem was connected with the client to allow 5G connection;
- 360° camera UE client: Intel NUC PC with Ubuntu connected to Insta 8K Pro camera with six lenses forming a 360° degree viewpoint. The video was streamed using FFmpeg and x264 with 4K resolution, 30fps, 40Mbit/s using Telewell modem connection to 5G network. The main purpose of this client was to stress the UL capacity of 5G;
- Smart Glasses: A dedicated video streaming application was implemented for Android, which is described in Section 4.1.2. The network connectivity was handled through 5G-compatible Oneplus 9 Pro smartphone;

- Remote video client: 360° and normal 2D streams were played with legacy smartphone and Ubuntu video playback applications: Insta360Player, mpv.io, and Dash.js. These applications can adapt to network fluctuations when MPEG-DASH format is used.

4.2.1.1.4 Video server

The video server, namely as Video streaming p/f in the architecture, was set up by the needs of the Enhanced Experience use case. The main responsibility of the server was to receive and host the live streams by the users to be accessed by the remote clients. The server was Intel Xeon E5-2680 @ 2.5GHz with 12 cores and 48 CPUs, 64-bit architecture with CentOS Stream 8 operating system, and the server was located in the far edge of the network, physically in 3rd floor of our building. The main responsibilities of the server were:

- Act as the RTSP/RTMP video server to receive live streams from the event site from Smart Glasses, 360° camera client, Smartphones and Ubuntu UE client;
- Act as video transcoder and generate adaptive (MPEG-DASH), multi-resolution video streams from the incoming stream(s);
- Act as video host (content broadcast server) for the remote spectators without storing the content due to GDPR restrictions;
- Act network/device performance database and interactive visualization platform to showcase the KPI values from several indicators;
- Act as an endpoint for NW UL measurements (from event site to edge).

In the pilot we kept these functionalities in a same machine for simplifying the setup, but the architecture visualized in WP2 illustrates how e.g., transcoding is distributed to several machines in order to decrease the load and/or to achieve energy savings as computation of-floading.

Figure 56: Left: Evolved Indoor/outdoor prototype of 5G MAP supporting 5G SA, 5G mmWave and WIFI6 technologies, Right: Mobile MAP used in the UC2 pilot.

4.2.2 Enhanced Experience use case implementation

4.2.2.1 DEDICAT 6G architecture components

The functional decomposition of the interconnection of this Use Case into DEDICAT 6G architecture and platform is fully described in D2.5 and started from implementation point of view in D6.1. During the evolution of the Enhanced Experience platform the refined architectural components alongside with the microservices include the following:

DEDICAT 6G architecture FCs	Description	Enhanced Experience implementation
Dashboard FC	Used for interaction with the <i>Event Organizer</i> in order to manage the deployment and management of the DEDICAT 6G components in the Enhanced Experience architecture	3D visualization application
AuthN FC	Responsible for the granting access of the DEDICAT 6G platform (relying on AuthZ for the "access rights" aspects).	TSDaaS; MQTT, Influx, Grafana
CEDM FC	Communicates with the IDDM FC to check μ S deployment feasibility (Connected car) with possibility to provide counter proposals, and instructs physical deployment of MAP	DEDICAT 6G controller, MiR controller, coverage extension algorithm
IDDM FC	Receives information about the ENs and the microservices and, as output, provides task/Physical System allocation to the Service Orchestrator FC which is responsible for the actual deployment of the tasks (μ S or FC).	Intelligent distribution algorithm
μ S/FC Repository FC	Stores the uploaded microservices such as video streaming platform	Docker
EN Status Agent FC	Provides monitored information about the current status of the edge nodes registered to the DEDICAT 6G platform	Qosium, Grafana, Gavazzi
NW Status Agent FC	Monitors the network of the Enhanced Experience infrastructure	Qosium
μ S/FC Status Agent FC	Provides monitored information about the current status of the microservices being executed in the use case infrastructure	DEDICAT 6G controller
Service Orchestrator FC	Receives recommendations from the IDDM FC and acts over the ENs in order to orchestrate the microservices and FCs deployed over the Enhanced Experience	DEDICAT 6G controller

NW Awareness FC	Provides information on the status of the network of the Enhanced Experience infrastructure	Qosium,
Network Performance Analytics FC	Receives network performance metrics from the μ Services and provides the information to Dashboard FC for visualization and analytics	Qosium Listener
Logging FC	Logs and collects, and stores several types of data of the system and platform behavior	Influx, Grafana
Load Balancing FC	Receives monitored information about the edge nodes and the microservices and acts over the Enhanced Experience infrastructure in order to balance the network and processing load	Influx, Grafana
ConnectedCar Operation FC	Provides a basic management of Connected Car.	DEDICAT 6G controller
MAP Operation FC	Receives CE decisions from CEDM FC and is responsible for implementing them. It is also responsible for the management of the CEaaS delivery life cycle.	DEDICAT 6G controller, MiR controller
Multicast-Broadcast service μ s	(B)5G Networking Equipment; responsible of provisioning the enhanced mobile multicast delivery	BPM
Unicast-Multicast controller μ s	(B)5G Networking Equipment; controlling the unicast-multicast delivery according to number of users	BMSC
Video transcoder μ s	Video transcoding from high quality to adaptive multi-layer representations	FFmpeg, Python
VideoStreaming p/f	Edge node for receiving all the streamed video content from the event site and hosting this content to clients	FFmpeg, Python

4.2.2.2 UC2 specific components

Real-time network performance indicators alongside visualization of the system functionality plays a key role in this use case. The developed functionalities rely on gathering essential network data for directing especially the functionality and performance of the live streaming platform. These parameters include:

- Network delay (maximum accepted network latency);
- Glass-to-Glass latency (maximum accepted latency starting from camera capture ending to display in client screen);
- Throughput (minimum accepted throughput and the increased throughput by the use of MAPs will be also considered as the effect of traffic offloading);

- Number of connected users (needed for switch for multicast to unicast and vice versa);
- Packet loss;
- Signal statistics (e.g., strength, *Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR)*).

One of the used network performance evaluation tools includes Qosium, which *Graphical User Interface (GUI)* is depicted in Figure 57. This SW-based tool performs passive network performance evaluation and gathers the needed and essential network parameters in focus. Qosium holds two parts, namely Qosium Probes and Scope. The Probes are installed to different network nodes of interest. In video streaming scenarios such as in UC2, they were installed in the network nodes related to the video transmission chain: source UE as for the content capture and streaming, edge nodes for content processing (transcoding), and client terminals for content consumption (video playback). During the second phase as an ongoing phase, it is still under investigation if Qosium Probe can be installed directly into the ORA-2 functioning as a rooted service. Alongside the Probes, Qosium Scope and Grafana are used for visualizing and/or gathering the results. During the measurements and piloting, we are sending the Qosium data real-time to the Influx database from which Grafana can retrieve the values for visualization. It suits also better for viewing long-term results and statistics regarding the system behaviour.

Figure 57: Qosium SW network tool for measuring and visualizing the KPIs

Nemo Handy commercial UE software from Keysight was utilised in conjunction with the 5G mmWave evaluation. Currently the 5G mmWave technology and equipment is under optimization at VTT, but some results were gained also in this project. One of the issues is related with the UEs, which tend to overheat especially when loading the DL.

Carlo Gavazzi ET112 and EM111 energy meters are used for determining the power/energy consumption in reliable manner. These meters have been scattered in different nodes of the 5GTN including servers, client devices, and base stations with their respective RRHs, ASiR hubs and system modules. The consumption is measured concerning the whole device, not only for the specific SW processes.

4.2.2.3 Interfaces

The table of interfaces has been introduced in D6.1 (UC2- Interfaces for components on the Enhanced Experience). Additionally, during Phase 2, we have added security and privacy protection framework (*Nokia Data MarketPlace*) into the plan running as an edge service for protecting the video streams against external intrusions. The final UC2 architecture with interfaces is described in D2.4 and D2.5 [1].

4.2.3 Integration report

The paragraph below describes the use of WPs outcomes in the UC2 and the contribution per partner participating in UC2, done during the project.

4.2.3.1 Description of WPs related outcomes used in UC2

Mechanisms for Dynamic Distribution of Intelligence (WP3):

Advancing the computation distribution in edge- and processor level. Finding the best practices for lowering the power/energy consumption in the video processing tasks (e.g., transcoding) with optimal real-time performance, which are relevant items for UC2. Testing and developing these distributed computing techniques into UC2 platform.

Mechanisms for Dynamic Coverage Extension (WP4):

Coverage extension algorithms and design for UC2 event scenario with dynamic/pre-deterministic MAP placement. Implementing and designing the actual MAP as a ConnectedCar into VTT premises in Oulu.

Mechanisms for Security, Privacy and Trust (WP5):

WP5 provided security and trust framework for Enhanced Experience use case with access control on both producer and consumer sides. This involved evolving the security and trust framework via Nokia Data Marketplace and integrating it partially with UC2 video streaming architecture especially in the downlink side between the video streaming platform (edge server) and end consumers.

4.2.3.2 Description of contribution per partner in UC2

UoS: Considering a group of UEs and multiple APs including MAPs and BSs, the efficient user association and resource allocation is required to provide robust connection to a group of UEs. During Phase 2, UoS has started to design how to associate UEs requiring different QoS to multiple UEs and allocate powers considering the power constraints. The algorithm has been designed for the case of pre-deterministic MAP placement. In the final phase, improvement of this algorithm was carried out to include dynamics of MAP positions so that real-time mobility of UEs can be efficiently managed.

ORANGE: Orange designed decision-making algorithms for resource orchestration, depending on the service requirements and with isolation guarantees for security purposes. In particular, the algorithm determined where to place the services on the different edge servers. The services include live video database, video processing functions, and any other function necessary for providing services to end-users. The placement has to find a compromise between uplink latency (for content production) and downlink latency (for content delivery), while being energy efficient. Of course, the quality of the service must be considered by providing enough resources (computing, memory, storage) to the functions and keeping the latency within acceptable bounds, defined by the services. The available resources must be shared by all the functions fairly, so that all the services run within the accepted quality. The algorithm is part of the Intelligence Distribution Decision-Making Functional Component.

VTT: Selecting the right components for the UC2 pilot during building the HW infrastructure in 5GTN and evaluating and measuring their performance from device and network (5G) perspective. Integrating and evaluating Smart Glasses as a part of UC2. Organizing a public pilot event in April 2023. VTT has also finalized the 3D-animation of UC2, which can visualize the scenarios like digital twin. Distributed computation in the edge server(s) has been tested and evaluated for enabling lower power/energy consumption in the edge, and also to load

balance the access network. Finally, measurements with 5G mmWave for considering IAB connection to ConnectedCar was done.

OPTIN: Optinvent and VTT have co-operated and developed an Android application suitable for live streaming in the ORA-2 Smart Glasses focusing on especially on the needs for integrating this device with DEDICAT 6G platform. A survey from novel versions of Smart Glasses has been also done in terms of introducing latest Glasses in the last phase. In addition, the preliminary performance of the application and ORA-2 has been done and is reported in Section 4.3.

VLF: Implementation of private permissioned blockchain and collection of smart contracts for security and trust management framework, described in D5.2 and D5.3.

4.2.3.3 Description of external assets used in UC2

The test facility 5GTN in Oulu has been used, developed, and upgraded in various national and international projects during the last few years, and it is in continuous evolution phase for utilizing the actual HW and SW components in B5G. Generally speaking, past national projects (such as Finnish 5G-FORCE¹⁹) have been the basis for 5GTN, and nowadays it is updated and upgraded by the different vertical projects. H2020 projects 5G-HEART²⁰ and 5G-ENHANCE²¹ have preceded the 4G/5G validation trials with live video streaming including also mobile multicast. Some of the streaming solutions developed and validated in these projects were exploited in UC2 by enhancing and tailoring these solutions with DEDICAT 6G architectural components with increased intelligence and flexibility for adapting real-time video against the network fluctuations. In addition, 6G-XR H2020 project starting at the beginning of 2023 focuses partially on lowering the energy consumption in XR streaming, which can form synergies with UC2 following the work initiated in CONVINCENCE²² project. UC2 also evolved the Monica²³ work with the ORA-2 Smart Glasses for dedicating the applications specifically on enhancing the real-time end user experience from a large event. Furthermore, the ongoing Terminet²⁴ project also utilizes the Smart Glasses for real-time remote attendance, which can also form possible synergies from streaming application perspective.

4.3 Evaluation and final results

Next, we illustrate the final results across the different selected KPIs gathered during the pilot and laboratory evaluation. The measurements in 5GTN test bed have been conducted by using the tools and techniques shown in Section 4.2.2.2. It is notable that some of the KPI targets and results have been verified extensively in the final deliverables of other WPs.

¹⁹ <https://5gtnf.fi/projects/5g-force/>

²⁰ <https://5gheart.org/>

²¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/815056>

²² <https://www.celticnext.eu/project-convince/>

²³ <https://www.monica-project.eu/>

²⁴ <https://terminet-h2020.eu/>

4.3.1 List of KPIs, target values and gain

4.3.1.1 KPIs and target values

The key characteristics of this Use Case can be summarized as real-time video streaming services for heavily crowded users and local distant users by using dynamic coverage provision with MAPs. Thus, the performance evaluation is focused on effects of dynamic coverage extension and impacts on real-time video streaming. Table 7 illustrates the KPI list with target and baseline values.

From the dynamic coverage extension perspective, service availability and edge offloading factor performance could be measured as well as decreased energy consumption mostly from the individual devices.

- Service availability: when the area of *Point of Interest (PoI)* is given for outdoor events, the video streaming service should be available for the whole area by either the ground base station or MAPs. Thus, the coverage where the service of required QoS is satisfied within the area of PIs;
- Edge offloading performance: due to the surge of end users crowded for the event, it is expected that the *ground BS (gBS)* capacity is not sufficient enough for all users. Since MAPs can be deployed for traffic offloading, the effectiveness of offloading in the system is measured. The performance is compared to the case of not using MAPs. Of course, this performance would highly rely on the number of deployed MAPs. In the final physical pilot, a single MAP was deployed and deployment of higher number of MAPs was verified via simulations;
- Decreased energy consumption: The developed solutions should contribute to decreased energy consumption in the network devices depending on the scenario. The savings can include servers, UEs or network components from mobile network infrastructure.

From the perspective of the real-time video streaming, service reliability measured by *Packet Loss Rate (PLR)*, service latency, and throughput per each user can be measured.

- Service reliability (measured by Packet Loss Rate): it represents the ratio of the number of lost packets to the total number of sent packets. When video streaming data is transmitted, the PLR directly impacted the quality of experiences at the end users. Thus, end-to-end packet loss ratio is measured;
- Service Latency: to make sure that the good quality of video streaming can be transmitted successfully, a low level of network delay performance needs to be guaranteed. The network delay comprises both uplink and downlink, but in the UC2 scenario especially the uplink delay is the more critical one. Along with the network delay, the overall end-to-end latency is measured which comprises the whole transmission chain starting from camera capture ending to video playback in the UE display;
- Throughput per user: the scenario focuses more on fulfilling the needs of a large audience group as congested crowd rather than serving individual users with the limits of promised B5G network speeds. Adaptive streaming is a flexible option in terms of available network resources at an arbitrary point in time. The throughput target can also be identified in the window of square meters;

Table 7: UC2 – Enhanced experience KPIs list

KPI ID	Description	Target value	Baseline
UC2_KPI1	Service (video) Latency	Network delay (either UL or DL) <10ms	5G as a baseline, shall be maintained / improved in congested scenarios using DEDICAT 6G architecture. The values are defined for live video transmission. "For live streaming in crowded areas, services for media production, augmented reality for collaborative gaming etc.: 20ms end-to-end (UL+DL) ([39], Annex A"
		E2E latency < 200ms	Motion-to-Photon or (Glass-to-Glass) latency; starting from camera capture ending to screen display. Literature indicates that higher latencies than 200ms affect negatively to QoE [32].
UC2_KPI2	Throughput for each user	Bitrate >5Mbit/s	Good bitrate for full HD video ranges from 3.5-6Mbits/s and we set 5Mbit/s as a target. For certain devices (i.e., Smart Glasses) some device-specific constraints apply. In [39], 3GPP standard, 50Mbit/s UL data rate is recommended for broadband access in a crowd in a confined area, such as in music concert with half million people/km ² (30% of active UE users).
UC2_KPI3	Service reliability	PLR <10 ⁻³	Our target and baseline from the 5G/3GPP standard [39]. No need in our case to have higher reliability; even random packet losses are accepted.
UC2_KPI4	Service availability	99%	Service should be available within the whole event area, including its boundaries. Introducing the MAP(s) can also improve the availability.
UC2_KPI5	Edge offloading performance	>50%	The use of MAPs in a heavy traffic load area can offload the traffic served by BSs. Compared to the case of no MAPs, the gain of traffic offloading is measured.
UC2_KPI6	Decreased energy consumption (servers / UEs)	<10Mbit/J	In this use case we aim to reduce energy in UEs and edge server(s) using the intelligent mechanism for distributing the load between servers and computing architectures, and also via proper video parametrization. Furthermore, we show that latest HW/SW process the video bits more energy-efficiently than the baseline devices selected during the project proposal phase.

The pilot measurements as well as other evaluations were logged into an Influx v2.7.1 time series database after which they could be viewed in real time using Grafana v10.1.2 monitoring tool. As Influx 2.X versions have a requirement of passing an access token alongside any measurement, an appropriate token was always included in a program or a script which enabled also security for the database.

Qosium (see Section 4.2.2.2) was used to measure the network performance in real-time. Qosium Probes were installed to Ubuntu UE client, 360° camera client, and video server and these devices were synchronized accurately via PTP master, which was additional edge server dedicated only for this purpose. Accurate time synchronization is needed in order to measure the service latency and especially network delay reliably.

Passing the measurements from Qosium into an Influx database was done using a listener program created for this purpose. The program was built in C++ and is used to receive measurements from Qosium using their helper library and parse them into a character string. CURL was then used to send the parsed measurements into the Influx server using the Influx line protocol. This was done in real-time.

Power measurements were created using a Carlo Gavazzi EM111 energy meter and a UWP 3.0 monitoring gateway. The measurements were then read from the UWP using a purpose-built Python script and sent to an Influx database with the use of Python's influxdb-client module²⁵.

²⁵ <https://pypi.org/project/influxdb-client/>

4.3.1.2 Evaluation and results

Table 8 summarizes the current evaluation results and preliminary gains. These are explained in detail in the following sub-sections.

Table 8: UC2 – Results obtained and gain

KPI ID	Evaluation method	Result	Gain
UC2_KPI1	Service latency is measured by placing the Qosium Probes to video source (smart glasses/smartphone), MEC, and in video client. By this both uplink and downlink network delay can be measured. End-to-end application latency is measured by recording the millisecond chronometer, encoding, transmitting and displaying the chronometer value in client display, which results in end-to-end latency.	Figure 60-63, Table 9	The results show that 10ms network delay is reachable in low congestion scenario. E2E latency < 200ms was achieved.
UC2_KPI2	Throughput is measured by placing the Qosium Probes to video source (smart glasses/smartphone), MEC, and in video client. Qosium Scope can then measure and collect the sent/received throughput from the specific network interface.	Figure 64 - Figure 67	5Mbit/s video achievable when using MAP and latest 5G technology in crowded scenarios.
UC2_KPI3	Service reliability is measured by placing the Qosium Probes to video source (smart glasses/smartphone), MEC, and in video client. The service reliability is then monitored and collected using Qosium packet loss ratio indicator.	Section 4.3.1.2.3	Service reliability was measured as planned and achieved during the demonstrations
UC2_KPI4	Service availability is measured as a ratio between uptime and downtime. Dedicated scripts (e.g., Python) was used for collecting the up- and downtimes, and for calculating the service availability.	Section 4.3.1.2.4	Service availability was achieved.
UC2_KPI5	Edge offloading performance is measured with S/W simulation-based patterns, where traffic over MAPs is divided by the total network traffic.	Figure 68, Table 10	124-207% improvement depending on number of users
UC2_KPI6	Energy consumption of different network nodes and servers were measured by placing Carlo Gavazzi energy meters to desired devices and comparing the results with baseline values.	Figure 69-71	Reduced energy consumption via video parametrization and BS configuration

Figure 58 illustrates the Grafana KPI visualization during the UC2 pilot in April 2023. We focused on showcasing the network throughputs and UL delays. The throughput was measured from the DEDICAT 6G Video server both as a total received throughput (the sum of all the clients) as well as from the Ubuntu UE client of which was measured also from network delay point of view. The Service availability and reliability were over 99% during the pilot event, no break-downs were observed for the live stream in focus.

Figure 58: Grafana visualization window during the UC2 pilot.

4.3.1.2.1 Service latency

In the Phase 2 of UC2, two aspects of video latency were measured: Video processing delay for the developed Android Smart Glasses video application, and video network latency in the uplink using the latest 5G SA technology integrated in VTT facilities (5G NR TDD Rel-16 SA @ 3.5GHz (band n78), BW = 60MHz). These results introduce the final status of the implementation. It is important to identify the processing delay (video capture + encoding + packetization) in the application level before the packet is ready to be transmitted in the network,

because it can have huge influence on total service latency (Glass-to-Glass) regardless of the used network.

Figure 59 illustrates the processing delay with the target bitrates for the developed Android application. We tested the application against ORA-2 Smart Glasses by Optinvent running on Android Kitkat as well as with the latest Motorola moto 5G+ smartphone running on the latest Android 11. As can be seen, ORA-2 performs well when using lower video resolution. Thus, with higher resolution it is evident that processing delay increases due to low processing capabilities by the computing HW, which is acceptable for considering the actual small-size device. Even if ORA-2 camera has 5Mpixels AF, the ORA-2 display is a real 480p (display resolution of 800x480) and usually the glasses are used to receive video with this resolution for hands-free functionality. Then, if we consider 480p only, we are equivalent to Motorola smartphone.

Figure 59: The processing delay comparison between ORA-2 Smart Glasses and Motorola moto 5G+.

As UC2 concentrates especially on live video streaming in crowded (congested) environment, we measured how additional data traffic, possibly from other users, affects to the video delay. Thus, the mobile uplink can be the bottleneck when live streaming from the event site. Uplink is relatively low even in commercial networks since operators do not see any real need for increasing its volume. The results are illustrated in Figure 63 where blue line represents the UL video delay over 5G, and green the additional data throughput generated with iPerf over another 5G access point. As we used $\frac{1}{4}$ data slot configuration for UL/DL share, the maximum UL capacity was measured approximately to 60Mbps by using Telewell modems. In this measurement, 4Mbps video at full HD resolution was used. From the curves, we see that network congestion increases also the delay for the video user and eventually leads to over 100ms delays (not visible in the curves) possibly alongside with significant packet loss rate. In Phase 3, after finalizing the MAP, we aim to show that we can reach lower network delay even at congested and low coverage scenarios by utilising the DEDICAT 6G architectural components in the MAP placement.

In the final Phase in UC2, we continued the network and glass-to-glass latency measurements in a real environment both during the UC2 pilot as well as in 5G laboratory at VTT. Figure 60 illustrates the network UL delay between Ubuntu UE client and Video server during the Spring pilot. The green curve shows the 5G SA delay and yellow WIFI6. For demonstrative purposes, we instructed the MAP to move from origin to near the user manually without activating the QoS threshold based on network UL delay and/or packet loss. This was mostly because other demonstrations in the same event used also the 5G network and we avoided to interfere with their system functionality. From the figure we can see that WIFI operates extremely well in indoor conditions in terms of UL delay and improves the QoS for the video user without any noticeable difference in the live video stream.

Figure 60: Network UL delay for 5G and WIFI during the UC2 pilot.

After the pilot, we focused also on using and evaluating the performance of the indoor MAP (see Figure 56) especially with the 5G mmWave technology to be used as IAB with 5G. *Two-way Active Management Protocol (TWAMP)* was used in the layer-3 delay measurements alongside with Qosium at the application layer. TWAMP uses its own server at 5G edge against which the measurements are run. Figure 61 illustrates the UL delay results measured with Qosium with different video bitrates. The maximum UL capacity was near 250Mbits/s, which nearly double compared to 5G SA UL capacity at this moment with 3/7 frame configuration. The 5G mmWave delay stays relatively similar level, but it is evident UL is not optimized yet with the radio.

Figure 61: UL delay measured with live video stream using next generation 5G mmWave equipment.

With TWAMP, we used a video profile for the packet traffic with 1272 bytes packets sent every 10ms and measured the *Round-trip Time (RTT)* for these packets. This resulted to 1 Mbit/s stream of which RTT is shown in Figure 62. This RTT is lower than the UL delay in previous figure, because the measurement is done in different measurement layer and directly from the UE. With Qosium, laptop is needed with UE tethering which causes extra delay in the measurement.

Figure 62: 5G mmWave round trip times for video packets measured with TWAMP and Nemo Handy.

One of the interesting KPIs was the service latency, which is basically the observed E2E latency of the live video streaming system. Naturally high network delay increases also the E2E latency, but for example the implemented coverage extension method using MAP can decrease the E2E latency. Table 9 illustrates the achieved service latencies for the developed Android streaming application measured with Motorola smartphone since it was difficult to measure the E2E latency through the Smart Glasses. As a reference, we showcase similar numbers for FFMpeg streaming application measured with Ubuntu laptop. The measurement is done by recording a digital, millisecond-accurate clock from a screen 1 with the 5G Android/Ubuntu device and playing the content from a wired Ubuntu laptop with mpv.io player application with low latency options without caching or buffering the incoming video packets (screen 2). Finally, we took pictures together from both of these streams and compared the values of digital clocks. For the ORA-2 application, we got E2E latencies below and above 200ms, which was our target. The results are good since we did not extremely optimize the streaming application. It is noticeable that already camera capture takes approximately 30ms as seen in Figure 59.

Table 9: Video service latencies for the Android and Ubuntu applications.

OS playback application	E2E latency (min)	E2E latency (max)	E2E latency (avg)
Android (ORA-2)	143ms	234ms	216ms
Ubuntu (Dell Core i9)	135ms	216ms	175ms

Figure 63: The effect of data rate to video uplink delay over 5G.

4.3.1.2.2 Throughput – Multicast vs unicast

The mobile multicast service is installed into VTT 5GTN and it has been currently tested against the Rel-14 version. In Phase 3 we are aiming at demonstrating the system against latest releases as well as with measured energy consumption values. Thus, the MBMS standardisation is active beyond Rel-17 and they are now boosting its importance in live streaming also from the commercial and sustainability point of view to be used not only for saving network load in the backbone, but also with less and efficient usage of resources. As UC2 tries to reach wide remote audience to access the live streams from the event site, possibly within the same radio cell, mobile multicast can do it efficiently by utilising the video streaming platform connected to the DEDICAT 6G platform. Figure 64 shows two benefits from the measurements conducted in 5GTN. On the left, it is seen that eMBMS can serve higher number of clients regardless of the multicast channel share allocation (during the measurements we had less DL capacity and bandwidth available than now). Secondly on the right figure, we see and validate how MBMS dynamic resource allocation performs; basically, it can reserve multicast resources in the base station in real-time and narrow down the unicast share as well. It is also notable that processor-based multicasting is also used as a spreading pattern for distributed communication, as introduced i.e., in D3.1.

Figure 64: Results of MBMS benefit and dynamic resource allocation between multicast and unicast channels.

The Ubuntu UE throughputs are illustrated in Figure 65. The target bit rate for the UE was set to 10Mbit/s with variable rate control by the x264 encoder. The “breaks” to zero are caused only by the change from one network to another (5G to WIFI and vice versa), but in reality, there was no breaks in the video stream. Similarly, in Figure 66 the total throughput for the video server is depicted.

Figure 65: Network UL throughput for 5G and WIFI during the UC2 pilot.

Figure 66: Network total UL throughput for 5G and WIFI during the UC2 pilot.

Figure 67 shows the current maximum UL throughput when using 5G mmWave technology and stressed the UL to its limits. As stated earlier, the maximum capacity at this moment is approximately 250Mbit/s for the uplink which is nearly double than 5G SA at VTT premises.

Figure 67: 5G mmWave uplink throughput measured with Openspeedtest and Nemo Handy.

4.3.1.2.3 Service Reliability

Service reliability was measured using Qosium packet loss indicator between Ubuntu UE video client and video server. During the pilot, we did not observe or monitor any packet losses which values were shown as zero. This yields partially from the set delay threshold (or manual threshold) for the MAP instructing to bring coverage to the site.

4.3.1.2.4 Service Availability

Service availability was measured by evaluating the video service uptime from the several test sessions during the testing, pre-pilots, and pilot. The service was stable during these sessions, which makes the system availability to 100%.

4.3.1.2.5 Edge Offloading Performance

By using MAPs, we can expect the edge offloading effect. In the case that there are many UEs requesting higher data rate, the ground BS would not be able to satisfy all UEs by supporting their required QoS. Additionally, for UEs at the cell edge, the received signal level would not be strong enough even though a gBS has the capacity to support UEs. In both cases, by deploying MAPs for the function of additional BSs, traffic can be offloaded. The gain achieved using MAPs is defined as the edge offloading factor and calculated as the ratio of data traffic sent by MAPs among the overall network traffic loads. Additionally, the area spectral efficiency is considered to show the effectiveness of edge offloading. By using two performance indicators, we measure the edge offloading performance of the proposed solution using MAPs and compare to the basic case that the only gBS provides the data service to UEs (without MAPs).

Figure 68: Edge Offloading Factor for different number of UEs.

As a ratio of transmitted data over MAPs among total transmitted data, the edge loading factor is illustrated in Figure 68. Two MAPs are assumed to be deployed with one gBS and the edge offloading factor is measured for different number of UEs. As the number of UEs increases, the amount of data traffic sent by MAPs tends to increase. For example, when there are 5 UEs, 32.56Mbps can be transmitted via MAPs, then it increases to 62.7453Mbps for the case of 25 UEs. Regardless of the number of UEs, the edge offloading factor could remain above 0.5.

Edge offloading factor is also measured in terms of *Area Spectral Efficiency (ASE)* as shown in Figure 68. Similar to the setup for Table 10, ASE is monitored for multiple number of UEs. For all cases of different number of UEs, deployment of MAPs leads to increase ASE.

Table 10: UC2 - Area Spectral Efficiency [bps/Hz/km²] for different number of UEs

No. of Users	5	10	15	25
Without MAPs	1.5701	2.8754	3.5362	4.7999
with MAPs	4.8262	6.6213	9.6408	10.7745
Improvement [bps/Hz/Km ²]	3.2560	3.7458	6.1046	5.9745
Improvement (%)	207.37	130.27	172.63	124.47

4.3.1.2.6 Energy consumption

One of the overall targets in DEDICAT 6G is to reduce the energy (or power) consumption during the live streaming. In UC2 context, we have identified that video parametrization and distributed computing can decrease the needed energy consumption. Video parametrization with less complex compression algorithms and optimal resolution selection (see also Figure 59) can lead to energy savings already in the capturing/sending device located in the event site. Furthermore, novel processing schemes in the edge servers (needed especially for video transcoding in order to enable network adaptation against different client devices and access networks) can balance the load from centralized servers. There are already good results from the computation perspective presented in D3.1 [3], D3.2 [6], and D3.3 [7].

Figure 69 illustrates real-time video encoding realized in an edge server for generating MPEG-DASH compatible 4-layered stream in order to enable adaptive HTTP streaming against network fluctuations and to enable flexibility for different client devices with varying playback characteristics. We utilize FFmpeg with x264 SW encoding, which is also needed in order to have dynamic, real-time configurability with the distributed offloading control.

In this case, the resolutions and bitrates were selected according to the 5G XR specifications [43] for H.264. The red curve 'combined' indicates for encoding all the video representation layers simultaneously, and the others individually according to the series name. It is notable that nowadays widely used, although already quite obsolete, 720p (HD ready) and 1080p (full HD) can be encoded/transcoded relatively easily using powerful HW. As depicted also in D2.5, we use Intel Xeon E5-2860@2.5 GHz processor with 64-bit instruction set with 48 CPUs (2 threads for each core). In the final phase, we aim at utilizing the DEDICAT 6G platform in decision-making for selecting the best edge server candidate and directing the video processing towards the optimal location.

Figure 69: Power consumption of real-time encoding (centralized (combined) vs distributed).

By using similar encoding structures as above, we also tested the client-side power consumption by using different mobile network technologies, illustrated in Figure 70. Dash.js player was run in Chrome browser, which was installed in Dell E6420 Core i7@2.7GHz laptop, and power measured using Carlo Gavazzi energy consumption meter. The video clips were streamed from the video streaming platform using the illustrated access network technologies. From the Figure 70 we see that a) access network technology does not have an influence on the in-device power consumption, b) video resolution and/or bitrate has significant influence on the client, especially with higher resolutions. It is also notable that video client can adapt the stream towards lower quality in order to save energy. Thus, video adaptation can be also done at the server side in order to lower down the transmission energy (transmitted bits).

Figure 70: Client power consumption using different bitrates and mobile network technologies in live streaming.

Figure 71 shows how much energy can be saved in base stations, if *Discontinuous Transmission (DTX)* is enabled for single-client scenario. The left figure is without DTX and right figure with DTX enabled. Approximately 50W can be reduced from energy consumption if the base station is under relatively heavy load (in this case 100Mbit/s).

Figure 71: 5G base station energy consumption for DL when using adaptive DTX during live video streaming.

4.3.1.3 Feedback analysis and evaluation

The Enhanced Experience pilot had several visitors; almost all the people amongst the event participants reviewed the demonstration. The DEDICAT 6G UC2 team received good feedback, future suggestions, and fruitful long discussions with the audience, which also continued beyond the official duration of the pilot. The main feedback and concerns from the audience were the following ones with respect to the answers of the UC2 pilot team:

- *In such mass event scenarios, where do the real needs and advantages of 6G come from and how does DEDICAT 6G address those?*

For future live streaming scenarios over 6G, it is not about extremely high throughputs for single user, but more likely to fill the QoS needs for a large group of people within the same base station/area. Future mobile networks demand dynamic intelligence to adapt the needs of users also in weak(er) signal areas. With the architecture of DEDICAT 6G the more

de-centralized distribution and intelligence will meet the expectations better different use cases. Greener networking favours also DEDICAT 6G architecture since dynamicity can also lead to decreased energy consumption.

- *What are the possible takeaways to standardization in this Use Case?*

Specifically in this use case, VTT is not contributing to standardization, but is involved strongly especially in 5G Trials working group. Thus, UC2 partners UoS and Orange are also strongly involved with the 6G architecture specification with inputs.

- *5G IAB may revolutionize and bring evident benefits on the path to 6G*

UC2 team agreed that IAB concept may generalize and arouse more interest in the near future. Use of IAB donor with IAB nodes can extend the coverage, such as in sports events.

- *Smart Glasses will generalize in future and the evolution should look more and more like "normal glasses"*

The Smart Glasses -as compensatory equipment for VR glasses- are definitely a future approach in terms of comfortability. As the processor can be fit to smaller and smaller physical spaces. As Optinvent introduced in D7.3 [50], the future optical lens technology is more similar to traditional glasses.

- *How AR could be used to visualize some additional information or feedback also back to the event streamers?*

This was an interesting comment since UC2 concentrates only on streaming from the event site. But from the Smart Glasses evaluations during the project, this AR information as feedback for the streamer could involve some network specific data in terms of network QoS (such as simple as green, yellow, or red indicator) or some feedback from the remote audience, which could be enabled as an optional feature. Although we implemented some delay tolerance to the streaming application which may occur due to low connectivity, the DEDICAT 6G platform should ensure the satisfying QoS for each use.

- *Hands-free streaming to social media has clear benefits especially in mass events such as music concerts*

This was an expected comment, and such wearable streaming technology will be a future approach. As the GUI and operation i.e., for the Smart Glasses is a bit difficult the use of streaming application should be as simple as possible.

- *What are the other Use Cases and their goals in DEDICAT 6G project?*

UC2 team introduced the other DEDICAT 6G use cases, environments and their goals. In overall the feedback was positive not only for the UC2 but also for high-level goals of the project. Dynamicity and real-time intelligence and decision-making will be 6G assets.

5 UC3: PUBLIC SAFETY

5.1 Scenario and stories

Public Protection and Disaster Relief (PPDR) and Public Safety organizations rely on reliable and efficient communications to respond to natural or man-made disasters. In most cases, PPDR and Public Safety organizations own their critical infrastructures which are operated at national level or small cell for tactical or urgent needs.

These infrastructures must be available at anytime, anywhere and make all communications efficient for voice or data. With the beginning of 5G deployment, organizations are looking to apply their critical communications on this new technology and balance the choice of solution depending on the long term investment.

DEDICAT 6G aims to deliver the high level of reliability as expected by PPDR and Public Safety organizations, by combining the use of operated connectivity (Public or Private) and the high-quality services of a dynamic and split architecture which serve users on the field.

The Public Safety Use Case has been described in the deliverables D2.1 and updated in D2.3 through two contexts: connectivity lost after a natural disaster and network failure during a large event. The related stories have been described in deliverables D2.1, D2.3, D6.1 and D6.2.

The Public Safety use case showcased:

- **Dynamic coverage extension** via robots or cars combined with heterogeneous wireless connectivity options (Wi-Fi, 3G, 4G, 5G, B5G/6G) to ensure network availability, ultra-low latency and ultra-fast response times;
- **Distributed intelligence** to achieve a near-optimal efficient placement of computation and AI functions (FCs, μ Ss and NF) in the network with respect to selected multi-objective KPIs (energy consumption, latency, reliability, and availability);
- Interoperability to enable **efficient communication** with and among a multitude of devices and systems (e.g., cameras, drones, AGVs, smartphones, diverse sensors, etc.);
- **Complementing PPDR systems easily and cost-efficiently** with additional devices and functionalities, e.g., through the exploitation of drones/AGVs hosting diverse functions/services, analytics-driven and user-oriented feedback;
- **Context aware access control** for emergency personnel and context-based evacuation route opening through otherwise closed doors and inaccessible areas.

5.1.1 Detailed Stories

Public Safety and PPDR users rely on Critical Communications in two main environments:

- Non-urban or natural disaster: there is no, or a lack in, infrastructure to support critical communication;
- Urban environment: during a crisis, the increased number of connected devices and the use of social Medias for a live snapshot sharing from the event in real-time cause failure or overloading of infrastructure .

Each story elucidates what is demonstrated and which are the components used from DEDICAT 6G platform and what is measured during the pilot.

Context #1: non-urban or natural disaster

The first context demonstrates loss of connectivity after a natural disaster through three stories related to three phases which could be encountered during crisis management:

- Connectivity recovery after disaster;

- Mission management capability with MCX;
- Enabling public communication for victims.

The first story mainly addresses the following components:

- Dynamic Coverage Extension: evaluation of time to deploy coverage (WP4);
- Distribution of Intelligence: evaluation of intelligence readability (WP3).

The second story addresses the following components:

- Dynamic Coverage Extension: evaluation of time to deploy coverage (WP4);

The third story addresses the following components:

- Distribution of Intelligence (WP4);
- Efficient communications.

Context #2: connectivity failure during a large event

The second context describes a connectivity failure during a large public event. Three stories related to three phases which could be encountered during the response to an incident:

- Support local connectivity;
- Welcome First Responders connection;
- Support video flow in real-time for leveraging situational awareness.

The first story mainly addresses the following components:

- Distribution of Intelligence: evaluation of intelligence readability (WP3);

The second addresses the following components:

- Dynamic Coverage Extension: evaluation of time to deploy coverage (WP4);

The third story addresses the following components:

- Distribution of Intelligence (WP4);
- Efficient multimedia communications.

This second context is similar to the use case 2: "Enhanced Experience". The UC3 Context #2 differs in the prioritization service offered to PPDR and Public Safety users comparing to consumer users. The 3GPP *Mission Critical Services (MCS)* define the capability of a Broadband system to prioritize some resources versus others, especially to support critical communications.

5.1.2 Services – Human centric applications

5.1.2.1 Mission Critical users' application

MCS are integrated to the DEDICAT 6G cloud infrastructure. Based on the orchestrator and agent notification, the platform is able to deploy services where it matters to offer efficient and resilient connectivity.

Based on a cloud server – mobile client architecture, the MCX solution has been split into several components that support the different MCX services independently from others. This Edge Computing oriented architecture allows the system to automatically redeploy a component in case of a service loss, in order to support critical communications resiliency but also to deploy a specific component to leverage the service efficiency, e.g., MC-PTT in case of an overloaded audio service.

To benefit from mission critical services provided by the DEDICAT 6G Platform, users need to connect to the services by using a client application. All the critical features shall be delivered through the same application. This application has supported the showcasing of access to the platform and performing evaluation.

Figure 72: MCX Client application

The MCX Client application shall provide Mission Critical *Push-To-Talk (PTT)* (voice) group call, Mission Critical video call, video streaming and Mission Critical Data mapping (as shown on Figure 72).

To implement the MCX Client, the mission critical services deliver interfaces allowing the use of main services (voice, video, or data).

5.1.2.2 Smart Glasses

Optinvent provided 4 ORA-2 smart glasses for the pilot. These devices are Android device platforms and each has been connected through a local smartphone to a Wi-Fi hotspot to be able to connect to the Internet, since the glasses do not have 4G or 5G intrinsic connectivity. The glasses are standalone devices that allow users to see bright images while maintaining the transparency of outdoor scene. The glasses have embedded GPS so that the position of the user could also be tracked during the event. This feature wasn't used during the pilot. The ORA-2 smart glasses use KitKat Android version and are compatible with main existing applications from Google Play store.

To interact with the glasses, a touch pad (located on the glasses temple) allows the user to go through a specific menu provided by the application, developed for this Use Case. However, for the sake of better ergonomics and in order to let the user be fully focused on the event, an accessory Joystick with Bluetooth connection to the glasses is possible to connect as depicted in Figure 73.

Figure 73: The components for the Smart Glasses used in the Public Safety use case

5.1.2.3 Coverage extension

5.1.2.3.1 Coverage extension with Clearpath Robotics Jackal Unmanned Ground Vehicle as Mobile Access Point

In the scope of this Use Case pilot, a Clearpath Robotics Jackal Unmanned Ground Vehicle/AGV was used as a MAP to reach a specific location with the aim of providing users with opportunistic wireless network for coverage extension. For demonstration purposes this is accompanied by a **coverage extension visualization dashboard** (Figure 74-Figure 78) that is connected to the robot and is also **integrated with an implementation of coverage extension mechanisms from WP4** (specifically the mechanism managing robot based MAPs described in section 4.5 of D4.2 [8] and section 5.1 of D4.3 [9]) and with **an implementation of the Threat identification and classification mechanism from WP5** (described in detail in section 6.1 of D5.2 [10] and 7.1 of D5.3 [11]).

There are two instantiations for the coverage extension visualisation dashboard: one for indoor and one for outdoor settings. The coverage extension visualisation dashboard allows the emulation of different user positions and consequently scenarios through the "new scenario" button. The virtual space of the application corresponds to the representation of an area of interest created for the lidar. The dashboard allows the configuration of the scenario by dragging and dropping users to different locations.

For this scenario it is assumed that the coverage range of Access Points (green), and Mobile Access Points (Yellow) is one square (in each direction). Outside of that range users have connectivity issues that need to be solved.

In this demo scenario two types of Mobile Access Points are considered: virtual (dummy) and one that corresponds to the actual Clearpath Robotics Jackal. The dashboard allows viewing robots/AGVs in two-dimensional graphics (Figure 75) or in 3D space (Figure 76). A location in the area of interest can be selected to view the coordinates. Users connected to the two networks (fixed Access Points or MAPs) are shown on the map represented with the human icon.

As long as they are connected to one of these networks, the icon remains green. If a user disconnects, the icon changes to red. If a period of time passes and the user is not covered by the network, then it is considered that he/she has left the coverage area. In such a case the Coverage Extension Decision Making algorithm (briefly also described in the following) is triggered which takes into account the scenario input and selects the optimal location for Mobile Access Points and the most appropriate allocation of users/mobile nodes to these Mobile Access Points. In this way all users have now access to the network. The dashboard also enables real space monitoring of the AGV mobile access point navigation to the given coordinates (Figure 77).

The coverage extension algorithm is an optimization algorithm based on/inspired by the classical k-means clustering algorithm which aims to provide coverage to most of the users with minimum number of utilized MAPs and minimum MAP traveling (linked to energy efficiency).

This algorithm is responsible for proposing the best physical locations for MAPs in order to extend the coverage and provide connection to the users in need with the minimum cost. The algorithm initializes a number of centroids whose coordinates denote the possible location of the MAP, and k-means clustering of users is performed. In the case the output

centroids are outside of the AP's transmission range, they are redetermined by their projection inside the range of the nearest AP.

Then, the algorithm checks if all users assigned to each cluster are inside the transmission range of the redetermined centroid/MAP and if not an appropriate number of "chained" centroids/MAPs is added to transmit signal to the user who is further away on each cluster. If still all users are not covered, the described procedure is repeated for increased number of clusters (increase by one each time) till all users are covered.

When a solution is found, the closest MAPs are assigned to the derived centroid's locations that cover the largest possible number of users by checking the capacity constraints, ensuring that the largest possible number of users can be covered (in the case of an insufficient number of available MAPs).

Finally, it defines the closest docking station for each utilized MAP. Additionally, for exploring non-static scenarios, a human trajectory prediction model is used, named Social GAN [44], for predicting the users' locations.

These predictions are provided as input to the coverage extension algorithm. This approach finally offers better solutions since it considers the possible delay of sending a robot-based MAP to a specific location when having moving users.

Figure 74: Overview of coverage extension visualization dashboard

Figure 75: Coverage extension visualization dashboard – 2D representation (indoor setting)

Figure 76: Coverage extension visualization dashboard – 3D representation (indoor setting)

Figure 77: Coverage extension visualization dashboard – Real space monitoring (indoor setting)

Figure 78: Coverage extension visualization dashboard (outdoor setting)

5.1.2.3.2 Coverage extension based on Integrated Access and Backhaul

In this section, we consider a coverage extension performed by a relay with Integrated Access and Backhaul (IAB).

This paragraph describes the IAB platform developed in the framework of DEDICAT 6G project. The overall setup is illustrated in Figure 79.

Figure 79: IAB platform overview

The platform is composed of several modules: an IAB donor which is fixed and is connected to the fiber network, an IAB Node which can be mobile (i.e., Mobile Access Point) and serves as a relay, and at least one User Equipment (UE).

The coverage extension is guaranteed by the multi-RAT technology. It means that the modules are connected via two RAN interfaces, one operating in the conventional sub-6GHz spectrum and the other operating in the mmWave band at 26 GHz. Balancing the traffic over the two bands makes it possible to ensure reliable coverage extension. Indeed, the mmWave spectrum offers enough bandwidth to simultaneously serve a large number of UEs. However, it may suffer from a large latency to access the medium because of beam control and from beam misalignments which may break the link.

To limit the latency needed to obtain a proper beam alignment, it has been assumed that each UE is capable to share with the IAB Donor (i.e. the CPU) its current location via GPS system or alike. The sub-6GHz benefits from its better propagation properties and is therefore more suitable to transmit critical messages (downlink) and control messages (uplink and downlink).

Each of the developed modules consists in a hybrid hardware/software implementation following the split division 7.2 (see Figure 80 below). Indeed, all the functions related to the PHY layer (LDPC en/decoding, de/modulation, framing, etc.) are implemented in hardware and MAC and link layers are implemented in software.

Figure 80: Implementation of the modules developed for the Coverage Extension based on IAB

The block diagrams for each module are given in Figure 81 and can be summarized as follows:

- IAB donor: it includes the orchestrator (or Common Processing Unit), a TX PHY-MAC and an IP tunnel. IAB donor can be considered as a Base Station (BS)
- IAB node: it consists of a RX PHY, a TX PHY and a relay software
- UE: it includes a RX PHY-MAC and an IP tunnel.

Figure 81: Layered architecture for Coverage Extension based on IAB

The *Medium Access Control (MAC)* layer (software) maintains the Tx and Rx coordination and dynamically configures the PHY layer: multi-user multiplexing and precoding, adaptation of the *Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS)*. The PHY layer (hardware) relies on a *Block-Filtered OFDM (BF-OFDM)* implementation, performs the CSI estimation and time/frequency interpolation.

Table 11: PHY parameters for Coverage Extension based on IAB

PHY Parameters	
Bandwidth	Up to 400 MHz (4 100-MHz channels)
Supported constellations	QPSK, 16-QAM, 64-QAM, 256-QAM
Supported MCS	4,5,7,8,11,12,13,14,15,17,18,19,21,23,25
Waveform	BF-OFDM, (K=3 Gaussian filter)

The orchestrator (software- part of the foreground for DEDICAT 6G project) manages the data downlink and forwards downlink packets either to the mmWave when available or to the sidelink. It uses feedback from UEs (received on sidelink). Indeed, on timer period, each UE shares with the IAB donor its location (GPS data), notifies whether it is connected to the mmWave and forwards its Channel State Information (CSI) to the MAC BS. When the UE is not

directly connected to the IAB donor, the GPS location is shared with the IAB node in order to adapt the beam alignment. The corresponding sequence diagram is illustrated in Figure 82.

Figure 82: Simplified orchestrator sequence diagram

5.1.2.3.3 User Safety Application for coverage extension using RSU and connected car

The client application for the Use Case of extending coverage using RSUs and connected cars in a disaster area where the communication infrastructure is damaged has been implemented based on Android, as shown in Figure 83.

Figure 83: User Safety Application

Figure 83(a) is a function that searches for a nearby MAP candidate for connection, and when connected to that MAP, sends a safety (SOS) message including its location information as shown in Figure 83(b). You can then confirm that a message has been sent from the cloud server, as shown in Figure 83(c).

Figure 83(d) shows a server application that is a Local Dynamic Map (LDM) application. When the communication link in the disaster area is restored, the location information transmitted from the client application is displayed in real time on the LDM map, which can help public safety (e.g. rescue) of users in the disaster area.

5.2 Scenario setup

The setup of the Use Case is the same for both contexts described in section 5.1.1. The DEDICAT 6G extended coverage and delivered mission critical services on the premises. Applications and equipment benefited from the connectivity delivered by the platform.

5.2.1 Pilot setup

Figure 84: Location of Pilot Setup for Public Safety UC3

For the Public Safety pilot, two main areas have been prepared to welcome partners and equipment, the Figure 84 illustrates the location of the Public Safety pilot:

- The Airbus eLab room: this area welcomes technology presentation and demonstration to stakeholders; It has been used to prepare and integrate different components of the project (connectivity, robots, mobile devices, etc.), share the organisations of the pilots in the scope of Public Safety Use Case. This area was open to people on Airbus site in order to share and discuss about projects outcomes (this part is described in the lessons learnt section);

- Outdoor area: the outdoor area was used to perform real experimentation for coverage extension based on AGVs (the Jackal robot) and performing MCX call in order to take some measurements.

The Public Safety Use Case took place on Airbus premises and welcome partners during 2 sessions of experimentations and demonstrations.

First UC3 pilot in June 2023

The first pilot trial took place from June 26th to June 28th, 2023 during which Airbus with WINGS performed on site experimentations with the integration of implementations done in WP3, WP4 and WP5. The AGV used *Real-time Kinematic (RTK)* signalisation for centimetre precision location. In France, there are two main providers delivering RTK signals, the one used for the Public Safety pilot was centipede (<https://centiped.fr>).

Table 12: Centipede NRTK provider information

Centipede RTK provider information			
Casting address	Caster.centipede.fr	Port	2101
Mounting pout	CDFX		
Login	centipede	Password	centipede
Data format	RTCM3		

The main issue encountered during the preparation phase of the pilot, was the quality of RTK signals in France. The closest physical mounting point is about 20km off the Airbus premises and the urban density decreases the quality of the signals. Some implementations between WINGS team in Greece and in France were necessary to make the AGV positioning working. The MCX components were deployed as containers in Airbus private infrastructure accessible through an Internet access with a public IP address. The containers were monitored with load balancing mechanisms in order to demonstrate resource distribution in the case of service failure.

- Figure 85 illustrates the preparation of the pilot:

Figure 85: Preparation of the first pilot

- Figure 86 illustrates the execution and the closing of the first pilot during which WINGS and AIRBUS have experimented and demonstrated dynamic coverage extension and measurement of MCX KPIs:

Figure 86: Execution and closing of the first pilot

Demonstration of Coverage Extension and Human Centric Applications at French National Firefighters Congress in October 2023

Firefighters' organisation in France organizes, every year in Autumn, a congress to present novel solution or technology supporting their mission and protecting their safety.

It was the key place (Figure 87) to present and demonstrate DEDICAT 6G outcomes about coverage extension and human centric applications.

Figure 87: DEDICAT 6G at French Firefighters Congress in Toulouse, France

The stakeholders in France have started the deployment of the new Sirius network for Critical Communications for Public Safety. Resiliency is a major issue and they are looking for future/novel solution improving it. End users from Firefighters organization or PPDR have welcomed DEDICAT 6G innovation in coverage extension, demonstrating that intelligent mechanisms for coverage extension bring a promising future to support their operations when responding to a disaster.

Second UC3 pilot in November 2023

The second pilot took place from November 28th to November 29th, 2023 during which AIRBUS welcomed WINGS, CEA and OPTINVENT on site.

For the needs of demonstration of the coverage extension mechanisms based on mmWaves in real aerial conditions, a prior authorization from the French electronic communications regulatory authority, ARCEP was necessary. The request for aerial emission concerned 1 fixed base station for 26,7GHz frequency band and a 100MHz bandwidth. The decision was obtained under the number 2023-2550 on November the 13th, 2023.

- Figure 88 illustrates the demonstration of mmWaves in 26GHz frequency for coverage extension with CEA:

Figure 88: Demonstration of coverage extension based on 26GHz mmWaves with CEA

- Figure 89 illustrates the experimentation and demonstration of AGV positioning and MCX with WINGS and AIRBUS:

Figure 89: AGV positioning and MCX with WINGS and AIRBUS

- Figure 90 illustrates the experimentation and demonstration of Remote Expert application and smart glasses with OPTINVENT and AIRBUS:

Figure 90: Airbus Remote Expert and Smart Glasses with OPTINVENT and AIRBUS

The following section describes the components used for the Public Safety pilot.

Mission Critical Components

The *Mission Critical (MC)* Services have been delivered as Docker containers. The MCX were hosted on Airbus premises on a private cloud accessible through an Internet connection by the DEDICAT 6G platform:

- Container #1: MC-Audio;
- Container #2: MC-Video;
- Container #3: MC-Location;
- Container #4: MC-Registrar;
- Container #5: MC-Management;
- A 6th container was deployed and was used for KPIs measurement.

All mission critical components were deployed and initial tests were executed to check the availability of the services by the MCX mobile clients.

MCX Mobile client and user device:

The MCX mobile application has been implemented to be executed in an Android environment compliant with the Android API level 7 (minimum Android 8.1 Oreo).

The MCX mobile Client offered a parameters page in order to let users change the parameters (MCX Components IP addresses on the DEDICAT 6G platform or on private or other cloud infrastructure).

For evaluation of KPIs, the video parameters had been set as default to the following value:

- Protocol: RSTP;
- Format: 640x480 (SD format);
- Bitrate: 850x1024 (480/3);
- FPS: 25;
- iFrame interval: 2.

For the demonstrations and evaluations, the device which was used was a Samsung XCover Pro 6 5G (since 2022):

Figure 91: Samsung XCover 6 Pro with MC-PTT button

This device offers 2 programmable buttons. The one the left side was used as a MC-PTT button through the MCX mobile applications.

The main characteristics of this device are:

- Ruggedized MIL-STD 810H et IP6;
- 5G Frequencies and Bands:
 - 5G FDD Sub6: N1 (2100 MHz), N3 (1800 MHz), N5 (850 MHz), N7 (2600 MHz), N8 (900 MHz), N20 (800 MHz), N28 (700 MHz);
 - 5G TDD Sub6: N38 (2600 MHz), N40 (2300 MHz), N41 (2500 MHz), N78 (3500 MHz).

For the experimentation and demonstration, 5 devices were used.

AGV

Figure 92: Clearpath Robotics Jackal Unmanned Ground Vehicle

In the scope of this use case pilot, a Clearpath Robotics Jackal Unmanned Ground Vehicle/AGV (Figure 92) was used as a MAP to reach a specific location with the aim of providing users with opportunistic wireless network for coverage extension.

Figure 93: Devices added to Jackal robot for outdoor navigation and positioning (a) MicroStrain AHRS GX-5; (b) RealSense 455 I depth camera; (c) Fixposition RTK-2; (d) Ouster OS-1 3D lidar

Jackal is a small, fast, entry-level field robotics research platform. It has an onboard computer, GPS, 3D lidar, camera and *Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU)* fully integrated with ROS. Jackal's chassis is made entirely from welded aluminium and provides IP65 protection. The high torque 4x4 drive train gives Jackal maximum traction, with enough on-board power available to traverse obstacles or unconsolidated terrain.

In addition, the Jackal was equipped with the following devices (Figure 93):

- MicroStrain AHRS GX-5 for Orientation Sensing. Such devices are used in various applications across industries due to their ability to provide accurate and real-time information about the orientation and motion of objects;
- A Realsense 455 I depth camera is used due to several advantages it offers in the context of visual *Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM)* applications. In our case we use RTAB-Map (where RTK's performance drops). RTAB-Map is an open-source RGB-D SLAM approach that can build a 3D map of an environment while simultaneously estimating the camera's pose within that environment;
- Fixposition RTK-2. Real-Time Kinematic is a satellite navigation technique used for accurate positioning (x-y) in outdoor environments. Reasons why RTK is commonly used for outdoor localization are: high accuracy, fast convergence, real time positioning and good behavior in challenging environments (including areas with obstructions such as trees, buildings, and urban canyons);

Ouster OS-1 3D lidar for Obstacle Detection and Avoidance, Mapping and Localization in Challenging Terrain. 3D LiDAR is well-suited for dynamic outdoor environments where the surroundings are changing rapidly. This is particularly important in applications like autonomous navigation, where real-time updates on the environment's structure are crucial for safe and efficient movement.

Figure 94: High-level view of Public Safety use case implementation with Clearpath Jackal being used as a MAP

Figure 94 depicts a high-level view of the Public Safety Use Case implementation comprising the Clearpath Jackal AGV as a MAP. The AGV has a ROS1/2 Bridge and containerized Docker microservices running on it. It communicates via the DEDICAT 6G controller via Fast DDS Discovery²⁶ (Figure 95, see also section 3.2.2) with the coverage extension visualisation dashboard for sending AGVs statuses, positionings/movements and camera feeds. The coverage extension visualisation dashboard provides 2D and 3D visualization of the area, monitors crowd – users and AGVs' positions, progress tracking and provides various notifications. Users' position is also sent via the DEDICAT 6G controller to the coverage extension visualisation dashboard. Hence, the DEDICAT 6G controller communicates with the AGV, the visualisation dashboard, user devices and the implemented Coverage extension algorithm and is responsible for distributing the information related to the position of robots and users to the coverage extension visualisation dashboard and the implemented coverage extension algorithm.

Similar to the implementation of the Smart Warehousing (see Section 3.2.2), the DEDICAT 6G controller is hosted in the cloud together with other auxiliary entities including an orchestrator based on open source ETSI MANO²⁷, the Kubernetes platform, the implementation of the coverage extension mechanism from WP4 (specifically the mechanism managing robot-based MAPs described in section 4.5 of D4.2 [8]) and an implementation of the Threat identification and classification mechanism from WP5 (described in detail in Section 6.1 of D5.2 [10]). The coverage extension algorithm is responsible for deciding on the optimal placement of the MAPs to the available locations of the area of interest, aiming to provide coverage to all users with minimum number of utilized MAPs and minimum MAP traveling (this is also linked to energy efficiency). The implemented coverage extension algorithm communicates with the DEDICAT 6G controller for collecting and providing the input and output of MAPs, and users positions. Finally, as already mentioned previously (in Section 3.2.2) the implemented Security Mechanisms are responsible for threat identification and classification and monitors network traffic over the public safety infrastructure. In the case of a possible detected threat/cyber-attack, it alerts DEDICAT 6G controller (the component that facilitates communication of the AGVs/robots with the user interfaces and the rest of the components) resulting in a relevant notification appearing on the Unity based coverage extension dashboard.

²⁶ <https://fast-dds.docs.eprosima.com/en/v2.1.0/02-formalia/titlepage.html>

²⁷ <https://osm.etsi.org/>

Figure 95: Coverage extension FAST API

Figure 96 depicts a network topology for the Public Safety Use Case implementation. The edge node in this topology hosts the Coverage Extension algorithm, as well as auxiliary services for the monitoring of the robot and the collection of the KPIs. As can be seen the Mobile Access Point on top of the robot offers 5G connectivity leveraging the commercial 5G network, as does the "fixed" Access Point. The Mobile Access Point is a DWR-2101 5G Wi-Fi 6 Mobile Hotspot²⁸. Its connectivity can be shared with up to 32 devices. The other Access Point is a Mobile Router Huawei CPE Pro 2 H122-373²⁹.

As can be further observed in the figure Zero Tier VPN is used. This was done primarily to address issues with ROS 2 auto-discovery to work is primarily influenced by the network architecture and security considerations. More specifically, ROS 2 uses DDS (Data Distribution Service) as its middleware, and DDS typically relies on multicast communication for auto-discovery of nodes and topics. However, multicast traffic is often restricted or not supported in certain types of networks, including many cellular networks. Multicast messages sent by ROS 2 for auto-discovery might not be propagated across the cellular network without proper support or configuration.

Virtual Private Networks (VPNs) can be configured to allow multicast traffic to flow across the network. By establishing a VPN connection, to create a secure and private network overlay on top of the existing infrastructure, multicast communication and, consequently, ROS 2 auto-discovery can work seamlessly. In addition, using a VPN can enhance the security of communication between ROS 2 nodes by creating a private and encrypted channel. VPNs add a layer of encryption, protecting the auto-discovery and other communication traffic from potential eavesdropping or tampering. Moreover, in some cases, robots may be behind NAT devices in the cellular network, which can complicate multicast communication. A VPN can help overcome NAT-related challenges and facilitate communication between nodes.

²⁸ <https://eu.dlink.com/uk/en/products/dwr-2101-5g-wifi-6-mobile-hotspot>

²⁹ <https://consumer.huawei.com/en/routers/5g-cpe-pro-2/>

Finally, a VPN can ensure a consistent and predictable network configuration across different robots and locations. This can be important for ROS 2 auto-discovery, as nodes rely on the ability to discover each other dynamically.

Figure 96: Network topology of Public Safety use case implementation

Architecture and integration of UC3 pilot execution

The following Figure 97 illustrates the integration of the DEDICAT 6G components use for the execution of the Public Safety Use Case pilot at the AIRBUS premises.

Figure 97: Integration of Coverage Extension in Public Safety Use Case

Coverage extension using RSU and Connected Car on disaster area

For a public safety demonstration that expanded coverage using RSU and connected car in a disaster area where communication infrastructure was damaged, the RSU and vehicle were each equipped with USRP N321 as shown in Figure 98(a) and (b), respectively. This demonstration was conducted at the TU Chemnitz campus, and the area marked in red in Figure 98(c) was set as a disaster area where existing communication was not possible. The orange square is the location where the RSU is installed, and it is assumed that the communication coverage area did not include the disaster area (red). To expand communication coverage, the connected car (BMW i3) equipped with the MAP function (Figure 98 (b)) was deployed near the disaster area, as shown in Figure 98 (d). It should be noted that this part of extending MAP coverage using RSUs and connected cars is largely similar to work done also done in the scope of UC4. Here the concept is applied to public safety (disaster area).

Figure 98: Testing of Public Safety at TU Chemnitz campus

As communication coverage expanded to the disaster area through the connected car's MAP, a proof of concept that transmitted public safety signals from the disaster area to the cloud server was tested as shown in Figure 99.

Figure 99: Transmission of public safety signals through a connected car

On the left side of Figure 99, the user runs the 'User Safety Application' in Figure 83 to find the MAP of nearby connected cars and transmits a public safety signal with location information to the cloud server. The signals are transmitted to the cloud server via the connected car and RSU, and the location information is displayed in the LDM application running on the cloud server, as shown on the right side of Figure 99.

5.2.2 Public Safety Use Case implementation

5.2.2.1 DEDICAT 6G architecture components

The detailed functional decomposition of the interconnection of this Use Case into DEDICAT 6G architecture and platform is described in D2.3, D6.1 and D6.2. Table 13 provides a mapping of the functionality of the DEDICAT 6G architecture FCs to the current Public Safety implementation of Figure 94.

Table 13: Mapping of DEDICAT 6G architecture FCs to Public Safety implementation (Figure 94)

DEDICAT 6G architecture FC	Description	Public Safety implementation (Figure 94)
μS/FC Repository FC	Stores the uploaded micro-services such as video streaming platform	Kubernetes
EN Status Agent FC	Provides monitored information about the current status of the edge nodes registered to the DEDICAT 6G platform	Kubernetes, Coverage extension visualization dashboard, ROS1/2 Bridge, DEDICAT 6G Controller
μS/FC Status Agent FC	Provides monitored information about the current status of the microservices being executed in the use case infrastructure	MANO, Kubernetes, ROS1/2 Bridge, DEDICAT 6G Controller
Service Orchestrator FC	Orchestrate the microservices and FCs deployed over the Public Safety depending on information collected with Status Agent FC.	MANO

NW Awareness FC	Provides information on the status of the network of the Public Safety infrastructure	DEDICAT 6G Controller
Load Balancing FC	Load balancing and service orchestration functionalities for deploying and balancing Mission Critical services in the suitable edge	MANO, Kubernetes
EN Awareness FC	Status agents for reporting periodically the state of the services in edge nodes and network	MANO, Kubernetes
μ S/FC Awareness FC	Receives information from a group of μ S Status Agent FC and publishes it to the rest of the FCs available on the DEDICAT 6G platform after enriching it to the DM expectations.	MANO, Kubernetes
CEDM FC	Instructs physical deployment of MAPs	Coverage Extension Algorithm
AGV Operation FC	Provides the basic management of robots and provides a basic palette of so-called atomic actions it can perform. Those atomic actions are then played with, in order to build more complex capabilities (e.g., for identifying parcels and moving them from A to B with obstacle avoidance or performing quality checks).	ROS1/2 Bridge, DEDICAT 6G Controller, containerized micro-services (docker/ROS)
MAP operation FC	Responsible for implementing the decision taken by the CEDM	ROS1/2 Bridge, DEDICAT 6G Controller, containerized micro-services (docker/ROS)
Threat Analysis FC	Performs threat detection, identification and classification and is executed either in centralized or in edge processing nodes. Threat analysis is based on ML models trained and updated on collected system logs.	Security Mechanism Algorithm

5.2.2.2 UC specific components

In order to use MCX features delivered by DEDICAT 6G platform, a Human-Centric application was implemented, and smartphones delivered to install the MCX Client application.

The MCX Client application was available for setup on applications stores or as an installation file as "APK" for local installation.

A video device was used to stream video from the field to Control Room and users on the field. A specific connector was implemented to connect the camera device to MCX services.

5.2.2.3 Interfaces

A view of the interfaces is provided in the UML diagrams for this Use Case in D2.3 [2]. An overview of the key interfaces between components that have been implemented so far in the scope of this use case pilot are listed (see also Table 13):

- The EN Status Agent FC, μ S/FC Status Agent FC and NW Status Agent FC interface with the EN Awareness FC, μ S/FC Awareness FC and NW Awareness FC respectively;
- The EN Awareness FC, μ S/FC Awareness FC and NW Awareness FC in turn provide input relating to the EN, μ S/FC and NW as contexts to the CEDM FC;
- The EN Registry FC, μ S/FC Registry FC, μ S/FC Repository FC and EC Policy Repository FC also interface with the CEDM FC;
- The CEDM FC has an interface with the Service Orchestrator FC;
- The Service Orchestrator FC has an interface with Load Balancing FC;
- The CEDM FC has an interface with the MAP operation FC.

In addition, the interfaces offer third application the capability to use Mission Critical services. The MCX Client used this interface to deliver MC-PTT, MC-Video and MC-Data features.

MCX features were available through an "APK" application for integration with other components (e.g., Smart Glasses).

MCX UAV Connector: connection of drone camera in order to enable video streaming through MCX and to MCX Client app.

Figure 100: Connectivity Client applications with MCX services

5.2.3 Final integration report

The paragraph below describes the use of WPs outcomes in the UC3 and the contribution per partner done during the period M15 to M36.

5.2.3.1 Description of WPs related outcomes in UC3

Mechanisms for Dynamic Distribution of Intelligence (WP3):

Outcomes of WP3 are used in both contexts defined in UC3 “Public Safety” in order to support connectivity to resources, especially the mission critical components for communications between First Responders or PPDR users as described in Section 2.2.1.

Mechanisms for Dynamic Coverage Extension (WP4):

Outcomes of WP4 are used mainly in the Context #1 “Loss of connectivity in a non-urban environment” in order to showcase how DEDICAT 6G could establish a connectivity for PPDR users immediately after a natural disaster as described in Section 2.2.2.

Mechanisms for Security, Privacy and Trust (WP5):

WP5 provides security and trust features to the Use Case. WP5 also provides access control on both producer and consumer sides as describe in Section 2.2.3.

5.2.3.2 Description of contribution per partner in UC3

WINGS: Implementation of a coverage extension decision making algorithm from WP4 (specifically the mechanism managing robot based MAPs described in Section 4.5 of D4.2 [8]) and 5.1 of D4.3 [9] and an implementation of the Threat identification and classification mechanism from WP5 (described in detail in Section 6.1 of D5.2 [10] and Section 7.1 of D5.3 [11]). Implementation of robot based Mobile Access Point as described in Section 5.2.1 of the current document. Implementation of coverage extension visualisation dashboard as described in Section 5.1 of the current document.

UoS: Contributed to the mechanism how to associate UEs requiring different QoS to multiple UEs and allocate powers considering the backhaul capacity and power constraints in a network including MAPs with multiple UEs distributed.

CEA: Based on a background demonstration platform with bidirectional, dual RAT capabilities, CEA has provided a demonstrator for coverage extension assuming Integrated Access and Backhaul with a moving IAB node. This includes Access and backhaul links management, Multi-Rat access (mm-wave and sub-6GHz bands) and multi-beam management.

AIRBUS: Implementation of a mobile client application which can connect to the different Mission Critical Services and, with several mobile applications connected, are able to join a multimedia group communication to make voice group call (MC-PTT), video group call (MC-VIDEO) or sharing operational statuses (MC-DATA). AIRBUS also evaluate novel features which could be supported by the DEDICAT 6G platform as drone or robot video streaming to a video group call (MC-VIDEO) and integration to other kind of rich features. Based on existing clouded server architecture, AIRBUS has split and implemented specific architecture in order to deliver FCs and services to be deployed at the Edge/Far Edge or in the Cloud when necessary.

VLF: Implementation of private permissioned blockchain and collection of smart contracts for security and trust management framework, described in D5.2

OPTIN: Provided ORA-2 smart glasses with “Remote Eye” application. This application shows how a remote expert connected to an operator wearing the ORA-2 smart glasses could

exchange in real time information such as pictures, augmented information, video, audio, map, and datasheet. Collaboration with AIRBUS on the Integration of a MCX application into ORA-2 smart-glasses.

TUC: Implementation of a User Safety application that searches for nearby connectable MAPs and transmits its location information based on RSUs and connected cars. Implementation of a local dynamic map application that monitors MAP status and displays location information of safety messages transmitted by the user safety application on a map.

ATOS: Integration of Service orchestrator to manage the deployments of μ Services required for intelligence distribution and coverage extension. Furthermore, the orchestration engine was adapted to provide the functionalities of the NFV-O connector FC, which served as interface between the Service Orchestrator and the NFV-O to instantiate the required network slices.

NOKIA: NOKIA has contributed to UC3 through the work achieved in WP5 in order to provide security, trust and privacy to the DEDICAT 6G platform for the Public Safety Use Case.

5.2.3.3 Description of external assets used in UC3

WINGS: Know-how and experience accumulated from the participation in projects such as OneFit³⁰ Clear5G³¹, One5G³², 5G-EVE³³, and 5G-TOURS³⁴ has been utilised for the implementation of the UC3 prototype and the testing performed so far. The development and implementation of all software and hardware components for UC3 have been done specifically in the context of DEDICAT 6G, with no re-use of specific assets.

AIRBUS: From the MCX solution used in 5G!DRONES³⁵ project, AIRBUS has split the architecture of in use MCX in order to make the new architecture addressing the requirements of DEDICAT 6G. To measure some of the KPIs and make evaluation, AIRBUS has connected the MCX for DEDICAT 6G project to the 5G-EPICENTRE³⁶ platform.

Optinvent has participated in the recent H2020 project called Monica (<https://www.monica-project.eu/>). There are some similarities between DEDICAT 6G UC3 and some features demonstrated by Monica project, especially those related to security management in events such as Fan zone. For Monica project, Optinvent developed an application on ORA-2 (called Monicora) that can help security staff or policemen to manage security issues such as lost children, people misconduct in events such as concert, Rugby match, etc. The application can track on a security map staff position, policemen direction of vision. It allows also to take pictures, videos and send them to a security center managing the event. The main difference between the two projects is the software platform and cover extension highly improved with DEDICAT 6G.

³⁰ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/257385>

³¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/761745>

³² <https://one5g.eu/>

³³ <https://www.5g-eve.eu/>

³⁴ <https://5gtours.eu/>

³⁵ <https://5gdrones.eu>

³⁶ <https://5gepicentre.eu>

CEA: The antenna system (i.e., programmable transmit array) has been designed, manufactured and tested during previous projects such as Carnot-5GmmFLASH and ANR-Mesanges³⁷. It has been used for the DEDICAT 6G radio-platform as a background. In a similar way, the RF and analogic components enabling transmission at 26GHz come from previous subsidies. The VHDL implementation of the physical layer has been developed first during the EU 5G-ALLSTAR³⁸ project. The existing implementation has been used as background for DEDICAT 6G and has been upgraded to support relay transmissions via the IAB node with compatible pilot sequences. The orchestration and routing protocols have been developed during DEDICAT 6G and are foreground of the latter.

5.3 Evaluation and final results

An implementation of a Public Safety prototype focused on coverage extension is available including the Jackal robot, the coverage extension visualisation dashboard, the implementation of a coverage extension decision making algorithm from WP4 and threat detection and identification as outlined in Section 5.1.2.3. Corresponding videos have been produced (<https://youtu.be/-QBJJTW0D8Q>). This setup has been tested at WINGS premises (Figure 77), at various outdoor premises in Athens and at AIRBUS premises. It was also demonstrated at events such as the EUCNC & 6G Summit in June 2023.

³⁷https://anr.fr/en/funded-projects-and-impact/funded-projects/project/funded/project/b2d9d3668f92a3b9fbbf7866072501ef-7c8dba08eb/?tx_anrprojects_funded%5Bcontroller%5D=Funded&cHash=c9501b43d4410f23accb84dc425ceeb5

³⁸ <https://5g-allstar.eu/>

Figure 101: Testing of Public Safety use case at AIRBUS premises

5.3.1 List of KPIs, target values and gain

5.3.1.1 KPIs and target values

Table 14 presents the list of KPIs related to the Public Safety Use Case, describing the evaluation method and defining the target values:

Table 14: UC3 – Public Safety KPIs list

KPI ID	Description	Target value	Baseline
UC3_KPI1	MC-PTT (voice) to MCX Audio service access time	Access time < 300ms 95% of request	<p>The baseline values are based on the 3GPP MCS standards (ETSI Technical Specification 122,179 (2020)). The DEDICAT 6G project brings a new architecture for mission critical services and aims to not decrease the performances established by the standard.</p> <p>The final evaluation which will be done during the third year of the project will allow to compare and determine the gain regarding the standard.</p>
UC3_KPI2	End-to-End MC-PTT (voice) access time for all MCX client under the same network coverage	Access time < 1000ms	
UC3_KPI3	Mouse-to-Ear (voice) latency	Access time < 300ms 95% of voice burst	
UC3_KPI4	Maximum late call entry time	Late entry time < 150ms 95% of late call request	
UC3_KPI5	End-to-End MC-DATA (IP Data) and MC-VIDEO (video) request time for IP packets transmission	Transmission request time < 10ms	
UC3_KPI6	User Data Rate	DL user data rate shall be 100Mbps UL user data rate shall be 50Mbps	
UC3_KPI7	Successful packet transmission (Reliability)	Reliability indicator at least 99,999% of success for a 32 bytes IP Packet within 1ms	
UC3_KPI8	E2E Service Latency (similar as in UC1)	10-100ms	
UC3_KPI9	Network energy efficiency and device energy efficiency	Reduction by a factor of 10	
			<p>The target values range from 10ms (augmented reality in human-machine interfaces) to 100ms having as a baseline the "Service requirements for the 5G system", (3GPP TS 22.261, Latency needs to support example use cases from vertical industries).</p>
			<p>Reduction of energy consumption by a factor of 10 (considering that intelligence distribution can contribute to increasing efficiency of Sleep Mode) [26][27]</p>

5.3.1.2 Final evaluation and results

Table 15 presents the list of KPIs related to the Public Safety use case, the results from measurement and the gain:

Table 15: UC3 – Results obtained and gain

KPI ID	Evaluation method	Results	Gain
UC3_KPI1	<p>A specific component has been developed to measure the KPIs related to the MCX solution.</p> <p>The component was deployed as a container on the same infrastructure than the MCX components.</p>	<p>Figure 107, Figure 108</p> <p>Table 16</p>	<p>The measurements done during the pilot demonstrate that there is no negative impact on access time or latency compared to the figures on the 3GPP MCS standards (ETSI Technical Specification 122,179 (2020)).</p>
UC3_KPI2			
UC3_KPI3			
UC3_KPI4			
UC3_KPI5			
UC3_KPI6	<p>User data rate measured on the IAB platform. Measurements have been collected with over-the-air transmissions at 26 GHz. The generation of IP packets is ensured by network management packages such as ping and iperf.</p>	<p>Figure 109</p>	<p>For UL transmissions, the platform fully supports the required 50 Mbits/s/user.</p> <p>However, when relaying is involved, the radio platform does not successfully support rates higher than 60 Mbits/s/user. Therefore, it does not meet the required KPIs for DL transmissions with relays. We provide at the end of Section 5.3.1.2.2 comments and perspectives to overcome the limitation.</p>
UC3_KPI7	<p>Measurements are collected at UE level.</p>	<p>Figure 108</p> <p>Figure 109</p>	<p>What we can see, in case of loss of service, the system is able to reach the baseline in term of reliability.</p>
UC3_KPI8	<p>Measurements are collected at the application layer by adding timestamps to requests between functional entities/service components of an overall service. Then the difference in time is calculated between the request from one entity (e.g., client) and the response from the other entity (e.g., server). Measurements</p>	<p>Figure 33-Figure 40</p> <p>Figure 102</p> <p>Figure 109</p> <p>Figure 110</p>	<p>From the various measurements latency is close to the target and baseline values.</p> <p>For the IAB platform, the KPI target is satisfied: less than 10ms</p>

KPI ID	Evaluation method	Results	Gain
	are also collected e.g., with the use of ping and iPerf.		
UC3_KPI9	The battery level of involved mobile nodes (e.g., phones, laptops, robots) is measured with and without the use of intelligence distribution mechanisms for certain services/applications. The power consumption of involved servers may also be measured or at least estimated using various ways ranging from cheap watt hour meters for on premises servers.	Figure 41	5-10%

5.3.1.2.1 Robot-based MAP coverage extension

As mentioned previously in this document results presented in Section 3.3 and Figure 33- Figure 43 under UC1, essentially are also applicable to the UC3 Public Safety part based on a similar implementation architecture (Figure 18 and Figure 94). Additional measurements for UC3_KPI8 are shown in Figure 102, where latency is at an average of 80ms.

Figure 102: Latency for Public Safety implementation with Coverage extension and robot-based MAP

In addition, measurements were derived on the time required from the triggering of the coverage extension algorithm up to the returning of the result from the corresponding decision-making process to the coverage extension visualisation dashboard and the Jackal robot as the MAP. The average time for this coverage extension process is currently measured at an average of 16 seconds. Details on the coverage extension algorithm implementation can be found in D4.2 and D4.3.

Regarding service reliability packet, Error Rate is measured continuously by sending test packets from a test sender to a test receiver, and back. No loss of packets was recorded and therefore service reliability is measured at 100%.

5.3.1.2.2 Mission Critical evaluation

Regarding the Mission Critical Services, the first evaluation has shown that the split architecture and potential deployment at the Edge have limited impact on the KPIs as defined in the 3GPP MCS standards, the values measured shown an increase latency for MC-VIDEO comparing to state-of-the-art technology based on Public 4G/5G operated networks.

The following paragraphs describe the evaluation of such novel split architecture in Mission Critical Services.

The 5G network used for the preliminary evaluation was the Orange public operated infrastructure without prioritization for mission critical applications.

All the MCX components are available as containers in a Kubernetes environment which has been chosen for the evaluation. The evaluation has been executed related to the first context of the Public Safety use case, context #1 "Loss of connectivity in a non-urban area after a natural disaster". A specific K8s context has been defined in order to support this Public Safety context with the automatic redeployment of a MCX component to support the MCX feature in use.

For the evaluation, two smartphone user devices have been used with a specific human-centric application implemented and deployed on them.

First step, after the initialization of the context, a script deployed all MCX components as shown in the Figure 103 below.


```

delmass@delmass-HP-ZBook-15-G2: ~/Kubernetes/M6/scripts
delmass@delmass-HP-ZBook-15-G2:~/Kubernetes/M6/scripts$ ./uc101connection.sh
Cluster "m6cluster" set.
User "ads-developer" set.
Context "m6context" modified.
Switched to context "m6context".
delmass@delmass-HP-ZBook-15-G2:~/Kubernetes/M6/scripts$ ./uc102deletedeployment.sh
deployment.apps "audiomedia" deleted
deployment.apps "audiosignalisation" deleted
deployment.apps "kpi" deleted
deployment.apps "registrar" deleted
deployment.apps "situation" deleted
deployment.apps "videomedia" deleted
deployment.apps "videosignalisation" deleted
deployment.apps "webapp" deleted
delmass@delmass-HP-ZBook-15-G2:~/Kubernetes/M6/scripts$ ./uc103startdeployment.sh
deployment.apps/audiomedia created
deployment.apps/audiosignalisation created
deployment.apps/kpi created
deployment.apps/registrar created
deployment.apps/situation created
deployment.apps/videomedia created
deployment.apps/videosignalisation created
deployment.apps/webapp created
delmass@delmass-HP-ZBook-15-G2:~/Kubernetes/M6/scripts$

```

Figure 103: DEDICAT 6G - Mission critical components deployment

On two user devices, the human centric application implemented to use MCX services is launched (Figure 104), and one device has started to stream the video from the user device camera to the other device which is able to display the video. The MC-VIDEO feature is supported by the MCX Videomedia component.

Figure 104: Mobile Client applications on user devices with the video stream up

The next step of the evaluation was to simulate the loss of the MC-VIDEO service. To do so, we have launched a script to kill the videomedia component (Figure 105).

Figure 105: Simulation of loss of MC-Video service

The behaviour which has been noticed was the loss of the video stream on the second device (the right one on both pictures presented in Figure 106) before it reappears a few moments after.

Figure 106: Mobile client (on right) loses video stream and a few instants later, the video stream is up

The system reacts as expected in the split environment. After the detection of the loss of one component which was in use. The orchestrator has created a new instance of the component and mobile devices have continued to deliver the information between them.

The data was collected and sent to an analyser component in order to measure the video latency.

Figure 107 and Table 16 illustrate the measurement of KPIs.

```

delmass@delmass-HP-ZBook-15-G2: ~/Kubernetes/M6/scripts
.FileLock
WARNING: Use --illegal-access=warn to enable warnings of further illegal reflective access operations
WARNING: All illegal access operations will be denied in a future release
OK1
OK3
OK4
Receive message -> [{"category": "experiment", "experiment_id": "01", "netapp_id": "remote_iperf_agent", "testbed_id": "1", "data": [{"timestamp": 1656457287.432912, "type": "Packet Loss", "value": 0, "unit": "%", "origin": "UE"}, {"timestamp": 1656457287.432912, "type": "Packet Loss", "value": 0, "unit": "%", "origin": "UE"}]}]
Receive message -> [{"category": "Experiment", "data": [{"type": "m6_video_latency", "value": 25, "origin": "UE", "unit": "ms", "timestamp": 1656498094331, "longitude": -4.49981645, "latitude": 36.71677381, "altitude": 87.33721923828125, "asu_level": 72, "level": 4, "csi_rsrq": 2147483647, "csi_rsrp": 2147483647, "dbm": -68, "csi_snr": 2147483647, "radio_type": "nr", "bitrate": 870400, "fps": 25, "iframe_interval": 2, "video_protocol": "mcs", "viewers": 0, "width": 640, "height": 480}, {"type": "m6_video_throughput", "value": 128062, "origin": "UE", "unit": "bps", "timestamp": 1656498094331, "longitude": -4.49981645, "latitude": 36.71677381, "altitude": 87.33721923828125, "asu_level": 72, "level": 4, "csi_rsrq": 2147483647, "csi_rsrp": 2147483647, "dbm": -68, "csi_snr": 2147483647, "radio_type": "nr", "bitrate": 870400, "fps": 25, "iframe_interval": 2, "video_protocol": "mcs", "viewers": 0, "width": 640, "height": 480}, {"type": "m6_video_max_throughput", "value": 321610, "origin": "UE", "unit": "bps", "timestamp": 1656498094331, "longitude": -4.49981645, "latitude": 36.71677381, "altitude": 87.33721923828125, "asu_level": 72, "level": 4, "csi_rsrq": 2147483647, "csi_rsrp": 2147483647, "dbm": -68, "csi_snr": 2147483647, "radio_type": "nr", "bitrate": 870400, "fps": 25, "iframe_interval": 2, "video_protocol": "mcs", "viewers": 0, "width": 640, "height": 480}], "Server_IP": "150.214.47.150", "NetApp_ID": "M6"}]

```

Figure 107: KPI evaluation for the recovery time of video media component supporting MC-VIDEO.

Table 16: UC3 – Measurements of MC-PTT and MC-VIDEO End-to-End access time

Measurement of MC-PTT and MC-VIDEO done during the second pilot

<pre> {id": "c65f802e-a73c-49ee-9ecc-d66e9948f23d", "position": { "longitude": "1.9708383333333333", "latitude": "48.79826333333334", "altitude": "258.5" }, "latency": 26, "timestamp": 1687784461759, "throughput": 706462, "max_throughput": 2058252, "type": "VIDEO", "radio_data": { "asu_level": 37, "rsii": -93, "level": 2, "rsrq": -11, "rsrp": -103, "rssi": 0, "ca": 2147483647, "ta": 0, "dbm": -103, "radio_type": "lte" }, "video_data": { "width": 640, "height": 480, "fps": 25, "bitrate": 870400, "viewers": 1, "video_protocol": "mcs", "iframe_interval": 2 } } </pre>	<pre> {id": "9add8f21-4be8-4ff0-8f10-765fc3355b22", "latency": 21, "timestamp": 1687784606311, "throughput": 1291263, "max_throughput": 1788191, "type": "VIDEO", "radio_data": { "asu_level": 96, "level": 4, "dbm": -24, "EcNo": 0, "radio_type": "wcdma" }, "video_data": { "width": 1280, "height": 720, "fps": 15, "bitrate": 1228800, "viewers": 1, "video_protocol": "mcs", "iframe_interval": 2 } } </pre>	<pre> {id": "1d774eef-d789-4ab5-b5a1-8ceee7ed01f6", "position": { "longitude": "1.97056264", "latitude": "48.79810481", "altitude": "244.35845947265625" }, "latency": 19, "timestamp": 1687787230924, "throughput": 1573730, "max_throughput": 7727449, "type": "VIDEO", "radio_data": { "asu_level": 96, "level": 4, "dbm": -24, "EcNo": 0, "radio_type": "wcdma" }, "video_data": { "width": 1280, "height": 720, "fps": 15, "bitrate": 1228800, "viewers": 0, "video_protocol": "mcs", "iframe_interval": 2 } } </pre>	<pre> {id": "be22a50e-cb4c-4b34-ba3b-6e7d4a0c92ac", "position": { "longitude": "1.97061648", "latitude": "48.79809016", "altitude": "261.623779296875" }, "latency": 4, "timestamp": 1687789386682, "throughput": 941455, "max_throughput": 2179254, "type": "VIDEO", "radio_data": { "asu_level": 96, "level": 3, "dbm": -24, "EcNo": 0, "radio_type": "wcdma" }, "video_data": { "width": 1280, "height": 720, "fps": 15, "bitrate": 1228800, "viewers": 2, "video_protocol": "mcs", "iframe_interval": 2 } } </pre>
<pre> {id": "e33d43a3-22d2-44bd-8fc7-7cee28f44ee1", "position": { "longitude": "1.9703134", "latitude": "48.7981549", "altitude": "215.89999389648438" }, "latency": 22, "timestamp": 1687784472671, "throughput": 29944, "max_throughput": 0, "type": "AUDIO", "radio_data": { "asu_level": 96, "level": 4, "dbm": -24, "EcNo": 0, "radio_type": "wcdma" } } </pre>	<pre> {id": "728353c9-0255-4d6a-99f6-d8808027e7ce", "latency": 40, "timestamp": 1687784620753, "throughput": 29201, "max_throughput": 0, "type": "AUDIO", "radio_data": { "asu_level": 96, "level": 4, "dbm": -24, "EcNo": 0, "radio_type": "wcdma" } } </pre>	<pre> {id": "c751c870-d160-4129-8078-d880802618a7", "position": { "longitude": "1.97061639", "latitude": "48.79808515", "altitude": "238.70928955078125" }, "latency": 20, "timestamp": 1687788890428, "throughput": 29637, "max_throughput": 0, "type": "AUDIO", "radio_data": { "asu_level": 96, "level": 4, "dbm": -24, "EcNo": 0, "radio_type": "wcdma" } } </pre>	

Figure 108: Video latency measured in 5G and results comparison with 4G.

The video latency (Figure 108) was measured several times to have an average of the latency. In 5G network the video latency value measured was between 5ms and 25ms.

Some measures were performed on 4G in order to have some comparison with 5G as shown on Figure 108, all the video latency were more than 30ms.

5.3.1.2.3 IAB platform coverage extension evaluation

The KPIs of interest to evaluate are rather PHY-related such as data rate and transmission latency. Figure 109 depicts the measured rates (for a 128 MHz bandwidth) and latency for direct IAB-Donor to UE link for two MCS: MCS 4 with QPSK symbols and MCS 15 with 64-QAM symbols. It proves that the 26GHz platform supports at least 120Mbits/s with an end-to-end latency around 3.5ms. Those KPIs meet the requirements for the physical layer.

Figure 109: Evaluation of user data rates and end-to-end latencies for MCS 4 (left) and MCS 15 (right)

Now, we can consider the scenario where the message is relayed by the IAB node. Figure 110 shows the latency comparison between the direct link case (in red) and relayed scenario (in blue).

Figure 110: Comparison of end-to-end latencies between direct link (red) and relays by IAB node (blue)

As expected, the experienced latency with relay is higher, up to 8ms in average. This result is promising as we are below the 10ms target. However, one can observe that maximum latency increases up to 30ms. First, those peaks do no longer meet the KPIs requirements (10ms max) but also limit the data rate to 60Mbits/user. Indeed, beyond 40Mbits/s/user, the latency instability may overload the memory blocks and lead to random packet drops. Beyond 60Mbits/s/user, the occurrences are frequent enough to lose most of the received packets at the IAB node side.

Those latency peaks are due to the frequent memory accesses between the FPGA and ARM units. This issue is caused by the capacity of the data buses integrated in the Xilinx Zynq boards that we use. It can be fixed by implementing more PHY-related features in hardware/FPGA (and in particular the packet filtering and forwarding between RX and TX RUs). However, our hardware design for the demodulator (RX) already fully occupies the FPGA resources and therefore it is not straightforward to add more features. We need to investigate designs with inter-board communications which greatly complexifies the design.

Figure 111: IAB and multi-RAT demonstration for coverage extension

The platform has been presented to the UC3 partners during the final pilot demonstration organized by Airbus-Paris in November 2023.

As a conclusion, the proposed platform validates Integrated Access and Backhaul and Multi-RAT technologies to be used for coverage extension. The radio platform demonstrates interesting results and reaches a TRL of 5. Nonetheless, further developments to make it a ready-to-market product are estimated to be about 5 years.

5.3.1.2.4 Coverage extension using RSU and connected car evaluation

Regarding the demonstration and testing at the TU Chemnitz campus (Figure 98, Figure 99), the latency of packets (< 40bytes) sent from the user safety application to the LDM was measured (UC3_KPI8).

Figure 112: Latency for Public Safety implementation from the user safety application and LDM

Figure 112(a) is the latency when the user is located close to the MAP of the vehicle as shown in Figure 99(a), and the latency when the user is located far away as shown in Figure 99(b) is shown in Figure 112(b). The average values of latency measured at the two locations are 18.37ms and 19.48ms, respectively.

6 UC4: SMART HIGHWAY

6.1 Scenario and stories

Smart Highway Use Case is executed in the context of smart mobility. The goal of this Use Case is to research and experiment beyond-5G connectivity in order to enhance safety on the road. Communications between vehicles and *Vulnerable Road Users (VRU)* are expected to have small delays and to be highly reliable. Cars, *Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV)* and roadside infrastructures are used as edges that provide services closer to the end users as well as to load-balance the computational resources. Furthermore, this Use Case demonstrates the coverage extension to ensure that the connectivity is always covered in the area by having a car that is mobile being exploited as a *Mobile Access Point (MAP)*.

6.1.1 Detailed Stories

The two stories planned for the Smart Highway Use Case take place in two locations: Belgium for Story 1 and Germany for Story 2.

Story 1 - VRU Detection at the highway exit: The story emphasised on the point of view of the driver of a car that is about to enter an intersection from the highway exit. The intersection is used by cars, as well as VRUs. All road users should be aware of each other so that navigational decision can be taken more carefully as well as to avoid any sorts of accident. The car that is exiting the highway can detect the presence of the VRUs by obtaining the information from the existing cars on the intersection that also forwards the information towards the roadside infrastructures, or the *Roadside Units (RSU)*. The car that is already in the area can capture the presence of the VRUs from LiDAR or camera. At the same time, the VRUs also send a beacon to all road users about their presence. In this sense, the overall vision about the scenario and any harmful situation is amplified, bypassing any obstacle (e.g., bridges, buildings, or trees) in the way. A subcase of Story 1 is the case of an accident on the highway, where temporarily, a group of moving users with dynamic demands, are clumped and stress the telecommunication network. The accident occurs near a highway exit road, where cars can choose either to leave or to wait alongside, forming a traffic jam. Thus, the use case involves cars not moving at the same speed, needing assistance from MAPs. Ensuring connectivity to these cars also protects rescuers, who are VRUs in the context of this UC.

Story 2 - Distributed situation knowledge in shared traffic spaces: This story focuses on the efficiently distributed situational awareness and knowledge through the exchange of (processed and/or raw) sensor information between vehicles and RSUs and VRUs to increase road safety and improve traffic flow in shared traffic spaces. In shared traffic spaces, VRUs are recognized through the vehicle-installed sensors (camera, LiDAR, etc.), the camera sensors are mounted on the RSU and the pedestrian's smart device app, and this information is shared with the vehicle and the RSU, which act as a MAP. Then, the *Local Dynamic Map (LDM)* is defined based on the shared information. While analysing the VRU's movement and trajectory in real time on the LDM, it is possible to predict dangerous situations in shared traffic spaces and display warning messages on the vehicle's screen and the VRUs' app in real time to increase road safety.

6.1.2 Services – Human centric applications

The VRUs are equipped with a UE that can sense the presence of other road users. This UE takes the form of a lightweight device that can visualize a LDM that can pinpoint a real-time location of all the road users.

6.1.2.1 Story 1: VRU Detection at the highway exit

In scenario 1 that is referent to the story 1, we provide a human centric application which has the objective to generate dynamically a LDM of the exit of a highway located in Wommelgem, Belgium. The LDM application has a server-side and a client-side component. On the server-side, the LDM application processes all the sensor data gathered by the Smart Cars and the VRUs and provide as output a single LDM to all involved users. Moreover, the server-side application identifies potentially dangerous situations and triggers warning messages towards the involved clients. In the client-side LDM application, depicted in Figure 113, the map of the specific location of the Smart Highway shows in which the Smart Cars and VRUs are shown for the connected clients. Moreover, in case of a dangerous situation, a notification is triggered to the connected users.

Figure 113: LDM App mock-up

The LDM application has the following features:

- VRU and Car detection and location information;
- Notification of obstruction, or warning between road users.

In the accident sub-story, we consider that MAPs are able to adapt to time-varying user behaviour, taking into account i) user mobility, ii) interference, iii) time-varying user traffic and iv) changing scenarios. In this context, we exploit the Dual-Attention Deep Reinforcement Learning algorithm for Multi-MAP 3D Trajectory Optimization in Dynamic 5G Networks that achieves real-time behavior by learning to perform distributed assignment of MAP-user positions. This algorithm also calculates the MAP paths without centralized user's clustering feedback, as presented in D4.3 [9] and [47].

6.1.2.2 Story 2: Distributed situation knowledge in shared traffic spaces

In scenario 2 that is linked to story 2, the human-centric application basically aims to increase road safety by recognizing VRUs at the roadside and predicting dangerous situations. For this purpose, RSU application is being developed that runs on NVIDIA Jetson AGX Orin device

servicing as edge computing. Also, a mobile application for pedestrians that can be linked with RSU is also being developed.

The RSU application in D6.3 has been updated to include MAP-enabled VRU data transfer functionality, as shown in Figure 114 with the following features:

- VRU detection and location information estimation on the road from the camera sensor installed in the RSU;
- Activate/deactivate a MAP feature for RSU;
- Activate/deactivate data transmission so that VRUs detected in RSU can be updated in real time on the LDM of the cloud server.

Figure 114: The RSU application:(a) deactivation of MAP and VRU broadcasting (b) activation of MAP and VRU broadcasting

The vehicle's On-Board Unit (OBU) application has been implemented with the following features as shown in Figure 115:

- Detect VRUs from the camera sensor installed in the front of the vehicle;
- Activate/deactivate a MAP feature for RSU;
- Activate/deactivate data transmission so that VRUs detected in RSU can be updated in real time on the LDM of the cloud server;
- Displays safety alarms around the vehicle predicted from LDM.

Figure 115: The OBU application: (a) deactivation of MAP and VRU broadcasting (b) activation of MAP and VRU broadcasting, safety alarm in case of dangerous situations around the vehicle

The LDM application running on the cloud server has been implemented with the following features, as shown in Figure 116:

- Monitoring for the network status depending on the activation of the MAP functionality of RSUs and vehicles;
- Adjusting for the map area according to the expansion of the communication coverage and VRU detection area;
- Monitoring for the packet size and latency transmitted from RSU and OBU;
- Real-time integration of vehicle location received from OBU and VRU location information received from VRU app;
- Using the traffic information of LDM to predict situations such as collision risk and send appropriate warning messages to drivers and pedestrians.

(a)

(b)

Figure 116: The LDM application: (a) when MAP of 1 RSU is only activated (b) when MAP of 1 RSU and 1 vehicle are activated (i.e., coverage extension), plotting the packet size and latency

The VRU mobile application based on Android OS, which is compatible with Android 6.0 or higher, has also been updated as shown in Figure 117: and has the following features:

- By logging in with a unique ID, RSU recognizes it as a unique VRU user;

- VRU (e.g., pedestrian, cyclist) location can be obtained using the Android smartphone's onboard GPS transceiver;
- The acquired location information is transmitted to the RSU in real time, including its unique VRU identifier;
- It receives a warning notification from RSU when there is a risk of collision predicted in LDM;
- A warning notification icon and a description of the situation are displayed on the screen.

Figure 117: VRU mobile application (a) when VRU is in a safe distance from the vehicle (b) when the vehicle is approaching but at a distance that does not pose threat to the VRU (c) warning screen when the vehicle is at a dangerous distance

6.2 Scenario Setup

6.2.1 Story 1 setup

6.2.1.1 Pilot setup

On the Belgian site, the execution took place in Wommelgem, near the city of Antwerp. The intersection is a junction between a national road and E313 highway in the form of a roundabout, as depicted in Figure 118. The highway on top of the intersection is equipped with an

RSU, as seen in Figure 119, capable of transmitting signals through short range communication towards road users. The roundabout connects to the exits of the highway.

Figure 118: Location of the UC on map (Belgium site)

Figure 119: Physical location of the UC (Belgium site)

The Use Case required several devices used such as:

- Cars with connectivity features (MAP and UE), sensors (LIDAR, GNSS) and computing capabilities (NVIDIA Jetson, general processing unit);
- Lightweight UE for VRUs;
- RSU with connectivity and edge computing capabilities.

As for the software, the UE and Cars are provided with an LDM application that can visualize the situation of the environment.

6.2.1.1.1 Remote processing data centre

The remote processing data centre is located outside of the Smart Highway (Figure 120). This asset gives the experimenters the capability of hosting the LDM application in servers with more processing power than the hosts placed at the edge such as the OBU and the RSU. Besides having more computing power, the Cloud provides a different setup network wise, since it increases the network latency of the LDM application. Therefore, the trade-off between computing power and network resources can be used as input to the research of the

project partners. For instance, the distributed intelligence algorithm could use hosts with different capabilities in order to maintain the QoS of the LDM application.

Figure 120: Remote processing data center (Belgium site)

6.2.1.1.2 V2X Platform

The *Vehicle to everything (V2X)* platform is composed of a car equipped with an *OBU*, and a *RSU* located on E313, a highway located in Wommelgem, Belgium. The platform can be used for experiments on V2X connectivity and edge computing. The units on the platform have communication modules capable of transmitting signals via short range, either cellular V2X (C-V2X, via PC5 side link interface) or ITS-G5 (WiFi based technology), and long-range, via 5G. Also, GNSS receivers are installed on the OBU in order to capture the location. In addition, both OBUs and RSUs can offer distributed computing features due to a powerful *General-Purpose Processor (GPP)*. More details about the RSU and the OBU are described below.

6.2.1.1.3 RSU

Figure 121 illustrates the RSU located on E313, a highway located in Wommelgem, Belgium. Each RSU consists of a large electrical cabinet which houses all the different modules of the RSU. These include modules for wireless communication, modules for local processing on the RSU and modules that allow the RSU to be managed and, if need be, recovered remotely. This RSU contains hardware and communication modules to provide V2X communication experience such as Ettus USRP N310, Mikrotik wAP LTE kit, and Cohda Wireless MK05 RSU.

Figure 121: RSU on E313 highway

6.2.1.1.4 Smart cars

The Smart cars of the Smart Highway are equipped with an OBU and a MAP. This MAP can be instantiated and activated automatically by an internal (e.g., GPS position) or external trigger, depending on the communication needs. In essence, the MAP acts as an access point that supports several wireless communication technologies, e.g., small 5G gNodeB system-in-a-box, to which other UEs can connect. This allows for high bandwidth data communication between vehicles, without the need for external infrastructure. The OBU is composed of processing capabilities and sensors that enable environment monitoring by the cars. To enable the processing capabilities, the OBUs counts with an Nvidia AGX Xavier. Moreover, the smart cars are equipped with LiDAR sensors, CAN-BUS, and GNSS receiver.

Figure 122: IMEC's experiment car with On-board Unit

6.2.1.1.5 The accident sub-use case

The accident scenario takes place in the same highway junction described in Section 6.1.2.1. However, we have implemented the above-mentioned Dual Attention algorithm in simulations only. In addition, we have made animated videos showing the cars motion and the UAVs trajectories towards their optimal positions.

6.2.1.2 Smart Highway – Story 1 implementation

6.2.1.2.1 DEDICAT 6G architecture components

While the architecture and the components have been introduced in UML diagrams in D2.3 [2], herein we focus more on the functional components.

6.2.1.2.2 UC4 specific components

The UC specific components detail in this section were described in the UML diagrams present in D2.3 [2]. Below, we briefly present a table of the UC-specific components identified during the UML diagrams specification.

Table 17: UC specific μ Services and components involved in UC4 – Scenario 1

Component	Description
V2X Application μ S	Part of the LDM application that is placed on the edge of the network for low-latency communication
V2X Communication Module	Responsible for sending sensor data for the LDM application in the cloud and also serving as client for the driver in the Smart car
GPS	Sensor responsible for informing geographical position of the Smart car or of the VRU
VRU App	Client application for VRU GPS information gathering, LDM and notification display
LiDAR	Sensor responsible for scanning the perimeter of the Smart car and sending the monitored data for the LDM application to be processed
LDM	Application responsible for building the Local Dynamic Map (LDM) and for dangerous situation identification

6.2.1.2.2.1. Implementation of accident sub-case

The simulation study takes place in a standard situation where temporarily, a group of moving users with dynamic demands, are clumped and stress the telecommunication network. We chose the highway section located in Belgium mentioned in Section 6.2.1.1

6.2.1.2.2.2. Scenario

Figure 123: Location of the original scenario

The scenario starts with an accident occurring near a motorway exit slip road, where cars choose either to leave or to wait alongside, forming a traffic jam. Depending on their choice, cars are not moving at the same speed and start to need the assistance of Mobile access points.

Figure 124: Scenario Area

6.2.1.2.2.3. Proposed Solution

Architecture

In this context, we exploit the Dual-Attention Deep Reinforcement Learning algorithm for Multi-MAP 3D Trajectory Optimization in Dynamic 5G Networks which achieves real-time behavior by learning to perform distributed assignment of MAP-user positions. This algorithm also calculates the MAP paths without centralized user's clustering feedback as presented in D4.3 and [47].

With this aim, we equip multiple MAPs with a custom Deep Reinforcement Learning architecture that embeds the well-known attention mechanism:

Figure 125: Dual-Attention-PPO architecture

In this architecture, each MAP collects information from its neighbourhood, including other MAPs and cars to calculate its next decision. This information is exchanged through messages received and sent by the MAPs and cars on the highway. Every entity shares its position and computes its relative position with a neighbouring set of other entities. By fixing the neighbourhood size and so the number of messages needed to take a decision, the proposed solution is scalable, decentralized and the Deep Reinforcement Learning core makes the solution dynamic and adaptive to handle multiple situations with the same AI weights. The training process and the exploitation phase are detailed in algorithm 1 and 2 in Annex 2.

Message exchange mechanism

With a network continuously changing, it is essential to set up a cooperation mechanism via a multi-agent coordination of deployed MAPs, which follow the same objective not to drop system performance [41]. In that scope, we propose to exchange messages between MAPs and we complete the framework with a Dual-Attention architecture that complements the standard Deep Reinforcement Learning framework:

Figure 126: Attention mechanism applied to message exchange

Specifically, each time a MAP needs to take a decision for its next move, it gathers surrounding UEs information and information of other MAPs. In that context, the attention mechanism is a prioritization of incoming messages that can be learnt depending on the context and network changes (Figure 126). Thus, each MAP is able to adapt its current strategy and its attention to other MAPs depending on the context. For instance, as described in Figure 126, UAV 0 is paying more attention to UAV 1 to take its decision, meaning that choices made by UAV 1 have a significant impact on UAV 0 decisions.

6.2.1.2.2.4. Parameters

We deploy 3 MAPs providing downlink connectivity to 25 cars moving at the same time on the 200m-by-200m scenario Area. These MAPs are equipped with a 28GHz directive mm-wave antenna with 10beams to provide connectivity to a neighbouring set of cars with a bandwidth of 500MHz (antenna gain is provided at Annex 1). In order to perform the training phase of MAPs 3D trajectory management, we performed 50 000 Monte-Carlo runs where MAPs are collecting messages from 15 neighbouring cars and all other MAPs with a learning rate of $l_r = 1.e^{-4}$ and gamma hyper parameter $\gamma = 0.6$ for neural networks of size 128 contained in 8 attention mechanisms in parallel. In Deep Reinforcement Learning, the

gamma parameter governs the number of predictions the model generated for the future. A gamma of 1 implies that the model aims to predict the future over an infinite time horizon, whereas a gamma of 0 provides a vision solely based on the instantaneous moment. We selected a value of 0.6 to enable the MAPs to anticipate short-term changes in the network while not assigning too high a value to uphold the stochastic nature of the environment.

Concerning communications, each established link between a MAP and a car suffers path-loss, shadowing and fast-fading effects which depend on *Line of Sight (LoS)* conditions:

$$PL(t) = p(t)PL^{(LOS)} + (1 - p(t))PL^{(nLOS)}$$

Where $p(t)$ is the LoS probability and $L^{(LOS)}$, $PL^{(nLOS)}$ defined as:

$$p(t) = (1 + \alpha e^{-\beta(\theta(t)-\alpha)})^{-1}$$

$$PL^l = 20 \log\left(\frac{4\pi f_c d(t)}{c}\right) + \chi_l, \text{ with } l=\{LOS, nLOS\}$$

where α and β are environment dependent parameters, θ the angle between the MAP and the car, f_c the carrier frequency, $d(t)$ the 3D distance between the MAP and the car, c the light velocity and $|\chi_l|$ the large-scale shadowing that depends on the LoS conditions.

Figure 127: Example of scenario sequence (from left to right: MAPs deployed; Coverage extension to users; traffic jam appearing while, coverage extension maintained)

We assume that each MAP is connected to a macro base station that is providing a large enough backhaul link.

6.2.1.2.2.5. Results

For the proposed highway scenario, we compare our solution with a centralized cluster approach. Every 50 steps, the network gathers all UEs positions to perform a clustering with parameter number set to the number of deployed MAPs. In addition, a Path-Planning algorithm pilots UAVs to the computed positions. This solution is really expensive for a dynamic scenario where clusters need to be re-computed every time the network topology changes and does only consider the geographical aspect without its effect on communication as, for instance, with the path-loss.

In order to highlight the MAP adaptability in the attention method, we propose to simulate the highway scenario with and without the accident with the model weights calculated without accident (without any re-training procedure). Comparison of sum-rate performance is shown in the following Figure 128 and Figure 129.

Without accident

Figure 128: Example of non-accident scenario and simulation sum-rate between the AI and the Benchmark

The MAP fleet is able to ensure better performance compared to the centralized benchmark method.

With accident

Figure 129: Example of accident scenario and simulation sum-rate between the AI and the Benchmark

The MAP fleet is able again provides better performance compared to the centralized benchmark method. Moreover, it ensures similar enhanced performance no matter the scenario in the highway environment (accident) without any re-training procedure vs the case without accident.

6.2.1.2.2.6. Conclusions

In this experimentation, we proposed an adaptive AI algorithm to manage dynamically the positions of Mobile Access Points over a highway. In this scenario, the proposed solution addresses an accident case where the concentration of users requires additional coverage to provide a higher capacity. The simulation shows that with a single set of AI model (trained in a general context), the attention model is able to perform better than a centralized approach over time. This experimentation highlights the necessity for modern telecommunication networks to tackle dynamic users and shows that the deployment of mobile access points arises as a perfectly balanced solution.

6.2.1.2.3 Interfaces

This section presents the hardware interfaces available in the Smart Highway testbed. More information about function components interfacing were in WP2 deliverables and in D6.2. The interfaces group for this Use Case is composed of RSU, OBU, and the VRU Smartphone. Moreover, details for their interfaces are detailed in Table 18.

Table 18: Hardware interfaces for components on the Smart Highway – Scenario 1

Component	Hardware Interfaces
Roadside Unit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wi-Fi 802.11b/g/n network interface @ 2.4 GHz • SDR: Ettus USRP N310 • ITS-G5: Cohda Wireless MK05 RSU • LTE-V: Cohda Wireless MK6c EVK • 2x antenna connector (connected to 5.9GHz antennas) • Internal GNSS receiver (connected to a GNSS antenna mounted inside the RSU) • 1x 1GigE Ethernet port for data communication and management of the device • Mikrotik wAP LTE kit
Onboard Unit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wi-Fi 802.11b/g/n network interface @ 2.4 GHz • 8x 1Gbit/s ports • C-V2X PC5 (Qualcomm 9150), Bandwidth 10 MHz, 2 C-V2X antennas, 1 GNSS antenna, Security; SXF1800 FIPS 140-2 level 3 compliant • LTE Category 4 (150Mbps downlink, 50Mbps uplink), Internal antennas with support for optional TS9 external antennas
Smartphone	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wi-Fi 802.11b/g/n mobile hotspot @ 2.4 GHz / (5 GHz) • B5G modem support as network interface (currently @ 3.5 GHz)

6.2.2 Story 2 setup

6.2.2.1 Pilot setup

The demonstration took place at the TU Chemnitz campus and focused on sharing VRU information on the road in an extended coverage area using an RSU and a vehicle's OBU), as shown in Figure 130.

Figure 130: Physical location of the UC (Germany site)

6.2.2.1.1 RSU platform

The final configuration of the RSU prototype hardware is shown in Figure 131. The RSU serves as an edge AI computer, capable of processing AI algorithms locally, and can detect and estimate VRU from images from the camera sensor in milliseconds without an Internet or cloud connection. It is an NVIDIA Jetson AGX Orin, an embedded device equipped with a GPU core for processing AI algorithms, and the camera sensor uses a BASLER acA2440-35uc. The RSU prototype hardware includes a USRP N321, a software-defined radio for communication between cloud servers, VRUs and vehicles, and the USRP N321's communication is handled in Intel NUC. Key specifications for each device are described in Section 6.2.2.2.2 of D6.2.

Figure 131: RSU prototype hardware configuration

6.2.2.1.2 VRU application

An initial version of the VRU app was implemented on the Android OS and described in D6.1 and D6.2. The VRU app has been slightly updated in D6.3 to expand coverage by adding the ability to find RSU or vehicle MAP. The GUI of the VRU application is the same as Figure 79 in D6.2. The main function of this VRU application is to use the GPS transceiver built into the Android smartphone to transmit the pedestrian's current location in real time to the LDM on the cloud server, and to receive notifications from the LDM about dangerous situations such as collision risk. A warning message then appears on the screen, accompanied by an audible alert or vibration.

6.2.2.1.3 Local Dynamic Map

In D6.2, the initial LDM application ran on the RSU, but in D6.3 it has been moved from the RSU to the Cloud Server and has been slightly updated for 'DEDICAT 6G architecture FCs (e.g., Load Balancing FC)'.

The CPU and GPU specifications of the Cloud Server where the LDM application operates are Intel Core i9 2.4GHz and Nvidia GeForce RTX 3080, respectively. The Cloud Server has been built with LAMP (Linux, Apache, MariaDB, PHP), the LDM application is implemented based on Python3 and QT5.

The architecture of the LDM is illustrated in Figure 132 and is defined based on the following components:

- LDM database: It is built with a MariaDB-based database to store dynamic data for the fourth layer;
- LDM database interface: It is a PHP-based database interface for performing *Create/Read/Update/Delete (CRUD)* operations for *Structured Query Language (SQL)*-type DB;
- LDM application programming interface: It is implemented in Python 3 with a set of functions to interact with the database, including input, computing and output interfaces.
 - o Input
 - Add VRUs: It is new or updated information about VRUs received from the RSU, the vehicle's OBU, and VRU app. The information of VRUs is updated in the fourth layer of LDM;
 - Collect network status: It collects the network MAP status of RSUs and OBUs. The first layer of the LDM, the static map, is updated accordingly;
 - o Computing
 - Load/update static map: It loads/updates a static map for the first layer of the LDM. Google map data are used in D6.3;
 - Predict collision risk: It estimates the collision risk between VRUs within a coverage area:
 - o Output
 - Notify warning: It notifies a warning message to vehicle drivers and VRUs on the road through the OBU screen and VRU app, respectively.

Figure 132: Architecture of the LDM

6.2.2.1.4 Vehicle platform

As shown in Figure 133, TUC's research vehicle, the BMU i3, was used for the final pilot of the UC4. The vehicle is equipped with an OBU and sensors such as RADAR, LiDAR, FIR, NIR, MobileEye, and GNSS for autonomous vehicle implementation. For UC4, the OBU program is implemented based on NVIDIA Jetson AGX Orin and the USRP N21 device is also equipped with SDR-based communication devices in order to extend the communication coverage.

Figure 133: TUC vehicle platform

6.2.2.1.5 End-to-End Network

Connected vehicles and RSUs can use IEEE 802.11p for *vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V)* and *vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I)* communications. The widespread deployment of connected vehicles and RSUs on the road and the introduction of autonomous driving applications significantly increases the need for network coverage scalability.

Figure 134: End-to-End Network for UC4

In UC4, USRP devices that can perform the MAP role are installed in the RSU and OBU to configure an end-to-end network between the vehicle, RSU, VRU, and (V2X) Cloud Server as shown in Figure 134. RSUs and connected vehicles can be used to extend the network coverage area for V2X applications.

6.2.2.1.6 Sensing node network

The sensing nodes are edge devices that collect information about the devices with short range radio technologies (WiFi and Bluetooth) enabled in their coverage area. These devices use 5G to communicate with a backend service which uses sensor nodes' data to estimate the number of VRUs. The system works under the assumption that most VRUs carry a mobile phone or a wearable device, which is usually the case.

Figure 135: High-level architecture of IoT Sensing Nodes network.

The network of sensing nodes generates occupancy heat maps in the area. These maps can contribute to the construction of a global map of VRUs and cars present in a given area (LDM). This provides context awareness to prevent risk situations for VRUs and vehicles.

Furthermore, sensor nodes offer a backup connection service that allows whitelisted devices to use them as if they were access points. This feature is not evaluated in the Use Case, though.

The sensor nodes are an enhanced version of the TTI People Counter device. People Counter has been enhanced with 5G connectivity for low latency data exchange with DEDICAT 6G μ S.

The device consists of four main components: power supply, People Counter, 5G router, and antennas (Figure 136). The main function of the sensor node is to capture the messages exchanged via WiFi and Bluetooth by the surrounding devices to extract information suitable

for the estimation of the devices present in the coverage area. The information extracted by the sensing nodes is the MAC information of the radio interfaces and the *Received Signal Strength Indicators (RSSI)*. After applying preliminary filters, this information is published to the DEDICAT 6G μ S using MQTT protocol. The information is stored in a database and used by the μ S application to generate heat maps with estimates of the coverage area occupancy, and to generate statistics and trends.

Figure 136: Sensor node parts.

The μ S consists of a backend and frontend applications for context awareness functionalities. The backend receives the data from the Sensor Nodes, applies information filtering algorithms and stores it in its database. It also serves functionality for retrieving database information and for generating occupancy estimates. On the other hand, the frontend application (Figure 137) allows Sensor Nodes supervision, visualisation of historical data in graphs and table format, data exportation, and occupancy heatmap visualisation.

Figure 137: Sensor Node DEDICAT6G μ S frontend.

6.2.2.1.6.1. Proof of concept

The sensor node network is part of the “Distributed situation knowledge in shared traffic spaces” (Story 2). Here it is used as an additional data source for the LDM generation. The sensor nodes are not autonomous and require power from the electrical grid for their

operation. This aspect meant that it was not possible to deploy the nodes on the German site due to difficulties in obtaining installation permits. Therefore, the installation for validation was carried out at the Science and Technology Park of Cantabria, Spain, where obtaining the necessary permissions for its installation was more straightforward. In total, 7 sensor nodes were deployed: 2 at the TTI facilities and 5 along a street in the Park, situated on street lights (Figure 138).

The validation scenario is part of Isabel Torres Street in the Science and Technology Park of Cantabria. This street is mainly used by workers of this area of the Park and by students coming to a university also located in the Park. This street is close to and parallel to a motorway, so it is also expected, albeit to a lesser extent, to take records of devices travelling along the motorway.

The scope of the validation encompasses both the correct functioning of the sensor nodes during the deployment period and the correct functioning of the μS in storing data, map generation, and displaying logs. The sensor nodes were deployed at the end of May 2023 and are still installed at the time of writing. The validation period is set from the 1st of June 2023 to 30th of November 2023.

Figure 138: Location of the Sensor Nodes deployed in the Scientific and Technology Park.

During the validation period, the correct operation of the 5 nodes deployed in the street was checked weekly. This task was carried out through the μS website, where for each sensor node it is indicated when was the last time each sensor node was active, and when was their last transmission. In addition, each unit sent a copy of its internal log daily to an e-mail address enabled for this task. Occasions were detected in which Sensor Nodes were not sending data. These cases were due to power cuts due to factors external to TTI.

The nodes were configured to activate every 10 minutes. That is, every 10 minutes the nodes wake up, scan devices accessible via WiFi and Bluetooth, and send the results of the operation to the cloud μS . In October, an analysis of the data stored in the database was carried out in order to check whether the consumption on the 5G SIM cards was correct or whether duplicate data was being sent. The result of this study was that the nodes were not sending duplicate data and the billed consumptions were correct.

Figure 96 shows the number of dispatches per day for each Sensor Node during the validation period. Set to 10 minutes, under normal coverage conditions they make 288 dispatches per day. This is due to the fact that the Sensor Nodes make a dispatch on activation and a final dispatch with the scan results. The gaps in the series are due to poor coverage conditions or power outages in the equipment.

Figure 139: Daily data sends per Sensor Node.

6.2.2.1.6.2. Conclusions

During the validation period, the different functionalities of the Sensor Nodes and the microservice for visualization of influx and map generation have been checked. The Sensor Nodes have been in operation for the 6 months of validation without any incident (due to malfunction) as well as the microservice. The following are conclusions and future perspectives obtained from the experience on three key aspects of the deployed system.

During the validation period, the Sensor Nodes were configured to scan and transmit data every 10 minutes. Depending on the application, this period may be considered high. For example, for UC4 itself where real-time information is required to preserve safety in critical road areas. However, since a joint integration was not finally carried out in Germany, the tests were maintained with a period of 10 min, a reasonable period for the generation of heat maps in the validation area. With the current system, it has been verified that the minimum response time is 1 minute. This is because the time required to activate the communication interfaces, perform the scans, send data and deactivate the interfaces is currently approximately 40 seconds.

Regarding the μS , it has been detected that the response times of the web application when displaying large volumes of records or generating heat maps are not optimal. For the exploitation of these services, we reviewed both the technologies that are being applied in the backend and the architecture of the application.

Heat maps are generated based on the RSSI of the signals received by each node. The current approach uses pre-set threshold values to generate the colour scale. Although this is a valid approach, a more adaptive solution could be considered, considering the context of each node to determine the intensity of the crowding around it. For example, an adaptation or training period could be considered in which an "average crowd" is analysed for each day of the week and different times of the day. These values would then be used to adjust the scales shown on the map. These scales would not necessarily remain fixed after the initial adaptation but could be continuously adjusted to fit the evolution of the Nodes' context.

Continuing with this idea of establishing a training period, it would be interesting to explore the functionality of predicting the influx of people through the generation of statistical or ML models. This functionality would be interesting, for example, for route management systems or predictive network resource management.

6.2.2.2 Smart Highway - Story 2 implementation

6.2.2.2.1 DEDICAT 6G architecture components

The detailed functional decomposition of the interconnection of this Use Case (Germany site) into DEDICAT 6G architecture and platform is finally described in D2.3 [2] and started from the implementation perspective for UC4 in D6.1. Table 19 provides a mapping of the functionality of the DEDICAT 6G architecture FCs to the architecture of end-to-end.

Table 19: Mapping of the functionality of the DEDICAT 6G architecture FCs

DEDICAT 6G architecture FCs	Description	Smart Highway implementation (Germany site)
Dashboard FC	Used to interact with Operation Manager to manage the deployment and management of DEDICAT 6G components.	RSU, OBU, LDM
AuthN FC	Responsible for granting the RSU, OBU, VRU apps access to the DEDICAT 6G platform.	Cloud server
CEDM FC	Communicates with NODM FC to collect network status information and to enable and disable MAP of RSU and OBU to perform the coverage extension.	RSU, OBU, LDM
IDDM FC	Receives information about ENs and μ S and then provides results to Service Orchestrator FC and Dashboard FC.	Cloud server, LDM
μ S/FC Repository FC	Stores the uploaded μ S related to the Smart Highway such as the V2X Application μ S and the Sensing Node μ S	RSU, Cloud server, OBU
EC Policy Repository FC	Stores the Edge Computing policies related to the Smart Highway.	Cloud server
μ S/FC Registry FC	Provide information on the V2X Application μ S and the Sensing Node μ S	RSU, Cloud server, OBU
EN Registry FC	Provides information on the Edge Nodes such as RSU, OBU that can be exploited for intelligence distribution.	RSU, Cloud server, OBU
Service Orchestrator FC	Receives recommendations from the IDDM FC and acts over the ENs in order to orchestrate the μ S and FCs deployed over the Smart Highway.	Cloud server, LDM
EN Status Agent FC	Provides monitored information about the current status of the edge nodes registered to the platform.	RSU, Cloud server, OBU

μ S/FC Status Agent FC	Provides monitored information about the current status of the μ S being executed in the use case infrastructure.	RSU, Cloud server, OBU
NW Awareness FC	Provides information on the network status in the Smart Highway infrastructure.	RSU, OBU, LDM
NW Status Agent FC	Provides monitored information about the current status of the network in the Smart Highway infrastructure.	Cloud server, LDM
NW Optimization FC	Optimizes the network for the coverage extension component based on the current status of RSU and OBU.	Cloud server, LDM
Load Balancing FC	Receives monitored information about the edge nodes and the microservices and acts over the Smart Highway infrastructure in order to balance the network and processing load over the multiple hosts available	Cloud server, LDM
NODM FC	Receives recommendations from NW Optimization FCs in order to reconfigure the network and meet the desired objectives for V2X communication	RSU, OBU
μ S/FC Awareness FC	Receives information from a group of μ S/FC Status Agent FCs and publishes it to the rest of the FCs available on the DEDICAT 6G platform	RSU, Cloud server, OBU
EN Awareness FC	Receives information from a group of EN Status Agent FCs and publishes it to the rest of the FCs available on the DEDICAT 6G platform	RSU, Cloud server, OBU

6.2.2.2.2 UC4 Story 2 - Specific components

The UC-specific components detail in this section were described in the UML diagrams present in D2.3 [2]. Below, we briefly present the table of the UC specific components (i.e., μ Services) identified during the UML diagrams specification in D2.3.

Table 20: UC-specific components in UC4 – Scenario 2

Component	Description
Sensing Node μ S	Sensor responsible for scanning the coverage area of the sensing node, discovering connected and non-connected VRUs and sending the estimated crowd data for the LDM application to be processed
V2X Application μ S	Fusion of collected sensor values as part of an LDM application that is placed on RSU and OBU networks for low-latency communication.
V2X Communication Module	Responsible for transmitting real-time collected sensor data for LDM applications and also serves as a client for the driver in the vehicle.

Component	Description
GPS	Provides information for V2X Application μ S as a sensor that collects the geographic location of smart cars
LiDAR	Provides information on V2X Application μ S with a sensor that scans the surroundings of a smart car
VRU App	Client application to collect GPS-based location information of VRU and display notifications
LDM	Application responsible for building LDM (Local Dynamic Map) based on data collected from RSU, OBU, and VRU App and identifying dangerous situations

6.2.2.2.3 Interfaces

This section describes the interfaces between components implemented for UC4 related to Scenario 2.

Table 21: Interfaces for components on the Smart Highway – Scenario 2

Component	Interfaces
Roadside Unit	HW: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wi-Fi 802.11b/g/n/ac network interface @ 2.4 GHz / 5GHz • SDR (Software Defined Radio) using USRP N321 • Camera sensor interface SW: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python 3 and C++ based implementation • GUI (QT5) • Local Dynamic Map
Vehicle / Onboard Unit	HW: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wi-Fi 802.11b/g/n/ac network interface @ 2.4 GHz / 5GHz • SDR (Software Defined Radio) using USRP N321 • Camera sensor interface • LiDAR sensor interface SW: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python 3 and C++ based implementation • GUI (QT5) • Sensor fusion interface for LiDAR and Camera
Smartphone / mobile devices	HW: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wi-Fi 802.11b/g/n/ac mobile hotspot @ 2.4 GHz / (5 GHz) • 5G modem support as network interface SW: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Android OS

Component	Interfaces
Sensing Node devices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Java or Kotlin based implementation
	HW: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wi-Fi 802.11b/g/n/ac mobile hotspot @ 2.4 GHz / (5 GHz) • Bluetooth 4.2, BLE • 3G/4G (possible 5G) • ETH 10/100 Mbps SW: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linux OS • Java / Python based implementation

6.2.3 Final integration report

The paragraph below describes the use of WPs outcomes in the UC4 and the contribution per partner done during the period M15 to M24.

6.2.3.1 Description of WPs related outcomes used in UC4

Mechanisms for Dynamic Distribution of Intelligence (WP3):

The distributed intelligence research has been applied to this use case in order to optimally find the best placement for the LDM application components. Furthermore, a custom monitoring system provides periodically metrics for the Distributed Intelligence Decision Making in order to maintain the QoS for the vehicular application in means of network latency, jitter and throughput.

Mechanisms for Dynamic Coverage Extension (WP4):

Context awareness strategy for tracking VRUs. Implementing and integrating to work with a local dynamic map running on RSU. The “Dual Attention” mechanism described in D4.3 was here applied to a relevant scenario.

Mechanisms for Security, Privacy and Trust (WP5):

WP5 provides security and trust and integrate it to the use-cases.

6.2.3.2 Description of contribution per partner participating in UC4

CEA: CEA has contributed to the MAP deployment strategy to provide appropriate QoS connectivity to mobile nodes and demonstrated some features through simulations.

IMEC: IMEC has contributed to the research network slicing mechanisms for enabling the dynamic connectivity required for the distribution of intelligence. Furthermore, we have provided distribution of intelligence algorithms to optimize the utilization of resources as well as the network service requirements.

IMEC has provided research on coverage extension applied to the smart highway use case by publishing papers on the area of spectrum sensing and mechanisms to trigger the extension of the coverage to users of the network that are not in good network coverage. Finally, IMEC designed the VRU warning app and successfully tested it at its premises.

TTI: TTI has provided research on context awareness using people counting techniques based on sensing characteristics of short-range radio technologies of the general-purpose devices to assist in coverage extension tasks.

TUC: Implementation of a VRU tracking strategy from WP4, which described in D4.2, and Local Dynamic Map in RSU application.

TUC also contributed to integration of LDM mechanism that can extend coverage for tracking VRUs in conjunction with VRU mobile app.

ATOS: ATOS has contributed to orchestrate the deployment of FCs/ μ Services (Intelligence distribution) in the Edge Nodes by using the Service Orchestrator-Edge Orchestrator Interface (K8s). ATOS has contributed to orchestrate the establishment of network services/slices (OSM interfacing) to enable 5G-based connectivity when coverage extension is needed. This has been done adapting the orchestration engine developed in the project to provide the functionalities of the NFV-O Controller, defined in D2.4.

VLF: Implementation of private permissioned blockchain and collection of smart contracts for security and trust management framework, described in D5.2

6.2.3.3 Description of external assets used in UC4

The vehicle platform ("CARAI"), from TUC partner, has been used, developed and upgraded in various domestic and international projects over the past few years. The platform is continuously evolving and has developed from three individuals, stand alone and unconnected vehicles to an increasingly integrated platform where all three vehicles as well as the RSU are connected via V2X.

In the context of DEDICAT 6G and in particular in UC4, a range of software and hardware components are being specifically developed and implemented. These components were developed from scratch and do extend the pre-existing CARAI platform.

TUC has also set up the "Smart Rail Connectivity Campus (SRCC)", at the core of which is a Cellular Testbed covering a Research railway line over a 25km stretch with a dedicated slice, in the 700MHz Band, on a commercial 5G-SA Network and comprising of two smaller (~6km and ~2km, respectively) campus networks that provide a highly adaptable cellular research infrastructure with two SA cores and OpenRAN capabilities. The aim was to deploy the CARAI platform in the SRCC testbed once the DEDICAT 6G extensions have been finalised and tested.

Moreover, IMEC has deployed a smart highway testbed (and a smart car) over the past few years that was used in an overall fashion for UC4 and the 5G portable testbed used specifically for the coverage extension mechanism. The Smart Highway was used to validate the VRU application developed in the context of UC4 and to monitor the KPIs associated to the 5G network and V2X communications. The RSUs found along the route of the Smart Highway were

6.3 Evaluation and final results

6.3.1 List of KPIs, target values and gain

6.3.1.1 KPIs and target values

Table 22 presents the list of KPIs related to the Smart Highway Use Case, describing the evaluation method and defining the target values:

Table 22: UC4 – Smart highway KPIs list

KPI ID	Description	Target value	Baseline
UC4_KPI1	5G Vehicular-Based MAP Downlink/Uplink Throughput	$\geq 16\text{Mbps}$	In accordance with ETSI Technical Specification 122 186 V16.2.0 (2020) [38] related to Service requirements for enhanced V2X scenarios (Video sharing between UEs supporting V2X application): 10Mbps
UC4_KPI2	5G Vehicular-Based MAP Latency	$\leq 20\text{ms}$	In accordance with ETSI Technical Specification 122 186 V16.2.0 (2020) related to Service requirements for enhanced V2X scenarios (Video sharing between UEs supporting V2X application, Lower degree of automation): 50ms
UC4_KPI3	LDM Response time from identifying dangerous situation until emitting warning message	$\leq 100\text{ms}$	The V2I target network latency is 100 ms taking as baseline the work done by Petrov et al [39].
UC4_KPI4	LDM network throughput downlink/uplink usage	$\geq 16\text{Mbps}$	The target throughput both in downlink and uplink for the usage of the LDM application is 16Mbps as experimented in the laboratory with the current LiDAR sensor and application developed.

6.3.1.2 Evaluation and results

Table 23: UC4 – Results obtained and gain

KPI ID	Evaluation method	Result	Gain
UC4_KPI1	Tests were set up where a known data stream was sent over UDP (e.g., using iperf) from the MAP to the UEs over 5G link. At the UEs, the throughput of the received data streams is measured of the application over a small-time window (e.g., per second)	Figure 140 (Germany site) Although latency increases, target network throughput is possible. (Germany site)	

UC4_KPI2	<p>Tests were set up where data packets are sent (over UDP or ICMP) from the MAP to the UEs over 5G link. The timestamp is logged at the sender when the packet is transmitted and at the receiver, when the packet is received. The sender and receiver should be time synchronized within 1ms accuracy</p>	<p>Figure 141 (Germany site) From the average latency is close to the target. (Germany site)</p>
UC4_KPI3	<p>The logging of the timestamp of the dangerous situation identification on the LDM application is crossed with the receiving of the notification on the VRU application and in the V2X communication module</p>	<p>The tests were successful after the implementation and testing of the VRU app developed by IMEC. The timestamp logging is indeed identical between the LDM and VRU application. Figure 142 (Germany site) From the average response time is close to the target. (Germany site)</p>
UC4_KPI4	<p>The downlink and uplink throughput are monitored on the components of the Smart Highway such as OBU, RSU and Cloud in order to validate that the minimum throughput for the use case is being met by the network solutions</p>	<p>After extensive testing on the Smart Highway, our measurements show that the minimum throughput is 32MB/s which conforms to the network solution implemented. Figure 140 (Germany site) Although latency increases, target network throughput is possible. (Germany site)</p>

6.3.1.2.1 Evaluation of VRU detection VIA RSU and Connected car

In UC4 (Germany site), the core algorithm for detecting VRUs on the road is designed with a structure in which the RSU and OBU run independently and only the results are transmitted to the cloud server, so specifications with large network throughput are not required. In other words, for V2X applications, the high data rate (sensor raw data) transmission process from the RSU and the OBU is not necessary, and only a few tens of kilobytes of data are transmitted. The results of measuring the average latency according to the data rate transmitted from the RSU to the cloud server running the LDM application are shown in Figure 140.

Figure 140: Comparison of average latency according to data rate

The data rates in Figure 140 are 1Mbps, 5Mbps, 10Mbps, 15Mbps, and 20Mbps, and the average network latency measured at the time were 18.42ms, 42.13ms, 66.85ms, 98.23ms, and 126.58ms, respectively. As the data rate increases, the network latency increases and exceeds the target value of UC4_KP12, but it shows that network throughput exceeding 16Mbps, which is the target value of UC4_KP11 and UC4_KP14, is possible. However, it notes that the actual transmitted data is small in UC4's V2X application, so it satisfies the UC4_KP12.

Figure 141 shows that UC4_KP12 measured the latency of packets sent from the RSU and the OBU to the Cloud Server (LDM application) via MAP. The average values of latency measured at the RSU and OBU are 17.43ms and 19.39ms, respectively.

Figure 141: Latency from the RSU (a) and the OBU (b) to the LDM via MAP

The latency of packets transmitted from the VRU application is shown in Figure 102 of UC3. These latencies can be affected by the size of the transmitted packet and the distance of the UE from the MAP. It should be noted that the task of detecting VRUs around the road is performed completely independently by the RSU and OBU, and only the results are transmitted to the LDM of the cloud server, so the actual transmitted packet size is not large in UC4 (German site).

The LDM average response time required to identify dangerous situations on the road from VRU information acquired from the RSU and OBU is shown in Figure 142.

Figure 142: LDM Response Time

The average response time in Figure 142 is 97.98 ms, and this value may vary depending on the number of acquired VRUs and the specifications (e.g. CPU, GPU, RAM, etc.) of the Cloud Server on which the LDM application runs.

6.3.1.2.2 Evaluation of Coverage extension evaluation

Figure 143 below shows the demonstration setup diagram for spectrum sensing based IMEC's 5G MAP configuration in this Use Case. It shows an interference generator, a smart car that is equipped with a 5G portable unit, and another car with a 5G UE. The interference generator is used to demonstrate the spectrum sensing based RAT configuration capability. This can be done by using ITS-G5 and/or C-V2X PC5 transmitters.

In the first smart car, a USRP connected to a host machine is used to sense the spectrum. The technology recognition, traffic characterization, and multi-RAT controller described in Section 6.1 are used to sense the spectrum and avoid interference with incumbent V2X transmissions. The RAT controller is used to select a channel based on the interference traffic characterized by the knowledge building process.

The smart car is also equipped with the IMEC portable 5G unit, which is used as a 5G MAP. IMEC has designed and built portable 5G units that allow testing, experimentation, and novel research based on 5G and beyond network technologies. These 5G units consist of both *Commercial Off-the-Shelf (COTS)* and *Software-defined Radio (SDR)* equipment, enabling flexibility for extensions and customization beyond the features offered in 3GPP releases and the capability for end-to-end experimentation involving business-critical and/or mission-critical applications with demanding QoS requirements in dynamic wireless environments.

The portable 5G units can be used both as UE and as an *open-RAN (O-RAN)* compatible base station (small cell) in combination with the 5G core network, either as a system in a box or running the 5G core on a central data server.

Figure 143: Demonstration setup layout for spectrum sensing based 5G MAP configuration in UC4

As shown in Figure 144, the 5G units include:

- The Accelleran O-RAN solution, which provides the Accelleran dRAX lab kit consisting of the software for the *Control Unit (CU)*, the *Distributed Unit (DU)* and the near real-time *RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC)*
- The Benetel outdoor *Radio Unit (RU)* that is O-RAN compatible
- COTS 5G router (5G UE)
- A powerful computing unit with GNSS support and accurate timing synchronization
- A power unit that allows the equipment to run over a battery or the power grid
- An SDR USRP 2943R that can be combined with open-source LTE/5G solutions, such as srsRAN and OAI

Figure 144: IMEC portable 5G unit hardware components

6.3.1.2.3 Evaluation of Distributed intelligence

For evaluation, a use case was crafted of 10 devices and 10 tasks, providing 1010 possible different placements. The networks and additions were built using RLLib [24]. Four objectives were evaluated: Energy, *Worst Case Execution Time (WCET)*, Latency and Bandwidth. For the Deep-Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) approach, Energy and WCET were scalarized as device objective, and Latency and Bandwidth scalarized as network objective. Due to instability and slower convergence, the vector Q-values, proposed by Mossalam *et al.* [22] were not used. We expanded on the existing approaches of the Deep-OLS and Conditioned networks by building them using a Double Dueling DQN, which improves general stability and convergence. The hyperparameters used are found in Table I. The results were compared with a Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II) approach, as proposed in previous research [25]. This algorithm was configured with a population size of 100, running for 1000 iterations. Additionally, a comparison was made with a standard random search, iterating over 1000 possibilities before finishing.

Table 24: Hyperparameters

γ	0.95
lr	0.00001
ϵ	150000
Batch size	32
Buffer size	20000
Weight change interval	10000 steps

All algorithms were generally able to find solutions that satisfied all constraints. Figure 145 represents the average time required to find a single solution. We pooled the Multi-objective reinforcement learning (MORL) algorithms, as they had similar networks and consequently similar inference time. The Cloud solution refers to placing all possible tasks on the cloud, showcasing the traditional approach. The log scale showcases that the proposed MORL approaches outperform the traditional NSGA-II algorithm by a factor 5. Note, however, that both NSGA-II and Random Search depend on the number of iterations to determine timing, whereas the proposed MORL algorithms have static timing and resource usage in nature. More interesting results are found on Figure 146 which shows the average reward over 50 runs. The x- axis shows the weight for the network objective, where a 0 is the corner weight focusing on device objectives and 1 is the opposite corner weight focusing on network objectives. Note that the cloud solution does not satisfy the latency solution and is invalid, being purely shown as reference.

Figure 145: Execution time

Figure 146: Average Scalarized Reward

It is clear that the NSGA-II algorithm finds the optimal solution. This is at the trade-off of consuming considerably more time and resources. The bi-objective Conditioned Network approach comes quite close to the NSGA-II algorithm, which showcases that a trained network is a valid approach in resource-constrained service placement. Interestingly, the neural network generally also finds better solutions in 50 timesteps than the random algorithm does in 1000. This is partially accredited to a light skew in the normalization, making network objectives slightly more valuable. In addition, if a corner weight of the Deep-OLS fails to converge, the subsequent search becomes infeasible. We notice that the conditioned network trained on four objectives succeeds at finding useful solutions but is outperformed by nearly all other approaches. This is likely due to the large jump in complexity between solving for two and four objectives.

The results showcase the brittleness of applying Deep-OLS in practical scenarios. The approach depends on finding the policies for the weight extrema first, but if these values are far apart, the algorithm stops working as expected. In addition, the approach suffers from search space complexity differences. In our scenario, it is considerably easier to optimize for network objectives, by putting all services on the same device, than it is to optimize for device objectives. This mismatch makes it difficult to build an automated Deep-OLS search methodology, as the network objective policy converges considerably faster. We recommend to instead train individual policies with individual hyperparameters per weight and apply OLS on top.

7 Lessons learnt, recommendations and guidelines

Throughout the development of the DEDICAT 6G project, we have seen the importance of connectivity to maintain a good user experience through the four Use Cases as the increase of the safety of users, e.g., First Responders during a response to a disaster or warehouse workers or road users. The correct functioning of the different human centric applications used in the four use cases depend to a large extent on the connectivity associated with this coverage at the site where the situation occurs.

Additionally, to the coverage extension, the project demonstrates the value of resource distribution which delivers the most suitable functions to support communications anywhere.

Finally, it is fundamentally important that intelligent resources distribution and dynamic coverage extension, in the near future, to drive the future of B5G/6G connectivity to make communication resilient and efficient for users, they could be citizens enjoying an event, goods management, First Responders responding to a crisis or road users moving in safety.

The rest of this section outlines lessons learnt, recommendations and guidelines from each of the use cases

7.1 Smart Warehouse Use Case

The ongoing challenges faced by the warehousing industry as a result of the pandemic, has led to a surge in e-commerce-driven demand and a significant growth of goods shipment. Not only has this shift increased the pressure on warehouses, but also it has resulted in a significant rise in inventories. Smart warehousing is key for the proper preservation of goods and consequently of the public health. However, the availability of data from real-time tracking of vehicles and goods as well as novel functionalities that can be supported by B5G/6G technologies along the warehousing and logistic supply chain, enable advanced services reducing operational delays and wastes.

During the pilot and laboratory experimentation of this Use Case, the partners involved in UC1 have demonstrated the value of applying distributed intelligence in an overall Smart Warehousing. Identifying the most appropriate placement algorithm for large-scale experiments is a nontrivial task. Given that execution time grows exponentially with an expanding solution space, achieving optimal performance within an acceptable execution time/latency becomes crucial. Hence, the development of the metaheuristic algorithm for addressing the intelligence functions placement problem was a well thought approach since it succeeds close to optimum solutions in an acceptable time window. Metaheuristics and AI algorithms as described here could be further explored.

Network and data security implemented in UC1 is not a one-time task. It's an ongoing process and continuous monitoring is crucial. ML models must be regularly updated and adjusted based on evolving threats and changes in network behavior. Trust metrics enhances the ability to identify and respond to emerging threats promptly, but only if ML models are trained properly with the latest virus and malware signatures.

Cybersecurity threats will continue to evolve and multiply over the years. Cybercriminals continually develop more sophisticated attack techniques, including polymorphic and metamorphic malware, AI-driven attacks, and targeted attacks tailored to specific device and service. IoT malware attacks have been on the rise in recent years, and this trend is expected to continue. Many IoT devices lack mechanisms for receiving security updates or patches, leaving them vulnerable to known vulnerabilities for extended periods. Even when updates are available, device manufacturers may not prioritize or provide ongoing support, leaving devices exposed to exploitation.

Several key lessons can be learned from this perspective regarding device and data security and risks. Zero-day vulnerabilities pose a significant threat to both IoT devices and networks. Zero-day vulnerabilities are a concern because they represent security flaws that are unknown to the vendor or the public. There are no patches or fixes available when they are discovered by attackers. This gives cybercriminals the opportunity to exploit these vulnerabilities and causing significant harm before they are discovered and patched.

Human error remains one of the major security risks in any network. Educating users about security best practices such as avoiding suspicious links, using strong passwords, and recognizing phishing attempts, can significantly enhance overall network security.

7.2 Enhanced Experience use case

The Enhanced Experience public pilot (Figure 56) took place in Finland on April 16th, 2023. It was organised by UC2 team and held at VTT Oulu premises with a public information and registration link with free of charge. There was 46 registered people from 15 different companies or institutes of which approximately 35 presents during the live event. Many of the participants had strong background and knowledge of the different aspects in mobile network communications as well as network security. 8 different demos were shown simultaneously at the event of which part them influenced to the existing B5G mobile network and caused a need for the DEDICAT 6G solution.

The technical approach of the pilot focused on demonstrating the coverage extension in mass events. In such events the underlying wireless network might be insufficient to fill the large amount of event participants with their active mobile devices. Such users may send live photos or video clips, or even live stream to their friends or social media which stresses especially the uplink capacity of the mobile network. In addition, the users may locate on the boundaries of the event site where the coverage might have lower QoS conditions. In these depicted cases, enhancing the coverage in a predetermined manner or dynamically according to the needs increases the value and reputation both for the event organizer as well as the network operator for establishing high quality settings for the event participants.

As introduced earlier, a mobile robot (MiR) acted as ConnectedCar (MAP) and was instructed to bring enhanced coverage and network capacity for the event participant who was considered to live stream from the site to the edge server for video delivery towards remote spectators. The movement of the MAP was based on both for network QoS and manual override for easier demonstration purposes. As the indoor environment restricted the usage of mmWave radio to demonstrate the IAB to form the backhaul connection towards core network, WiFi 6 technology was used in this context. The network connection with the observed video user was switched between 5G and WiFi when MAP arrived closer to the user without any breaks or stalls in the video stream. 360° camera was used to congest 5G uplink with Smart Glasses. Several video client applications were available to playback the live stream.

Technically- and implementation-wise the pilot demonstration met the expectations and functioned as planned with high number of different components and software implementations. The KPI visualization illustrated how latency and jitter improved when switching from congested 5G network to WiFi with higher capacity. It was observed that the uplink in 5G/mmWave was the bottleneck when streaming from mass events. Network configuration especially in private mobile network context for weighting the uplink more than downlink is one option to improve the performance as shown also in the KPI measurement section. VTT team also surprised a bit how technically "simple" scenario was relatively hard to implement in real network context with real physical devices. Some of the complexity arises from NW

analytics, which requires very accurate time synchronization (minimum 1ms accuracy) via GPS or wired LAN. Thus, crowded mass event scenario re-quires multiple UEs.

Figure 147: Enhanced Experience pilot of UC2

7.3 Public Safety use case

Communications are one of the pillars in crisis management. With the raise of new information and communication technologies supported by 3GPP MCS standards, DEDICAT 6G project brought the opportunity to implement Mission Critical Services with B5G/6G connectivity, with the introduction of micro-services infrastructure for dynamic resources distribution at the Edge and automated coverage extension. The outcomes were evaluated on real life scenario in Airbus premises trough 2 pilots and demonstrated at the French National Fire-fighter Congress in Toulouse, France. The pilots were the opportunity to evaluate novel tool and means of collaboration as the capacity to make resilient connectivity when the life matters.

It's not about group call communication like legacy TETRA or TETRAPOL technologies but features enhancing situational awareness.

The pilots were open to Airbus stakeholders who have interest in critical connectivity, several visitors representing technical experts, business analysts or solutions providers from Airbus or its partners take the step to visit the Airbus eLab in order to meet DEDICAT 6G partners involved in the UC3 to share about the outcomes of the project and benefits for the Public Safety or PPDR stakeholders. The visitors shared a great interest and positive feedbacks in the project to bring resiliency in connectivity for First Responders. Main interrogation was about the capacity for AGVs to bring extended connectivity in complex environment after a disaster. This point raises an interest to study and participate in the requirement to a possible new product in order to offer a Vehicular Relay for Public Safety.

The coverage extension and human centric applications have been demonstrated at the French National Firefighter Congress in Toulouse, France. This was the opportunity to share the DEDICAT 6G project results in Public Safety Use Case to First Responders. Their main concern is about the connectivity anytime, everywhere, which objective is the protect First Responders safety.

Not only a MCX tool has been evaluated during the pilots and demonstration but a Remote expert tool in collaboration with Optinvent and its Smart Glasses have been evaluated. Main issues after visitors on the booth discussed with project representatives was about the use of smart glasses with helmets. However, the FRs shared positive feedback on this tool embedded in smart glasses and bring possibility to exchange with experts connected remotely and share the decision-making process to avoid mistake and put FRs safety first in the decision.

In terms of the mechanisms and algorithms, the coverage extension optimisation problem was of course a challenging one since it calculates not only the best physical locations of the MAPs to provide the users with connectivity but also the positions of the relaying nodes (MAPs) to pass on the information to the final destination. Dividing the space to squares and using a MIP solution is not suggested because it is computational intractable to check within so many possible locations. A heuristic, AI-based algorithm is suggested for solving a problem like this, and the clustering-based approach implemented here yielded very good results.

In the scope of the robot's autonomous outdoor navigation was another key challenge, in terms of integrating various technologies to achieve precise and reliable robot localization. The Public Safety use case involved navigating a robot in outdoor conditions, where a combination of Real-Time Kinematic (RTK) positioning and visual algorithms, was utilized particularly RTAB-Map, to accomplish the task. Basic experiences gained:

1. Understanding of RTK and GNSS Limitations: In environments like urban canyons, we encountered limitations with RTK due to signal interference and multipath effects from tall buildings. This experience highlighted the importance of understanding environmental impacts on navigation technologies;
2. Adapting with Visual SLAM: To overcome GPS-denied environments, we integrated RTAB-Map, a Visual Simultaneous Localization and Mapping algorithm. This not only provided a backup in the absence of reliable GPS but also offered a more comprehensive understanding of SLAM technologies in real-world applications;
3. Sensor Fusion and Data Analysis: Implementing and fine-tuning RTAB-Map required a deep dive into sensor fusion, utilizing data from LiDAR, cameras, and IMUs. Analyzing and interpreting this sensor data was crucial in diagnosing navigational issues and optimizing performance;
4. Field Testing and Real-World Application: Extensive field tests under varying conditions were invaluable. They not only tested the system's robustness but also provided insights into practical problem-solving and adaptability.

A summary of the corresponding lessons learned based on these experiences is outline below:

1. It is important to understand the strengths and weaknesses of each technology: RTK offers precision, but its effectiveness is environment dependent. Visual SLAM algorithms like RTAB-Map can fill gaps in GPS-denied areas but require careful calibration and integration. A balanced approach, leveraging the strengths of each technology, is crucial.
2. Sensor Fusion: No single sensor or technology is foolproof. Combining data from various sources can significantly enhance accuracy and reliability.
3. Field testing in actual outdoor environments is non-negotiable. Simulated tests can't fully replicate real-world challenges.
4. Be prepared for continuous adjustments and improvements. What works in one environment may not work in another. Continuous updating with new technologies and algorithms for robotic navigation is vital

In terms of AR and the use of smart glasses, we have demonstrated:

1. "MCX" application adapted to ORA-2 smart glasses. This web-based application created by AIRBUS was demonstrated on the ORA-2 glasses to Fire fighter professional public during Toulouse annual meeting held in October 2023 on AIRBUS booth (<https://congres2023.pompiers.fr/>);
2. "Remote Eye" application developed by Optinvent, demonstration of capabilities to partners. This application shows how a remote expert connected to an operator wearing the ORA-2 smart glasses could exchange in real time information such as pictures,

- augmented information, video, audio, map, datasheet, etc. to fulfil maintenance operation remotely in hands free mode for the operator;
3. "Remote Expert" application developed by AIRBUS during EUCNC 2023 event. This application has been developed specifically for fire fighter needs;
 4. "Remote Expert" during Nov 29th pilot in AIRBUS.

Lessons learned from annual Fire fighter congress exhibition held Toulouse France:

- ORA-2 smart glasses demonstration done successfully to a large professional public; part of the audience never saw an AR content overlaying in front of their eyes;
- Hands free AR device has been appreciated as an efficient device to display in real time pertinent information in hands free mode.
- The human centric functionality of the glasses is in line with professional needs to allow them to focus on their work, while feeding them essential information during operation;
- Human-Machine interface on the ORA-2 glasses is a tactile interface (located on the right side of temple) are not useful in emergency where operators have gloves and need their hands for other tasks. The ORA-2 platform allows to use either voice control (using digital Mic) or hand gesture associated to the camera and specific software. Since the camera is essential to capture and to stream video, the best solution is to use voice control through dedicated software working preferably online. Local voice control program works, but they are less efficient as limited in calculation process for voice and message recognition;
- The ORA-2 as a glasses-made device cannot be used by fire fighters as is, since the smart glasses need to be integrated into existing fire fighter helmet (Figure 148). The ORA-2 system components (electronics, display, battery, GPS, Camera, etc.) embedded in the glasses should be modified to fit within the helmet available space. This task goes beyond DEDICAT 6G project objectives and should imply a close technical work with the helmet manufacturer for both integration and qualification. When the ORA-2 system is integrated into the helmet, they will be part of it and should follow strict qualification procedure for the helmet itself. This being said, Optinvent conducted design work on this integration. The design work shows that it is possible to integrate the ORA-2 hardware platform inside the helmet.

Figure 148: Design of smart glasses integration to First Responders helmet

Figure 148 depicts on the left the design work to integrate the ORA-2 hardware platform inside the helmet. The module shown in front of the user is the transparent display that will fit within the helmet space. However, the full integration should be managed in close collaboration with helmet manufacturer for security and qualification matters. The right part of Figure 148 depicts a photo of the current MSA Gallet F1 helmet used by French fire fighters.

As for the Integrated Access and Backhaul concept, the proposed platform validates IAB and Multi-RAT technologies to be used for coverage extension. The radio platform demonstrates interesting results and reaches a TRL of 5. Nonetheless, the actual implementation (split 7.2) creates limits on the latency and data rates. Further developments to make it a ready-to-market product are estimated to be about 5 years.

7.4 Smart Highway use case

For TUC: the third phase was to integrate components and services from WP3 and WP4 , following the Architecture from WP2, into UC4, as shown in Figure 111. We completed the implementation of the V2X communication module based on the USRP N321 and applied it to UC4. we pursued and concluded an evaluation and measurements of the developed component's performance and KPIs using the implemented V2X communication module. In addition, we prepared as proof-of-concept demonstration a video of UC4 at the German site. The evaluation further proves the validity of the approach taken in DEDICAT6G. Based on the results obtained, this approach (i.e. DEDICAT6G) provides a suitable platform for further investigations into provisioning of (future) services that rely on distributed analysis and decision making.

For IMEC: relating to coverage extension, the focus was on the configuration and coexistence of different RATs based on the technology recognition. Moreover, for the topic of distributed intelligence, using the MORL techniques described, further objectives, such as privacy and security, and constraints, such as software requirements, can easily be added. The impact of these added objectives and constraints were evaluated, and the scalability of the proposed techniques validated. The trained models could be further improved to reduce resource consumption and inference time, using network pruning. In addition, our proposed technique can be extended to larger and varying computer networks or application chains such as the LDM for the Smart Highway. This can be tackled by using the strengths of *Graph Neural Networks (GNNs)*, which allow neural networks to process graphs of any size.

For CEA: we proposed an adaptive AI algorithm to manage dynamically the positions of Mobile Access Points over a highway, in particular an accident case where users are concentrated in an area then requiring additional telecommunication coverage in terms of capacity. The simulation shows that with a single set of AI model (trained in a general context), the attention model is able to perform better than a centralized approach over time. This experimentation highlights the necessity for modern telecommunication networks to tackle dynamic users and shows that the deployment of mobile access points arises as a perfectly balanced solution.

TTI proposed an Edge Node and backend service for crowd estimation and heatmap generation based on the exploitation of short-range radio technologies and 5G. After the 6-month validation period, the system has proven to perform its functions robustly. The following lessons learned deal with improvements that would make the system more efficient:

- The response times of the web application when handling large data volumes or generating heat maps are not optimal. This indicates a need for a review of the backend technologies and application architecture for handling large data volumes more efficiently.

- The current approach to generating heat maps uses pre-set threshold values based on the Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) of each node's signals. While this is a valid approach, a more adaptive solution could be considered. A potential future work could be to develop an algorithm that dynamically adjusts the threshold values based on the context and historical data. This work can already be done using the data obtained during validation.

8 Conclusion

This deliverable reports the overall activity conducted in WP6 on the integration pilot setup and testing of the four use cases: Smart Warehousing (UC1), Enhanced Experience (UC2), Public Safety (UC3) and Smart Highway (UC4) from the start of WP6 in month M8 to the end of the project.

The DEDICAT 6G project's pilots, evaluating and demonstrating dynamic mechanisms based on real-life scenarios, allowed the partners to present the future of 5G/6G connectivity and improvements compared to state-of-the-art communications. The pilots' demonstrations and events supported the promotion of the technologies increasing awareness among stakeholders, and potentially facilitating broader adoption of such novel technologies in the future.

Through the Smart Warehousing use case (UC1), the project demonstrated the value of increased warehouse automation powered among others by distributed intelligence to achieve optimal performance of execution time of diverse tasks and processes, responding to ongoing and new challenges warehousing and logistic industries are facing.

Coverage Extension Mechanisms were demonstrated in the Enhanced Experience (UC2) and Public Safety (UC3) use cases. The Enhanced Experience use case demonstrated the benefit brought by the DEDICAT 6G mechanisms during a large event, allowing not only attendees at the event, but also the ones following the event remotely to enjoy a great experience of the show despite of the number of simultaneous connections.

Through the Public Safety use case (UC3), the project demonstrated how Coverage extension mechanisms can facilitate continuum in critical communications for First Responders, especially for the communicants at the edge of the communication chain and improving the safety of First Responders who responded to a crisis. Two testing events were carried out in realistic conditions at Airbus premises, while the outcomes were also presented among others to stakeholders during one of the major events in France dedicated to Response to crisis and disasters, bringing the hope of more resilient critical communications when it matters and supporting a new era of tools allowing for the decision making process to become faster.

The fourth use case, Smart Highway, (UC4), demonstrated the benefit of AI algorithms to manage MAPs positions in a highway and the value to share a real-time situation to all road users to make road travelling safer. This use case showcased the benefits of DEDICAT 6G mechanisms for efficient connectivity and consequentially the potentials for an era of safer roads for everyone.

The pilots provided valuable data to technologies providers with the challenges they were faced in coverage extension and resources distribution, creating opportunities for pre-standardization activities.

In conclusion, DEDICAT 6G use cases have highlighted, through the pilots and demonstrations, the potential of the platform's novel technologies in enhancing the capabilities and user experience of stakeholders in various life situations.

9 Annexes

Annex 1

Figure 149: Simulated TX/RX antenna gain radiation pattern for an array of 20×20 (diag 1), 10×10 (diag 2), 5×5 (diag 3) elements operating at 28 GHz [42]

Annex 2

Algorithm 1: Training algorithm

Input: Init model weights w , environment state \mathcal{S}

- 1 **for** $run = 1 \dots run$ **do**
- 2 Randomly deploy agents in the cell
- 3 Agents receive UE centroids location $c_i(0)$
- 4 Agents compute their neighborhood $\mathcal{N}_i^{(r)}(0)$
- 5 Agents gather messages from $\mathcal{N}_i^{(r)}(0)$
- 6 Agents compute their state representation $\phi_i^{(r)}(0)$
- 7 **for** $t = 1 \dots T_e$ **do**
- 8 Agents select and execute $a_i(t)$
- 9 Agents receive their nearest assigned centroid $c_i(t)$
- 10 Agents receive rewards $r_i(t)$
- 11 Update the environment state \mathcal{S}
- 12 Agents compute their neighborhood $\mathcal{N}_i^{(r)}(t)$
- 13 Agents gather messages from $\mathcal{N}_i^{(r)}(t)$
- 14 Agents compute their state representation $\phi_i^{(r)}(t)$
- 15 **end**
- 16 Compute (ϵ_1, ϵ_2) -clipped proximal loss
- 17 Performs gradient descent step with Adam
- 18 Update policies $\pi_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{M}$
- 19 **end**

Output: policies π_i

Figure 150: MAPs training process

Algorithm 2: Testing algorithm

Input: Load model weights w .
Trained agent policies π_i

```
1 for run = 1...run do
2   for  $t = 1 \dots T_c$  do
3     Agents computes their neighborhood  $\mathcal{N}_i^{(r)}(t)$ 
4     Agents gather messages from  $\mathcal{N}_i^{(r)}(t)$ 
5     Agents computes their state representation  $\phi_i^{(r)}(t)$ 
6     Agents select and execute  $a_i(t)$ 
7     Update the environment state  $\mathcal{S}$ 
8     Compute  $R(t)$ 
9   end
10 end
```

Output: $E[R(t)]$

Figure 151: MAPs exploitation algorithm

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